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Two- and Three-Dimensional Osteometric Variability of the Foramen Magnum in Modern Humans

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born on October 15, 1995, in Oranienburg, Germany

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Disclaimer

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The publication was written by the author alone. No funding was provided. Ideation, sample collection, data collection, data analysis, coding, interpretation, text writing, editing, figure generation, and image generation were solely done by the author if not stated otherwise.

All sources have been cited following academic standards. A citation program was used for the generation of the reference list (i.e., Endnote). This list has been thoroughly checked after its completion for grammatical errors, duplicates, and missing entries.

The supervisors have been contracted frequently to report updates on the progress. None of their feedback was included word for word and has been cited as personal communications.

The edited thesis and its supplementary materials, including raw data, were made openly and freely available to serve the public interest in scientific topics and to improve the accessibility of generated scientific outputs. The act of publication thus does not necessarily or primarily follow no commercial interest.

The original thesis was written in English, which does not represent the author's first language. The edited and published versions have been checked for grammatical errors by others and artificial intelligence. Some grammatical errors might still be present within the text. The correction did not change any of the text contents.

The author strictly distances himself from any abuse by others with respect to racist, sexist, ableist, or any other inhuman, intolerant, and discriminating attitudes of his results or collected data, which are made available here. This work promotes scientific ideas that strongly contradict narratives of pseudoscientific socio-biological hierarchies between disproved, non-existing human races and biological sexes. The author follows common scientific terminology that is meant to be inclusive and representative of the state-of-the-art in his field of research. In this sense, the term "sex" refers to the primarily binary concept in biology comprising individuals of biological female and male sexes. The term sex does not equal the sociocultural concept of gender, which, unfortunately, is often confused among many studies in foramen magnum research (among other studies).

The thesis and its supplementary materials deal with the analysis of real human remains and, furthermore, contain selected images of real human remains and three-dimensional digital surface scans. All work done to retrieve data and process and analyze this data was done in compliance with the granted permission to access and study human remains, with official best practice guidelines by different accredited institutions, and with the authors own ethical considerations. The author has worked on multiple occasions with human remains, and he assures that his research interests are always subject to ethical restrictions. These aspects are further discussed within the text.

Eidesstaatliche Erklärung zur selbstständigen Durchführung und Anfertigung der vorliegenden Abschlussarbeit

Hiermit versichere ich, dass ich vorliegende Arbeit selbständig verfasst und nur unter Verwendung der angegebenen Hilfsmittel und Quellen angefertigt habe. Die Stellen meiner Arbeit, die dem Wortlaut oder dem Sinn nach anderen Werken entnommen sind, habe ich in jedem Fall unter Angabe der Quelle als Entlehnung kenntlich gemacht. Dasselbe gilt sinngemäß für Tabellen, Karten und Abbildungen. Diese Arbeit ist weder in Teilen noch im Ganzen Gegenstand eines anderen Prüfungsverfahrens.

Dominik Göldner

Tübingen, 30.03.2022

Dear Reader,

if you are reading this, it is probably because you are interested in foramen magnum research. The monographic text you have downloaded comprises my master thesis, which I have written and submitted. If I remember correctly, I started this project in early 2021. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic (beginning in 2019), I had to face several difficulties, such as accessing the Berlin collections to study the human remains, I needed for my analysis or staying in contact with my supervisors. It took me around one year to finalize the thesis, but I made it. On April 21, 2022, I finally defended it successfully in front of my supervisors, university staff, fellows, students, and friends at the Eberhard Karls University in Tübingen, Germany.

The reasons I chose this topic were simple: first, I wanted to use my knowledge gained about geometric morphometric analysis, which I gained during my master's program at the University of Tübingen. Furthermore, since my bachelor's time at the Free University in Berlin (2015–2019), I have had a close connection to the anthropological collections in Berlin, where many of my close friends and dear colleagues are working. Over the years, I have myself worked at these collections for quite some time as a student assistant for Miss Barbara Teßmann, M.A. (anthropologist and curator of the Rudolf-Virchow Collection in Berlin), and Prof. Johannes Krause (at that time director at the Max-Planck-Institute for human evolutionary history in Jena, Germany). During all that time, I learned not just a lot about physical anthropology but also about the Berlin collections and their colonial history. Soon, I became an advocate of provenience research – the attempt to study the origin of collection inventories to identify their origin, the circumstances and rightfulness of their acquisition, and their justified repatriation. As a result of my work on the collection, I wrote my bachelor thesis at the Free University based on a small sample of fifteen early medieval skulls from Germany. Unfortunately, a few years ago, the conditions and perspectives of provenience research were not looking very promising, despite growing media and public attention. But things became better with time, and I sincerely hope that my small contribution was of little help.

For my master thesis in Tübingen, I requested access to the collection again, but this time with a much more ambitious project for which I aimed to analyze a diverse global sample that needed a lot of planning and previous provenience research because I was adamant about not including any remains that originated from unethical, illegal, and inhuman contexts. With my intended analysis, I was hoping to evaluate whether my chosen methodology would be suitable to be applied to human remains housed in such collections and could help to infer basic biological information like sex, age-at-death, or population affinity. Often, there is not a

lot of well-documented information on the origin of human remains in these old collections. Here, physical anthropology can play a vital role in the identification of these deceased individuals. However, these methods, which are based on the analysis and utilization of human variation, must constantly be newly developed, validated, and adjusted to cover the wide and diverse human variation. I specifically chose the foramen magnum because this is a cranial structure that is most often preserved, even when the remains are heavily fragmented. The anthropological collections in Berlin predominantly contain skulls and an indescribable amount of fragmented human remains, which accumulated over decades due to mishandling and a lack of care. As I was screening and sorting through dozens of kilos of such unsorted, fragmented remains as a volunteer at the collections, I realized that many of the larger fragments were occipital bones, or at least parts of them, with often more or less intact foramina magna. Provenience research on such isolated and completely contextless fragments appears almost desperate, but I wanted to try to give some of the remains a minimum of what I, as a white, privileged, and biologically male scientist, understand as dignity. Sadly, what I call “minimum attention” and care is often the maximum most of these fragments will ever face.

I was illusive enough to believe that the research on the foramen magnum would be relatively simple since this structure can easily be measured and analyzed. My assumption was soon proven wrong: there was a magnitude (100+ articles) of published osteometric research with unstandardized methodology, making the complex difficult and complex. It took me months to work through this mountain of literature, and even more time to grasp the amount of deeply rooted biases in this field of research. It was a stressful time, but eventually things became much clearer, and I, overall, consider this a valuable experience and have learned a lot. Now, more than one year after completion, I must say that I hope to never again conduct an analysis based on poorly documented and, more importantly, human remains from archeological or even colonial times. The level of uncertainty that comes with the obtained data is tremendous, but I have done my best to report reasonable results.

Despite my own doubts, I am more than happy to tell you that exactly one year after my thesis defense, I was awarded the Rudolf-Virchow Prize 2023 for the best master thesis by the BGAEU, together with two other recent graduates. The ceremony took place at the Free University in Berlin on May 21, where all three of us briefly presented our results to a small audience. I want to thank the BGAEU for this award and express my gratitude to everyone who was there. This award further allows me to publish my summarized thesis, titled “Reshaping Foramen Magnum Research. Analyzing foramen magnum variation in modern humans using 2D osteometry and 3D geometric morphometrics: A master thesis summary” in the 2023 edition of the *Mitteilungen der Berliner Gesellschaft für Anthropologie, Ethnologie und Urgeschichte* (ISSN: 0178-7896; publisher website link: <https://www.logos-verlag.de/cgi->

[bin/engtransid?page=/bgaeu.html&lng=deu&id=](#)), I am planning to continue working on this critical research, following up with one or two publications focusing on different aspects of foramen magnum research in more detail. To follow my later work, please be aware of ORCID: 0000-0002-5432-3273 or contact me via email at d.goldner@protonmail.com.

~ The Author (Norma frontalis) ~

Dominik Göldner, Tübingen den 15.10.2023

About the Author

Dominik Göldner, born October 15, 1995, in Oranienburg, Germany, received his German A-level (Abitur) at the Eduard-Maurer-Oberstufenzentrum in Hennigsdorf bei Berlin in 2015. During his school years, he already found a deep interest in the social and natural sciences, most importantly archaeology and paleontology. As a teenager, he went “fossil hunting” on several occasions and learned how to prepare them. Before the age of 18, he did several personal internships at different locations and institutions, including the Natural History Museum in Berlin and the Free University in Berlin (FUB).

Shortly after finishing school in 2015, he began studying prehistoric archaeology at the FUB and graduated in 2019. During this time, he worked on several archeological excavations in Germany (Heuneburg, Bullenheimer Berg, Hornow, Flatow), Italy (Pompeii), and Romania (Cornesti-Iarcuri). He also worked as a research assistant for Miss Barbara Teßmann, M.A., and Prof. Dr. Johannes Krause (Max-Planck-Institute Jena) at the anthropological collections in Berlin. During his undergraduate studies, a profound interest in physical anthropology and bioarcheology awakened in him. As there were no classes taught in this subject at FUB, he acquired the basics through self-study and the mentoring provided by Barbara Teßmann. This led to the topic of his bachelor thesis, focusing on the estimation of sex and age as well as taphonomic markers on a small sample of early medieval skulls from Alsheim, Germany. He successfully submitted his thesis in 2019.

After graduation, he moved to Tübingen, Germany, to start a master’s program in archeological science, specializing in paleoanthropology. Here, he not only consolidated his anthropological knowledge but also started to learn geometric morphometrics and advanced imaging techniques. Over the years, he worked as a research assistant for several researchers (including PD Dr. Sireen El-Zaatari, Dr. Armando Falcucci, and Ass.-Prof. Dr. Hugo Reyes-Centeno) on a variety of projects, ranging from dental microwear and geometric morphometric analysis of lithic artifacts to imaging analysis of tattooed Philippian mummies. Some of these resulted in publications. During this time, he also worked as an osteoarcheologist for the German Archaeological Institute at an excavation in Tayma, Saudi Arabia.

He submitted and defended his master thesis in 2022, after which he continued his job as a research assistant for Dr. El-Zaatari. He simultaneously started an apprenticeship at the University Clinic in Tübingen to become a state-certified radiological technologist and deepen his technical and practical knowledge of medical imaging techniques. However, I continued to work on different research projects and publications. In May 2023, he was awarded the Rudolf-Virchow Prize for his master thesis. Dominik plans to start his dissertation research after completing the apprenticeship.

Curriculum vitae (Excerpt)

Name: Dominik Göldner
Date of Birth: 15.10.1995
Place of Birth: Oranienburg, Germany
Degrees (2023): Master of Science, M.Sc. (2022)
Bachelor of Arts, B.A. (2019)

Education

Since October 2022 Apprenticeship as state-certified medical technologist for radiology at the MTR-School, University Clinic Tübingen, Germany

April 2019 – April 2022 Master of Science at the Eberhard Karls University Tübingen, Germany, Department for Archeological Science, Institute for Paleoanthropology (final grade: 1,3)

Oct. 2015 – March 2019 Bachelor of Arts at the Free University Berlin, Germany
Department for Ancient Studies, Institute for Prehistoric Archaeology (final grade: 1,1)

Aug. 2012 – June 2015 Eduard-Maurer-Oberstufenzentrum Hennigsdorf, Germany
(final grade: 1,8)

Excavations

Feb. – April 2020 Tayma, Saudi-Arabia

September 2018 Flatow, Germany

August 2018 Hornow, Germany

July 2018 Pompeii, Italy

August – Sept. 2017 Cornesti-Iarcuri, Rumania

August 2016 Heuneburg, Germany

March – April / 2016 Bullenheimer Berg, Germany

Research Jobs

Seit April 2021	Research assistant for Sireen El-Zataari, PD, Eberhard Karls University Tübingen, Institut für Paläanthropologie. Tübingen Germany
April 2021 – Oct. 2021	Research assistant for Dr. Armando Falucci, DFG-Project „Untersuchungen zu technologischer Variabilität und kultureller Dynamik im frühen Jungpaläolithikum südlich der Alpen“, Tübingen, Germany
Sept. 2019 – July 2020	Research assistant for the DFG-Center for Advanced Studies: Words, Bones, Genes, Tools, Tübingen, Germany
Feb. – April 2020	Research assistant for the German Archaeological Institute, Orient Abteilung, Project: „Funeräre Landschaften“, Tayma, Saudi-Arabia
June 2017 – Jan. 2019	Research assistant for the Max-Planck-Institut für Menschheitsgeschichte Jena, Germany
2016 –2017	Student assistant for B. Teßmann, M.A., Berlin, Germany
2016 – 2017	Student assistant for Dr. Cornelia Becker, Free University Berlin

Scholarships and Awards

May 2023	Rudolf-Virchow-Förderpreis 2023 by Berliner Gesellschaft für Anthropologie, Ethnologie und Urgeschichte (500 €)
April 2021 – April 2022	Deutschlandstipendium (3.600 €)
July 2018	Stipendium des PROMOS-Programms, DAAD (500 €)

Thesis Works

- Master thesis 2022 *“Two- and Three-Dimensional Osteometric Variability of the Foramen Magnum in Modern Humans.”* At the Eberhard Karls University Tübingen. Supervised by Prof. Dr. Katerina Harvati, Dr. Alexandros Karakostis, and Dr. Hugo Reyes-Centeno, PD
- Bachelor thesis 2019 *„Die frühmittelalterlichen Schädel aus Alsheim in der Rudolf-Virchow-Sammlung. Versuch der Rekontextualisierung eines Gräberfeldes aus interdisziplinärer Sicht.“* At the Free University Berlin. Supervised by Prof. Dr. Elke Kaiser and Dr. Georg Roth

Publications (First Author)

D. Göldner, [in preparation]. Reshaping Foramen Magnum Research. Analyzing foramen magnum variation in modern humans using 2D osteometry and 3D geometric morphometrics: A master thesis summary and research review. *Mitteilungen der Berliner Gesellschaft für Anthropologie, Ethnologie und Urgeschichte* 43 (2023).

D. Göldner, 2023. Two- and Three-Dimensional Osteometric Variability of the Foramen Magnum in Modern Humans. Master Thesis 2022. Eberhard Karls University Tübingen. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10038819

D. Göldner, A. Deter-Wolf, 2023. DStretch Tattoo Protocol: Full step-by-step protocol for identification and visualization of tattoos on preserved archaeological remains using the ImageJ plugin DStretch. DOI: 10.17504/protocols.io.n92ldp52xl5b/v1

D. Göldner, 2022. ArchaeoScale Protocol: Inserting digital scale bars into scientific images – Full step-by-step guideline for anthropological and archaeological specimen photography v2. DOI: 10.17504/protocols.io.8epv5j1p6l1b/v1

D. Göldner et al. 2022. Practical and technical aspects for the 3D scanning of lithic artefacts using micro-computed tomography techniques and laser light scanners for subsequent geometric morphometric analysis. Introducing the StyroStone protocol. *PLoS ONE* 17(4):e0267163. DOI:10.1371/journal.pone.0267163

D. Göldner et al. 2022. StyroStone: A protocol for scanning and extracting three-dimensional meshes of stone artefacts using Micro-CT scanners, v2. DOI: 10.17504/protocols.io.4r3l24d9qg1y/v2

D. Göldner, 2021. Anthropologische und taphonomische Analysen zur Befundrekonstruktion der frühmittelalterlichen Alsheim-Schädel in der Berliner Rudolf-Virchow-Sammlung. *Mitteilungen der Berliner Gesellschaft für Anthropologie, Ethnologie und Urgeschichte* 41 (2020), pp. 171-186. DOI: 10.30819/mbgaeu.41.14

D. Göldner, 2019. Without context. Recontextualization of Early Medieval Skulls from Alsheim in the Rudolf-Virchow-Collection. Konferenzposter. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8136729

Publications (Co-Author)

J. Keppeler, **D. Göldner** et al. Documentation and image enhancement of decorative tattoos in human mummified remains: The Case of Apo Anno (Benguet, Philippines). Digital Applications in Archaeology and Cultural Heritage (in preparation).

A. Falcucci, **D. Göldner** et al. 2022. Bringing shape into focus: Assessing differences between blades and bladelets and their technological significance in 3D form. Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports 43(8):103490. DOI: 10.1016/j.jasrep.2022.103490

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Zenodo:

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Important Technical Notes

This master thesis has been published on Zenodo as an open-science document to make it publicly available. If not stated otherwise, all figures have been created by the author (DG). All copyright rights belong to the authors. Please cite this thesis accordingly (see below).

The entire study was initiated, proposed, planned/structured, and executed (data collection, analysis, and interpretation) by the author. Occasionally, feedback was obtained from the supervisors. Their input has been cited accordingly. Note that this study was not peer-reviewed otherwise.

The present document represents a reworked version of the original master thesis. However, the text and its contents have not been significantly changed after submission at the university in March 2022 and prior to final publication on Zenodo in October 2023. Texts have only been changed to correct grammatical errors. Due to space limitations, the original manuscript displayed only a few within-text figures. The remaining figures had to be attached to the supplementary materials. To increase the readability of the present publication, important figures have now been included in the text. Note that they have retained their original supplementary material figure or table number to avoid confusion and error with respect to within-text figure or table references. The original supplementary materials (S1, S2, and S3) have not been changed at all. They have also been uploaded to the same Zenodo repository as the current PDF file, including the thesis text. They therefore possess the same DOI number. In addition, the thesis raw data have also been published as CSV files within the same repository, together with an explanatory metadata file (S4). The raw data files include the 2D osteometric measurements of the newly collected data from Berlin (S5.1 and S5.2), reported summary statistics of the reference data from the published literature, including the new data (S6), and ZIP container file archives including NTS raw landmark data files for the 3D geometric morphometric analysis (S7.1 and S7.2). Furthermore, specific files generated for the 3D GM analysis have also been published (S8.1 – S10). Lastly, the original master thesis proposal, where the initial study idea and plan were proposed, has been included in the supplementary materials (S11) for interested readers that seek to learn a little bit more about the genesis of this project. The 3D surface scans of the scanned human cranial remains were not made openly available. Likewise, subsequently generated datasets like the Procrustes transformed shape coordinates or the PC scores are not separately published as datafiles, as tables within the original supplementary materials S2 and S3 contain most of this information already. Otherwise, this data can be generated by others using the provided raw data. The R

codes used to perform the analysis and generate the graphs in this study are not yet published. It is planned that they will be published on Zenodo soon.

Also note that since the thesis submission at the university in 2022, new studies about the foramen magnum have been published. Likewise, older studies have been found online that have not been found before by the author. All these studies are not considered here. However, upon closer inspection, it seems not to be the case that any of these studies have reported fundamentally ground-breaking results in foramen magnum research. Likewise, none of these studies have been found to overall contradict the results of the current study.

How to cite this publication and the supplementary materials:

Upon your citation of the supplementary materials, you are kindly requested to insert the respective figure or table number(s) that you are referring to.

Thesis:

D. Göldner, 2023. Two- and Three-Dimensional Osteometric Variability of the Foramen Magnum in Modern Humans. Master Thesis 2022 (edited version). Eberhard Karls University Tübingen. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10038819.

Supplementary Materials S1 – S11

D. Göldner, 2023. Two- and Three-Dimensional Osteometric Variability of the Foramen Magnum in Modern Humans. Supplementary Materials [INSERT SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL NUMBER HERE]: [INSERT FIGURE/TABLE NUMBER OF THE REFERED CONTENT HERE]. Master Thesis 2022. Eberhard Karls University Tübingen. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10038819

Supplementary Materials – List of Contents

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2. Supplementary material – S2 – Materials

→ S2_Göldner_Materials.pdf

3. Supplementary material – S3 – Results

→ S3_Göldner_Results.pdf

4. Supplementary material – S4 – Metadata file

→ S4_Göldner_Metadata_File.txt

5.1 Supplementary material – S5.1 – 2D Osteometric data (all individuals)

→ S5.1_Göldner_OsteometricData_2D_all-individuals.csv

5.2 Supplementary material – S5.2 – 2D Osteometric data (sex-known individuals)

→ S5.2_Göldner_OsteometricData_2D_sex-known-individuals.csv

6. Supplementary material – S6 – 2D Osteometric reference summary statistic data

→ 6_Göldner_OsteometricSummaryStatistics_2D_PublishedReferenceData_summarized.csv

7.1 Supplementary material – S7.1 – Landmark raw data (all individuals)

→ S7.1_Göldner_NTS_raw-landmarkcoordinate-files_all-individuals.zip

7.2 Supplementary material – S7.2 – Landmark raw data (sex-known individuals)

→ S7.2_Göldner_NTS_raw-landmarkcoordinate-files_sex-known-individuals.zip

8.1 Supplementary material – S8.1 – Classifier for 3D GM analysis (all individuals)

→ S8.1_Göldner_Classifier_3DGM_all-individuals.csv

8.2 Supplementary material – S8.2 – Classifier for 3D GM analysis (sex-known individuals)

→ S8.2_Göldner_Classifier_3DGM_sex-known-individuals.csv

9. Supplementary material – S9 – Curveslide file

→ S9_Göldner_Curveslide_3DGM.csv

10. Supplementary material – S10 – WireframeLinks file

→ S10_Göldner_WireframeLinks_3DGM.csv

11. Supplementary material – S11 – Master thesis proposal text

→ S11_Göldner_2021_Master-thesis-proposal.pdf

Original Supplementary Materials – List of Contents

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First, I would like to thank my three supervisors for their interest and dedication towards my study. Their academic advice gave me the support needed to successfully complete this study. A special thanks goes to my dear friends and colleagues, namely Barbara Teßmann, Dr. Bernhard Heeb, Renée Hämmerling, B.A., and Marius Kowalak, at the anthropological collections and State Museums in Berlin. Likewise, I want to officially thank the Berliner Gesellschaft für Anthropologie, Ethnologie und Urgeschichte (BGAEU) and the State Museums in Berlin (SMB). Without their permission to access the collections and their help, this thesis could never have been realized. I want to thank my family and all my friends for being there for me whenever I needed them; without all of you, I would have never come so far. Among these people, probably the most grateful thanks go to my beloved bestie, *Leah Böttger*, M.Sc., who has always been there for me. We have had a great time together in Berlin and Tübingen throughout our time as students, and I feel grateful for every moment. Likewise, I would like to say thank you to all my other flatmates in both WGs during my time in Tübingen, especially Elli, who always gave me valuable support with the R codes and statistical aspects. Many thanks also go to Arianna Weingarten, M.Sc., Maddy McCartin, M.Sc., and Nolan Ferar, M.Sc., for their valuable comments. I also want to thank my friend Malte Loetz, B.A., among all students the greatest of all theoretical thinkers, one of a kind, for his help with the production of the political map. Finally, I would like to thank all the people who helped me throughout my time as a student over the past seven years.

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Abstract

The foramen magnum (FM) is a prominent structure located at the basicranial portion of the occipital bone in modern humans. It serves as a passage for vital tissues that connect the brain with the spinal cord. The morphology of the FM has been of continued interest in physical anthropology, bioarchaeology, forensics, and medical science, and many studies have empirically analyzed differences in FM size and shape between sexes within single populations using traditional osteometric distance measurements and indices, as well as visual shape categorizations. Although many of these studies found significant mean differences in FM size between females and males, other FM studies did not. Studies on differences between populations and landmark-based geometric morphometric approaches, on the other hand, are rare. In this thesis, persisting methodological problems from previous FM research are reviewed and discussed. An alternative, geometric morphometric approach that does not rely on visual and subjective shape assessments is applied and compared to results obtained from traditional osteometric analysis of the same cranial specimens. For this endeavor, new two-(2D) and three-dimensional (3D) data ($n = 98$) as well as published 2D osteometric data ($n = 9,977$) of the FM spanning a wide geographical range were collected and analyzed using uni- and multivariate statistics to estimate FM differences between sexes and populations. The results of this study suggest that even if there are significant differences between sexes and populations, they are small and imposed by large overlaps between the studied groups. Such overlaps reduce the overall utility of FM variables in the osteometric identification of sex and population affinity from unknown human remains in forensic and archaeological contexts. Nevertheless, small trends in mean differences between populations have been documented and discussed. Overall, size, shape, and form variability in FM in modern humans appears to be likely driven by genetic, environmental, and cultural factors, which have not yet been fully clarified.

1. Introduction

The foramen magnum (FM) in modern humans serves a wide range of vital physiological functions and is thus of great interest to different research fields, including evolutionary studies, biology, medicine, and physical anthropology (Ficke and Varacallo, 2021; Richards and Jabbour, 2011; Zdilla et al., 2017). Like many other cranial structures, metric, and non-metric characteristics of the FM in modern humans have been examined for their potential to infer basic information (i.e., age, population affinity or geographical provenience, sex, and stature) from the biological profile (Bruzek and Murail, 2006; Cunha and Ubelaker, 2020; Moore, 2013). Developing such identification methods is, however, an ever-ongoing field

of inquiry. Adequate modern or ethnographic skeletal collections are rare due to factors such as differential preservation, accessibility, and the representativeness of human remains. These obstacles undermine the reliability of any method built upon those samples. Furthermore, derived and validated methods to determine biological parameters should only be applied with great caution to populations other than those included in the reference dataset. This is because intra- and interpopulation differences, secular trends, and age-related changes might lead to systematic biases and lower accuracy rates. The applicability and reliability of existing methods should therefore be rigorously evaluated and, if possible, adjusted to individual populations (Alves et al., 2020; Bigoni et al., 2010; Bruzek and Murail, 2006; Elliott and Collard, 2009; Gapert et al., 2009; Gapert et al., 2013; McDowell et al., 2012; Ramsthaler et al., 2007; Rogers, 1982). Because of these limiting factors and the fragile nature of osteological remains, often fragmented in archaeological or forensic contexts (Gapert et al., 2013; Stojanowski et al., 2002), anthropological research must constantly try to evaluate, validate, and develop methodologies for different anatomical elements to estimate and/or assess parameters of the biological profile (Casado, 2017a; Elliott and Collard, 2009; Gapert et al., 2009; Holland, 1986a, b; Krishan et al., 2016).

In this regard, the FM has been considered to be an ideal structure to study intra- and interpopulation differences (Tran, 2020), as it can be described as a relatively simple anatomical structure that is easy to access, observe, and measure (Holland, 1986b; Wescott and Moore-Jansen, 2001). Its growth across human populations is completed relatively early in life, around the age of 10 (Richards and Jabbour, 2011), after which no significant age-related changes have been observed (Gapert et al., 2013; Wescott and Moore-Jansen, 2001). A preliminary study by Gruber et al. (2009) using human remains spanning from the Late Pleistocene to modern times further suggested no significant changes in its size due to secular processes, giving the impression that the FM could be an evolutionary relatively stable feature. Due to its location at the cranial base, protected by a larger mass of soft tissue and bone structures, the FM is often better preserved in archaeological or forensic contexts (Gapert et al., 2013; Graw, 2001; Stojanowski et al., 2002). Most FM studies so far have largely focused on within-population differences to evaluate its utility to discriminate between sexes (Abo El-Atta et al., 2020; Akay et al., 2017; Burdan et al., 2012; Catalina-Herrera, 1987; Chovalopoulou and Bertsatos, 2017; Gapert et al., 2009b; Ukoha et al., 2011; among many others). Interpopulation differences with regards to the identification of population affinities, on the other hand, have rarely been addressed so far (Holland, 1986a; Manoel et al., 2009; Tran, 2020; Zdilla et al., 2017).

Several methodical issues can be identified across many morphological FM studies. First, the commonly employed approach involving the measurement of a few linear distances is not sufficient to capture the overall shape and form of the FM. Further, high levels of subjectivity in visual FM shape categorization, measurement errors related to different data

collection methods (El-Barrany et al., 2016; Zdilla et al., 2017), the lack of raw data availability, as well as inconsistencies and discrepancies in reported summary statistics, compound the challenges and biases in FM research. This makes it difficult to effectively compile larger comparative datasets to study global patterns of similarities and differences among populations regarding this anatomical structure, not to mention validating the reliability of many previous intra- and interpopulation studies. A proper solution to overcome subjective biases and to capture and preserve shape and form information throughout the statistical analysis of morphological structures are for example landmark-based geometric morphometrics (GM). Multivariate statistical analyses of landmark data have long been demonstrated to reveal more detailed insights into the nature of biological structures than traditional, linear metric and visual, non-metric attempts. Because unique shape and form properties are retained throughout the GM analysis, actual shape deformations can be effectively quantified and visualized helping the assessment and interpretation of the morphological variance within the analyzed sample (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009; Mitteroecker et al., 2013).

This study aims to review the published FM research and to address these problems using two-dimensional (2D) osteometry in comparison with three-dimensional (3D) GM methods. Newly collected FM data from four different modern human populations from Africa, Asia, and Europe are analyzed using both methods to evaluate the potential of the 2D and 3D variables as proxies for the identification of the sex or population affinity of unknown human remains.

1.1 Anatomy and Ontogeny of the FM in Modern Humans

The FM is the largest, singular foramen of the modern human cranium. It is located at the center of the basicranial portion of the occipital bone at the most inferior point of the posterior cranial fossa (Ficke and Varacallo, 2021) (Figs. 1a and 1b). By connecting the cranial base and the brain with the postcranium and vertebral canal, the FM serves as a passage for various vital locomotor, hemo- and hydrodynamic, as well as neurological tissues. In other words, the FM represents an endo-to-ectocranial intersection of the central nervous system and for the blood and cerebrospinal fluid flows in and out the cranium (Ficke and Varacallo, 2021; Richards and Jabbour, 2011). Ectocranially, the FM is surrounded by many different anatomical structures, including the clivus, the lateral parts of the occipital bone, the nuchal plane, the left and right atlanto-occipital condyles (AOC) that articulate with the first cervical vertebra (C1 or atlas), as well as multiple attachment sites for the dura mater, ligaments, tendons of the atlanto-occipital joints and various neck muscles (Fig. 1a). Of particular interest in morphological FM studies of the cranial base are the AOC because of their close spatial and functional relationships to the foramen: their medial portion anterolaterally borders the FM and they have often been observed to slightly protrude into the foramen's space, therefore partially

contributing to the anterolateral shape outline of the FM (Ficke and Varacallo, 2021). The left and right hypoglossal canals, allowing the exit of the hypoglossal or twelfth cerebral nerve, are located towards the endocranial portion of the FM – superior to the middle third of the two AOC and the innermost edge of the FM and inferior of the bilateral jugular tubercles. The hypoglossal nerve and occasionally a third meningeal branch of the ascending pharyngeal artery may also partially run through the FM (Hacein-Bey et al., 2002; Paraskevas et al., 2009; Richards and Jabbour, 2011). From endocranial view, the FM is posteriorly delimited by the left and right posterior cerebellar fossae and the inferior part of the internal occipital crest (Fig. 1b). Its anterior boundaries are the clivus and the left and right jugular tubercles. The cerebellar fossae as well as the lateral parts of the occipital bones form the lateral and posterolateral borders of the FM (Inderbir, 2012; Matsushima, 2015; Tubbs et al., 2010b; Tubbs et al., 2004).

The ontogeny of the FM is a complex developmental process, many aspects of which remain unknown (Bernard et al., 2015; Coll et al., 2016; Jin et al., 2016; Matsumura et al., 1994; Richards and Jabbour, 2011). During fetal life stages, the FM has been documented to be primarily long-oval in shape, whereas more diverse shapes begin to develop only after birth. The overall growth patterns of the FM differ significantly between its sagittal (FM length, FML) and transversal (FM breadth, FMB) dimensions, which could be related to the developmental sequences and spatial arrangement of the various structures passing through the FM. Whereas the growth of FML is completed by the age of five, FMB continues to grow until the age of ten, when the FM finally obtains its final adult dimensions (Richards and Jabbour, 2011). Further growth differences have been observed between the ventral and dorsal portions of the FM, which might be connected to the differential, responsive development and to the functions of the structures passing through the anterior or posterior part of this foramen (Richards and Jabbour, 2011). Because of the structured spatial organization of many tissues that run through the FM and their mutual relationships with each other, it has been suggested that the FM should be divided into two functional matrices (Moss and Young, 1960): the anterior (ventral, narrower) and the posterior (dorsal, broader) units, which are separated by the tectorial membrane – the cephalic extension of the dorsal or posterior longitudinal ligament – forming a dense soft tissue barrier between them. Whereas this division is currently widely accepted in physiology, physical anthropology continues to treat the FM as a uniform cranial entity (Richards and Jabbour, 2011). Topographically, the anterior matrix spans the anterior and anterolateral margins of the FM and entails the dens or odontoid process of the axis vertebrae (C2), the bilateral accessory atlanto-axial(-occipital), transverse occipital, apical, cruciform, and alar ligaments, as well as the anterior atlantooccipital-, and tectorial membranes (Fig. S1.3). Together with the atlanto-occipital and atlanto-axial joints, including the left and right atlanto-occipital condyles (AOC), these locomotor tissues mainly facilitate head movement and stabilization (Richards and Jabbour, 2011).

Anterior FM matrix (A)

- 1 - Anterior atlantooccipital membrane
- 2 - Odontoid process (dens) of axis
- 3 - Apical odontoid ligament of dens
- 4 - Odontoid or alar ligament*
- 5 - Transverse occipital ligaments
- 6 - Accessory atlantoaxial(-occipital) ligaments L/R
- 7 - Superior longitudinal band of cruciform ligament of atlas (curs superius)
- 8 - Tectorial membrane of atlanto-axial joint

Posterior FM matrix (B)

- 9 - Posterior internal vertebral venous plexus
 - 10 - Extradural space
 - 11 - Dura mater
 - 12 - Subdural space
 - 13 - Arachnoid mater
 - 14 - Subarachnoid space with cerebrospinal fluid
 - 15 - Pia mater
 - 16 - White matter of spinal cord
 - 17 - Grey matter of spinal cord
 - 18 - Central canal of spinal cord
 - 19 - Vertebral artery*
 - 20 - Anterior spinal artery
 - 21 - Spinal root of accessory nerve*
 - 22 - Posterior vertebral artery*
 - 23 - Tonsil of cerebellum*
 - 24 - Posterior atlantooccipital membrane
- } Medulla oblongata
- } Meninges

Fig. S1.3: Schematic overview of the structures passing through the foramen magnum. Anterior is facing upwards. Not to scale. * = bilateral occurring structures. Designed by the author, modified after Inderbir (2012), Matsushima (2015), Tubbs et al. (2010b), and Tubbs et al. (2004). Created with Procreate® (version 4.3.9) using the Apple iPad® (6th generation, version 15.1) and Apple Pencil®.

Fig. 1a (left) and 1b (right): Virtual 3D reconstruction of a medical CT scan of an adult modern human skull (the authors; DG) and foramen magnum (of the author) in ecto- (left) and endocranial (right) view. Anterior is facing upwards. Legend: 1) foramen magnum, 2) atlanto-occipital condyles*, 3) clivus, 4) nuchal plane / squamous part of the occipital bone, 5) condylar fossa* and condylar foramen* / posterior condylar canal*, 6) petrous bones*, 7) lateral parts of the occipital bone*, 8) hypoglossal canals*, 9) jugular tubercles*, 10) internal occipital crest, 11) cerebellar fossae*. * = bilateral occurring structures. The depicted individual is not included in the analyses.

The posterior matrix, also called ‘proper foramen magnum’ (Burdan et al., 2012), is delimited by the posterior and posterolateral edges of the FM. It serves as a passage for several important neurovascular tissues, including the medulla oblongata part of the brainstem,

the spinal cord, the three meninges, the posterior atlanto-occipital membrane, the spinal roots of the spinal accessory nerve (CNXI), the lower part of the basilar and external vertebral venous plexus, the venous marginal sinuses, and the vertebral, anterior, and posterior spinal arteries (Fig. S1.3). Although the posterior unit also contributes to head movement and stabilization, the primary purposes of the tissues running through this matrix are of hydro-, hemodynamic, and neurological nature.

1.2 Cranial Variation and its Relations to Population Affinity and Sex Identification

Identifying the biological sex or population affinity of skeletal remains, along with other characteristics such as age-at-death or body stature, is usually one of the first steps in osteological examinations carried out by physical anthropologists. These biological parameters are crucial in a variety of contexts, including the identification of unknown individuals in medicolegal cases, reconstructing the pathway of morphological evolution, and analyzing patterns and changes in the paleodemography of past groups and societies (Bruzek and Murail, 2006; Cunha and Ubelaker, 2020; Moore, 2013). A wide range of metric as well as non-metric skeletal traits have been empirically demonstrated to be useful in sex or population affinity identification. Their utility and accuracy, however, vary between traits as well as between the sexes, age groups, and populations under study (Dawson et al., 2011; Ferguson et al., 2011). There are major methodological differences in the ways metric and non-metric skeletal traits are recorded and analyzed, and a terminological distinction can be drawn between them according to the anthropological nomenclature. When dealing with osteometric variables, proxies of the biological profile like sex and population affinity are '*estimated*', whereas non-metric traits are used to '*assess*' them (Moore, 2013). As metric estimation and non-metric assessment both play major roles in FM research, both terms will be applied throughout this study following this definition.

The possibility to infer population affinity from skeletal remains (Cunha and Ubelaker, 2020; Relethford, 2009) relies on the existence of considerable correlations between global patterns of cranial phenotypic and geographic distances, showing that human variation is geographically structured following clinal gradients (Elliott and Collard, 2009; Relethford and Harpending, 1994), as predicted by the *Isolation-by-Distance Model* (Wright, 1938, 1940). According to this model, gene flow is spatially limited by geographic distance, meaning that genotypic and phenotypic similarities decrease exponentially between populations with increasing geographic distances and vice versa (Crow and Kimura, 1970; Malecot, 1969; Morton, 1977). The highest amount of variation can be observed within the African continent, which exponentially declines with increasing geographical distance from this continent (Relethford and Harpending, 1994). The human skull is the most widely studied anatomical

structure with regards to intra- and interpopulation differences and has been noted to be the most useful in population affinity estimation or assessment (Casado, 2017a; Cunha and Ubelaker, 2020; Relethford, 2009).

Different cranial traits can be used to estimate or assess the biological sex of individuals due to observable and measurable differences in the size, shape, and/or form of bony structures in female and male anatomy (Frayner and Wolpoff, 1985). Numerous potential causes of sexual differences in the human skeleton have been debated, and originally two models were brought forward to explain their origin (Frayner and Wolpoff, 1985). The *Proximate Causation Model* argues for the effect and interplay of extrinsic, non-genetic factors, mainly differences in diet, nutrition, health, biomechanical forces in relation to labor, activity levels, and behaviors, as well as culture (Casado, 2017a; Frayer and Wolpoff, 1985; Moore, 2013; Stinson, 2012). The *Ultimate Causation Model*, on the other hand, relies on intrinsic or genetic factors to explain sexual dimorphism as adaptation to ecological, economic, or social factors through selection (Frayner and Wolpoff, 1985). Here, internal biochemical conditions like hormone levels and activities during fetal stages in utero and later during puberty are the main drivers of sexual differences (Ammerpohl et al., 2013; Sadler, 2006). With regards to the social aspect as an influence on sexual differences, more recent studies have suggested and demonstrated that socio-cultural factors such as marriage practices, gender-specific workload, and different gender roles in general play important roles in the manifestation of sexual dimorphism (Kirchengast, 2014). Overall, both models include important aspects known to play roles in body development. It is therefore very likely that sexual dimorphism depends on both extrinsic and intrinsic factors (Stinson, 2012). It must be noted that, from an anthropological point of view, sexual dimorphism is used as a common term when referring to differences between females and males, although there are systematically high levels of trait overlap between both sexes. This definition might therefore diverge from the nomenclature in biomedical and general biological science, where 'dimorphism' refers to traits with little to no overlap between groups, whereas 'differentiation' is usually used in cases of considerable similarities and overlap (personal communication with Hugo Reyes-Centeno (HRC), January 2022). On average, size dimensions in males mostly exceed those of females, who often have smaller and less "robust" bones and bodies (Frayner and Wolpoff, 1985). However, the degree of sexual dimorphism in modern humans, especially in their bone morphology, is relatively low compared to other primate and mammal species (e.g., gorilla), and there exists a huge overlap in the range of trait expressions between both sexes (Bogin, 2020; Frayer and Wolpoff, 1985). The extent to which sexual dimorphic traits are expressed further varies across populations and age groups, as well as according to which morphological structure is examined (Buikstra and Ubelaker, 1994; Cunha and Ubelaker, 2020; Lewis and Garvin, 2016). The most sexually dimorphic element in the human skeleton is the pelvic girdle due to its role in reproduction (Bogin, 2020; Bruzek and Murail, 2006; Buikstra and Ubelaker, 1994; Krogman and Isçan, 1986; Moore, 2013; Phenice, 1969). Following the pelvis, the skull has often empirically been

proven to be the second most useful structure for sex assessment or estimation in modern humans (Bass, 2005; Bruzek and Murail, 2006; Krogman and Isçan, 1986). Other than the pelvis, the skull possesses only secondary sexual characteristics emerging due to hormonal differences (Quinn et al., 2014) or muscle-induced biomechanical forces (Bass, 2005). Differences between male and female skulls are therefore often more subtle than in other primates (Dawson et al., 2011), with traits showing a higher degree of overlap, thus making attempts to identify the sex of human individuals based on the cranium alone slightly less reliable (Bruzek and Murail, 2006).

1.3 Methodological Approaches to Estimate or Assess Population Affinity and Sex

Many osteological studies have demonstrated the ability of non-metric and metric cranial traits to provide information on population affinity and sex (Atkinson and Tallman, 2020; Bigoni et al., 2010; Buikstra and Ubelaker, 1994; Elliott and Collard, 2009; Gillet et al., 2020; Hefner, 2009; Hefner et al., 2016; Hefner et al., 2014; Kenyhercza et al., 2019; Navega et al., 2014; Petaros et al., 2021; Ramsthaler et al., 2007; Rogers, 2005; Spradley and Jantz, 2016; Williams and Rogers, 2006; and many other studies). Non-metric or discrete trait assessments have often been considered to be capable of capturing far more information than osteometric measurements, given that many anatomical features are not metrically quantifiable, such as the presence or absence of traits or their degree of expression (Hauser and De Stefano, 1989; Lewis and Garvin, 2016). In practice, software solutions like the web-based application rASUDAS (Scott et al., 2018) for dental traits or hefneR (Coelho and Navega) for discrete cranial traits (Hefner, 2009) can be used to non-metrically assess the population affinity of skeletal remains. Such morphognostic approaches do not require special, costly equipment and can therefore be easily applied (Casado, 2017a; Lewis and Garvin, 2016). Non-metric traits are, moreover, often concentrated on singular anatomical areas, allowing for better examination of highly fragmented remains (Lewis and Garvin, 2016). Because of this, non-metric cranial traits have been widely employed to assess the population affinity of unknown humans, with accuracy rates ranging from approximately 60% to 90% depending on the combination of traits and the populations under study, using different statistical methods (Atkinson and Tallman, 2020; Hefner, 2009; Hefner et al., 2014; Plemons and Hefner, 2016; Scott et al., 2018; among many others). Likewise, sex assessments using non-metric cranial traits have reportedly reached correct classification rates of up to 96% (Alves et al., 2020; Lewis and Garvin, 2016; Walker, 2008; Williams and Rogers, 2006, among many others). On the other hand, non-metric trait analyses have proven to be more prone to subjective biases and to require higher levels of observer experience, which can result in high rates of interobserver error (Casado, 2017a; Cunha and Ubelaker, 2020; Hefner, 2009; Lewis and Garvin, 2016; Plemons and Hefner, 2016).

Sex or population affinity can further be estimated using morphometric data, including absolute measurements of linear distances, angles, and areas, as well as derived indices derived from these measurements, hereafter referred to as 'traditional' metrics. Most of these traditional measurements, which are still widely used today, have already been clearly defined, summarized, and standardized in the early to late 20th century (e.g., Martin, 1914, 1928a; Martin and Saller, 1957) and later (e.g., Bräuer, 1988; Bräuer and Knußmann, 1988; Howells, 1973). Today, statistical computer programs that rely on larger 2D osteometric reference datasets, such as CRANID (Wright, 2012), FORDISC (Jantz and Ousley, 2017; Ousley and Jantz, 1996; Ousley and Jantz, 2012; Ousley and Jantz, 2013), and AncesTrees (Navega et al., 2014), are available to osteometrically estimate the population affinity (and sex) of unknown human individuals in forensic practice. In contrast to non-metrical assessments, metrical data can easily be collected using standardized osteometric equipment (Bräuer and Knußmann, 1988). These measurements are repeatable and therefore not as much affected by subjective biases related to the identification and categorization of distinct shapes, for example (Casado, 2017a; Moore, 2013). The strength of metric reproducibility and reliability lies in the possibility of expressing them as statistical intra- and interobserver error or methodological accuracy rates, often expressed as percentage values. This is of particular importance in forensic cases where medicolegal evidence must be presented and defended in courtrooms. Under the widely applied Daubert Standards, methods must be objective, empirically tested, and peer-reviewed, meaning they must be reliably reproducible to support the trustworthiness of juristic testimonies (Casado, 2017a; Casado, 2017b; Cheng and Yoon, 2005; Christensen, 2006; Grivas and Komar, 2008). Because of this, metric methods should generally be favored over non-metric ones, especially in the legal system (Moore, 2013). Some argue, however, that to increase the reliability of anthropological examinations, both approaches should be used in tandem (Cunha and Ubelaker, 2020). For the human cranium, population affinity estimations using linear measurements have reached correct classification accuracy rates of up to 94% based on multivariate analyses (Guyomarch and Bruzek, 2011; L'Abbé et al., 2013; Navega et al., 2014; Spradley and Jantz, 2011; among many others). Sexing based on osteometric variables reaches similarly high accuracy rates, between 70% and 94%, depending on the population studied and measurements used (Casado, 2017b; Ramsthaler et al., 2007; Spradley and Jantz, 2011; among many others).

Despite their advantages, traditional morphometrics have several methodological restrictions, particularly regarding shape and form (Perez et al. 2006). One of the main problems lies in the relatively low number of defined traditional osteometric measurements used to represent bone morphologies. Many anatomical structures are not quantified in detail, if at all, and are therefore often completely excluded from subsequent osteometric analyses. Those morphological structures summarized by measurements must be sufficiently well preserved to be measured (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009). Establishing homology between particular measuring points for specific measurements is also not always straightforward,

especially when they cannot be precisely defined, as in the case of the maximum cranial breadth measurements (i.e., left to right Euryon) (Adams et al., 2004). Another problem is that it is usually not possible to establish spatial relationships between the measured variables, consequently leading to the loss of the geometry of the studied specimen's structure throughout the analysis (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009; O'Higgins, 2000), and thus also preventing the graphical representation of shape in most cases (Adams et al., 2004).

Two approaches have been developed to counteract the loss of shape information in traditional linear measurement analysis: the first relies on a number of size corrections that have been employed to study size-independent variation. However, most of these established scaling factors were used without common scientific agreement on their utility, leading to diverging, incomparable results (Adams et al., 2004). As a second solution, the calculation of osteometric indices, which can be derived from the relative aspect ratio of two (or sometimes more) linear measurements, has been proposed and are still commonly used as metric descriptors of shape (Bräuer and Knußmann, 1988). Osteometric indices are often divided into different main shape categories, which are sometimes even further divided into more specific subcategories (Martin, 1928a). Although a large number of indices for different pairs of measurements have been defined, such as the aspect ratio between the maximum transversal and sagittal diameters of the FM, also known as the *foramen magnum index* (FMI) (Bräuer, 1988), their use and biological meaningfulness can be questioned as the classification into distinct shape categories is arbitrary and might not reflect actual biological shape variation (Bräuer, 1988; Bräuer and Knußmann, 1988; Martin, 1928a).

To account for these disadvantages of non-metric as well as traditional metric analyses, GM approaches can be used to more objectively and accurately capture and quantify the shape or form of a vast number of anatomical structures (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009). The beginning of modern GM can be found in the late 19th to early 20th centuries (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009), but it only became widely applicable with the advances in computational power and the spread of affordable personal computers in the later 20th century. These enhanced technological capacities, together with the development of coordinate-based methods and the formulation of the theory of statistical shape analysis, led to a major revolution in morphometrics, which can be seen as the foundation of modern GM as practiced today (Adams et al., 2004; Bookstein, 1998; Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009; O'Higgins, 2000; Rohlf and Marcus, 1993). GM has found a wide range of applications within physical anthropology, from the study of morphological variability, plasticity, modularity, and integration (Cottin et al., 2017; Püschel et al., 2020), ontogenetic development and age-related changes (Urban et al., 2016), biomechanics and functional morphology (Karakostis and Harvati, 2021; Ledogar et al., 2016; Noback and Harvati, 2015; von Cramon-Taubadel, 2011), to the reconstruction of human phylogeny and population history (de León et al., 2018; Palci and Lee, 2019; Reyes-Centeno et al., 2017; Smith, 2009). Relative to non-metric and traditional osteometric methods, more

sophisticated equipment and software are required to collect and analyze GM data, either directly from the specimen or indirectly from virtual 3D models derived from surface- or volume scans (Bräuer and Knußmann, 1988; Fahrni et al., 2017; Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009). Nowadays, the majority of GM methods to capture and analyze shape and/or form information are landmark-based (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009). *Traditional, definite, or fixed landmarks*, as initially defined by Bookstein (1991) and later redefined by Weber and Bookstein (2011), are biologically homologous loci that have unique 2D or 3D Cartesian coordinates that aim to reflect points of geometric correspondence across specimens. In many cases, these landmarks directly coincide with the clearly defined endpoints of traditional linear distance measurements. In contrast to traditional osteometry, however, the relative spatial position of landmark points or configurations is captured in GM, which is then used to infer information about shape and/or form (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009). The term *shape* refers to the geometric characteristics of a studied structure invariant of its overall size, position, and orientation in space (Dryden and Mardia, 1998; Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009; O'Higgins, 2000). Other fields of anthropological research also rely on factor *size*, however, such as studies on sexual dimorphic variation or development (i.e., ontogenetic allometry) (Lewis and Garvin, 2016; Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009). When preserving size in GM analyses, the *form* of biological structures is considered, which is only independent of a specimen's position and orientation but not scaling (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009). The statistical association between size and shape variables, or the study of the size effect on shape, is called *allometry* (Mitteroecker et al., 2013). As with traditional 2D osteometric measurements, 3D cranial landmark data from different populations can be utilized by programs such as 3D-ID to predict the population affinity and sex of unknown human remains in medicolegal cases (Slice and Ross, 2012). Because of their ability to capture and study spatial anatomical relationships, many studies have empirically demonstrated that GM approaches can yield higher accuracy rates than linear methods when trying to discriminate between species, populations, or sexes (Bigoni et al., 2010). Landmark data of different cranial and craniofacial structures of modern humans yield accurate classifications and separation between individuals from different populations with accuracy rates up to around 96% using different multivariate methods (Bigoni et al., 2010; Chovalopoulou et al., 2016; Del Bove et al., 2020; McDowell et al., 2012; among many others; Stull et al., 2014). It has, however, also been noted that landmark data might not necessarily perform better than traditional Euclidean distance measurements with regards to differentiation between populations (Spradley and Jantz, 2016). This might, however, depend on the selected landmarks and captured structures.

Although fixed landmarks enable the collection of relational shape and form information, many morphological structures such as curves, outlines, surfaces, and any other feature without clearly defined landmark locations cannot be captured. This is mainly because, per definition, fixed landmarks represent the same anatomical locations that are also used as endpoints for traditional 2D distance measurements (Gunz and Mitteroecker, 2013; Perez et

al., 2006). To account for these structures and to increase the applicability of GM, the concept of *sliding semilandmarks* has been introduced (Bookstein, 1991; Bookstein, 1997; Green, 1996; Gunz et al., 2005). Semilandmarks are 2D or 3D landmarks positioned along morphological curvatures or over surfaces. Because semilandmarks are not restricted to traditional landmark definitions, they can be used to capture a much wider range of anatomical structures, including foramina, muscle attachment facets, and joint surfaces. Other than fixed landmarks, semilandmarks arbitrarily placed along curvatures or on surfaces in roughly equidistant intervals can never be considered to be exact corresponding points. However, the semilandmark algorithms only require the captured anatomical structure to be homologous. The arbitrary interlandmark distances are equalized during the subsequent standardization process, which involves the sliding of the semilandmarks along a curve or over a surface until the differences between all individual specimen landmark configurations are minimal. In the following statistical analysis, slid semilandmark coordinate data can then be treated in the same way as traditional landmark data (Gunz and Mitteroecker, 2013; Perez et al., 2006). In addition to Bookstein's traditional categorization system from 1991 of fixed landmarks, landmarks and semilandmarks are now categorized into six distinct types, which reflect their identifiability as well as the anatomical properties of the structures they are intended to capture (Weber and Bookstein, 2011).

GM studies of the FM are still rare. This might be related to the fact that the acquisition of landmark data and subsequent statistical analyses are more complex and time-consuming than traditional approaches. The FM has primarily been considered as a 2D structure (Richards and Jabbour, 2011), and only two articles could be found that analyzed it using semilandmark approaches (Toneva et al., 2018; Zdilla et al., 2017). Whereas Toneva et al. (2018) extracted 3D semilandmark data from virtual volume models to capture 3D FM information, Zdilla et al. (2017) solely relied on raw CT image slices to obtain 2D semilandmark points. The scarcity of 3D landmark-based GM analyses in FM research indicates the lack of novel 3D shape and form analysis in this field as compared to the much larger research body of studies that have relied on 2D perspectives. It also calls for more systematic investigations and comparisons of already established methods for this anatomical structure to further test the potential of alternative approaches, namely GM.

1.4 Research Questions and Study Aims

The present study has two aims: a) to give a critical and comprehensive review of the published record of metric and non-metric FM research as part of the discussion; and b) to metrically estimate the global osteometric within- and between-population variation of the FM using alternative approaches less prone to subjective biases. Two datasets – traditional 2D measurements and 3D semilandmark data, all collected from the same cranial specimens –

will be analyzed statistically, and uni- as well as multivariate methods will be used to infer their utility in distinguishing between sexes and populations to further evaluate the usefulness of the FM in forensic victim identification and anthropological provenience research.

Taken together, the research questions of the current study can be summarized as follows:

- 1) What is the current state of FM research, and what are the underlying problems that might bias FM study results?
- 2) Does the size, shape, and/or form of the FM differ between sexes and/or populations?
- 3) Which variable, or which type of osteometric data (2D linear measurements or 3D sliding semilandmarks) better separates sexes and/or populations statistically?
- 4) Can the FM be reliably used to accurately infer the population affinity and sex of unknown human remains?

With regards to research questions 2) to 4), two main hypotheses will be statistically tested for the individual datasets of 2D measurements and 3D landmark data:

- H_{0.1}: There are no statistically significant mean differences in FM size, shape, or form measurements between sexes for each population.
- H_{0.2}: There are no statistically significant mean differences in FM size, shape, or form measurements between populations.

Fig. 2: Schematic overview of the ten sub-hypotheses of H_{0.1} and H_{0.2} statistically tested in this study.

Note that the size hypotheses can be split into individual sub-hypotheses for each of the analyzed 2D measurements: FML, FMB, and FMI. Taken singularly, a total of ten sub-hypotheses for the two main hypotheses will be statistically tested in this study, summarized in the overview graphic in Figure 2.

2. Materials

To study global patterns in the morphological variation of the FM, osteometric data chosen for this study was collected from 1) original data of modern, adult human crania from Africa (Eritrea), Asia (Japan), and Europe (Germany and Greece) and 2) from the published literature, including samples covering almost all inhabited continents, for further meta-analyses. The following sections present detailed background information about the newly collected samples as well as about the reference dataset.

2.1 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

This study includes only adult, dry modern human skulls of known provenience, representing both sexes, and with intact and accessible FMs. The inclusion criteria have been left considerably open and flexible to maximize the sample sizes of each population. However, a few criteria have been predefined to exclude potential outliers that could negatively affect the analyses:

1) First, only specimens that are well preserved for handling and scanning were considered for further investigations to avoid physically damaging the bone. Extremely fragile and fragmented remains were therefore excluded upon first sight.

2) As previous studies did not find any significant secular trend in the dimensions of the FM over the past millennia (Gruber et al., 2009), this study used remains from various time periods, i.e., archaeological, historical, and (pre-)modern times. This was also helpful because exact dates were not available for most specimens.

3) Individuals were excluded when their taphonomic and pathological status visibly affected the integrity of the FM. In cases where the AOC displayed traces of erosion and/or fragmentation but the outline of the FM was still intact, the skull in question was included.

4) Skulls with signs of advanced congenital, developmental conditions (e.g., craniosynostosis, also called premature suture closure or stenosis due to Crouzon or similar syndromes, hydro-, macro-, or microcephaly, etc.) or infectious diseases (e.g., syphilis (cranial syphilitic osteomyelitis) or leprosy) were excluded (Coll et al., 2015; Duffon et al., 2011; Hecht et al., 1989; Mann and Hunt, 2005).

5) Pathological conditions that are directly associated with the FM or its surrounding area, including the AOC, were excluded, such as occipito-cervical synostosis or atlanto-occipital fusion, pseudarthrosis in the precondylar region, precondylar defects with the appearance of small fossa-like concavities, or large ossicles (Barnes, 1994; Mann and Hunt, 2005).

6) Individuals with smaller Basion tubercles were kept in the sample to not further decrease the already small subsample sizes.

7) Individuals with pathologies that have a limited effect on bones or that are more locally restricted and not associated with the occipital part of the cranial base (e.g., *Cribrum cranii*, *Cribrum orbitalia*, scurvy, etc.) were included (Mann and Hunt, 2005). Likewise, individuals that have AOC showing signs of progressed degenerative joint diseases (e.g., sclerotic lipping) were included if the osteophytes and lipping did not excessively protrude into the FM space. It must be noted that in almost all observed and studied cases, most AOCs displayed such changes only towards their posterolateral sides. The FM is usually not much affected by degenerative AOC changes.

8) For the within-population analysis, to investigate between-sex differences, morphologically unidentified individuals were excluded. Those sex-unknown specimens, however, were included in the interpopulation analyses to increase the overall sample size of the respective population and the reliability of the statistical results.

2.2 Berlin Samples

All specimens for which new FM data were collected for this study are permanently housed at the Berlin anthropological collections at the outer depot of the *Staatlichen Museen zu Berlin* (SMB, Berlin State Museums) in Friedrichshagen, Berlin, Germany, and include: 1) Rudolf-Virchow-Collection (RVS), 2) Felix-von-Luschan-Collection (S-Collection), 3) Former-Charité-Collection (O-Cha-Collection), and 4) Former-Racial-Skull-Collection (RSK). Permissions to scan and analyze all the skulls were thankfully granted by the collection curators of the *Berliner Gesellschaft für Anthropologie Ethnologie und Urgeschichte* (BGAEU; in possession of the RVS) and the SMB (in possession of the RSK, S-, and Former-Charité-Collections). Both permission letters are reprinted in the supplementary materials (S1.1 and S1.2). Although access and usage to a much larger sample were initially permitted (see next section on provenience research below), the final dataset used here consists of 98 individuals from four geographically distant populations covering a wide global range, including Africa (Eritrea), Asia (Japan), and Europe (Germany and Greece) (Fig. 3; see Sections 2.2.3 to 2.2.6). Each of these four population samples will be presented in more detail in the following chapters. Tables S2.1 to S2.4 summarize general information about the sex and provenance of these individuals.

2.2.1 Ethical Code

Human remains housed in anthropological or medical collections are a valuable source for scientific research, but more importantly, they represent the mortal remnants of once-living individuals. All working steps therefore strictly followed the official regulations of the housing collections in Berlin (not published), as well as national and international standards and ethical codes for the interaction and study of human remains. This was done to treat the studied individuals with great dignity, care, and respect, as well as to preserve their integrity for future research (Fuchs et al., 2020; Mühlenberend et al., 2018; Museumsbund, 2013, 2021). As shown in the next section, much time and dedication were spent on the provenience research to assure that no osteological specimens from presumed or proven unethical contexts would enter the analysis. The author, therefore, declares that every action that was taken to retrieve, analyze, and interpret the data and results of this study was done in compliance with the above-mentioned standards and without any conflict of interest after the removal of specimens from

ethically questionable origins. Furthermore, no aspect of this study or its outcome is meant to hurt or violate personal or human rights in any way. The author disassociates himself from any interpretations adapted by others who might use the results of this study to promote sexist, racist, ableist, or any other inhumane conclusions.

2.2.2 Provenience Research for the Berlin Samples

Provenience research deals with the investigation and identification of the rightful ownership, origin, and circumstances of the acquisition of collection inventories of any kind. For the scope of this study, provenience research was conducted to ensure that no elements included in this study originate from contexts of injustice. Therefore, the provenience of each individual was checked before the analysis. In the case of the Berlin anthropological collections, it is not surprising that many individuals were acquired during a period of European colonialism in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, as much of the collection was compiled during this period. More detailed information on the history of the Berlin collections, as well as current and past projects on provenience research, is available in the *Mitteilungen der Berliner Gesellschaft für Anthropologie, Ethnologie und Urgeschichte* (Journal of the Berlin Society for Anthropology, Ethnology, and Prehistory, Creutz, 2006; Göldner, 2020a; Hämmerling, 2020; Koel-Abt, 2012; Kowalak and Heeb, 2016; Lewerentz, 1998, 2000a, b, 2020; Schier, 2020; Seethaler, 2012, 2014).

To gather information on their origin and circummundane of acquisition, the collection's unpublished virtual database (DB, all collections), archival documents (e.g., "Karteikarten", ID cards for RVS, unpublished), and inventory catalogs (e.g., Strauch- and Unterkiefer-Catalogue for RVS, unpublished; Broesike (1880)-Catalogue for RSK), as well as publicly accessible journals, e.g., *Zeitschrift für Ethnologie* (ZfE, Journal of Ethnology, mostly for RVS), were consulted and screened for information on the specimens. An individual was ultimately excluded from this study when information about their origin and acquisition was clearly indicative of a context of injustice or in cases where unethical acquisition of the remains could have been reasonably assumed. A classic example of such contexts is the theft of human remains, mostly by European collectors who did not obtain permission from the respective indigenous communities. Often, such thieving practices were described by the collectors themselves in detail in letters or diaries, making a judgment on the legality of their activities easy. Illustrative examples with associations to the Berlin collections are the explanations given by Meyer (1885) of his theft of Igorot skulls from the Philippines, Hildebrandt (1880) about stolen Sakalava skulls from Madagascar, or Horck (1876) about unwanted openings of Sami burials in Scandinavia. In other cases, more time was spent retrieving such information. For some individuals, provenience was not possible due to different external factors, e.g., when archival documentation was lost due to war, past collection movements, etc. To effectively

compile as much information as possible, the author worked in close correspondence with the curators and museum staff. Occasionally, when no information was accessible at all, related research on the general reservations of the respective indigenous groups towards handling and research on the human remains of their related ancestors was consulted (Makino, 2015; Weston, 2020). This served as a good indicator of whether a sample should indeed be used or not.

Fig. 3: Political world map showing the geographic distribution of the newly collected samples for this study (shown in blue and marked with *) and reference samples from the literature for the meta-analysis (shown in grey) from: **Africa:** 1) Egypt, 2) Eritrea*, 3) Kenya, 4) Nigeria, 5) Sudan); **America (North):** 6) USA; **(South):** 7) Brazil, 8) Chile, 9) Peru); **Asia:** 10) China, 11) India, 12) Iran, 13) Iraq, 14) Japan, 15) Malaysia, 16) Nepal, 17) Oman, 18) Saudi Arabia, 19) Turkey); and **Europe:** 20) Britain, 21) Bulgaria, 22) France, 23) Germany*, 24) Greece* (new and reference data), 25) Italy, 26) Poland, 27) Portugal, 28) Spain. Not highlighted are the generalized subsamples of Africa, Europe, and East Asia from Zdilla et al. (2017). The map was thankfully produced by M. Loetz (University of Tübingen) using QGIS (v3.16.5) and open data from the ArcGIS hub (https://hub.arcgis.com/datasets/2b93b06dc0dc4e809d3c8db5cb96ba69_0/explore?location=-0.000286%2C9.987952%2C1.00).

The current study was initially outlined using a much larger and ambitious dataset, including around 400 cranial specimens from approximately 26 geographically distant human populations from Africa, Asia, Europe, and the Pacific Ocean – all listed in the permission letters. The use of those samples was permitted under the condition that none of them originated from former German colonies. The author also ensured the study of the provenience history for each of the cranial series in advance. Due to personal ethical considerations and further provenience research by the author and Leah Böttger, who also included some of the same specimens in her master thesis, it was mutually decided to exclude most of these skull series whenever unethical, colonial contexts of injustice could be reasonably assumed or proven. For this reason, the initial sample was reduced to only four populations comprising around 100 skulls whose use can ethically be justified based on their provenience status. As for the ethical and political sensitivity of this kind of information, the list of specimens with questionable or proven unethical contexts is not reported here but was handed over to the curators. Likewise, no data from these specimens retrieved by the author that was potentially

collected before the final exclusion will be made publicly available and/or destroyed to prevent further scientific usage and exploitation. Although the status of all the remaining human remains was found to be non-controversial, it must be noted that this point of view on the usability and accessibility of these specimens (and any kind of data collected from them) may change at any time in the future, e.g., according to collection or state guidelines.

2.2.3 Africa – Eritrean Sample

The African dataset of this study comes from the former Italian colony in modern-day Eritrea, located in the north-eastern part of the continent. The remains were excavated in 1894 by a German expedition from a chamber grave on the Kohaito (also called Qohaito or Qohayto) Plateau, located close to the central-western border of Ethiopia. The Kohaito Plateau has an interesting archaeological history, with flourishing settlement activity during Aksumitic and later Christian times. Numerous remnants of architectural structures remain intact to this day. During the 1990s, the plateau was superficially survived by the German Archaeological Institute, but due to political instabilities in Eritrea, further research was halted (Eigner, 2006; Schreibner, 2006; Wenig, 2006). The 1894 expedition during which the Kohaito skulls were excavated was led by the German industrialist Max Schoeller, who was accompanied by scientists, most importantly the Berlin botanist and Africa-anthropologist Georg August Schweinfurth, who was in close correspondence with Rudolf Virchow in Berlin.

The context and provenience of this cranial series can be reconstructed relatively well, given that Schoeller gave detailed reports in his diary (Schoeller, 1895). In addition to that, Schweinfurth also wrote some brief articles about the skulls in the *ZfE* (Schweinfurth, 1984). Besides being included in Sergi's *Crania Habessinica* from 1912 (Sergi, 1912), it seems that Virchow never wrote about the Kohaito skulls in his own Eritrea collection series. According to Schoeller's and Schweinfurth's reports, a total of 70 skeletons in different preservation states were found, all buried within the same stone chamber beneath the ground. According to their records, everything placed inside this chamber was excavated, but only 31 skulls and some mandibles were sent to Virchow for his collection in Berlin (RVS inventory numbers: RV 1065, RV 1066, RV 1283–1309). Nothing is known about the destination of the remaining bones and grave goods. Based on artifacts that were buried alongside the deceased, as well as anthropological markers such as artificial body modifications (i.e., intentional extraction of the upper and lower front teeth in male individuals) and the appearance of some preserved head hair, Schweinfurth and Schoeller reasoned that the remains were likely related to a Hamitic Galla tribe (Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984). Schweinfurth suggested that the remains could be between 200 and 1.000 years old (Schweinfurth, 1984). Modern radiocarbon dating of six of the skulls (RV 1065, RV 1283, RV 1284, RV 1292, RV 1296, and RV 1306) revealed an absolute age of the specimens between the 11th and early 15th centuries AD (Tab. S1.5)

(Wenig and Vogt, 2017). Based on these dates, it can be assumed that the remaining, undated skulls would date similarly. The grave structure itself is suggested to be of a much older age, meaning that the community from which the excavated remains originate must likely have emptied and reused the existing grave chamber for their own deceased (Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984). Schoeller describes that the Assorta (Saho) people that lived there at the time of the excavation (and still live there today) used to take blocks of stones from the overground structure of the tomb to build animal traps (Schoeller, 1895; Wenig, 2006), which can be taken as an indication that the Saho people did not have a deeper social or spiritual connection to the grave and its former interments. For further aspects of the provenience debate of the Kohaito skulls, refer to Wenig and Vogt (2017). In more recent times, the entire Kohaito skull series has been anthropologically examined by Bettina Jungklaus (2017), who documented standard anthropological parameters, including sex information, using the same morphognostic method (Acsádi et al., 1970) applied here (see below). Her results, however, have to be treated with caution, as some of the mandibles do not match with the accompanying crania – a problem that biases morphological sexing using the method by Acsádi et al. (1970) and which has not been considered by Jungklaus. Sex information about the Kohaito skulls has been further documented on the RVS ID cards by Jan Czekanowski, a well-established Polish Africa anthropologist of the 20th century. Twenty-one of the 31 Kohaito skulls have been included in the analysis after four subadult individuals and crania with taphonomically damaged FMs were sorted out.

2.2.4 Asia – Japanese Sample

The smallest among the newly collected population samples is the Japanese dataset, comprising eleven individuals. Initially, 22 individuals were planned to be included. However, due to the provenience research, it became clear that most of the skulls belong to Ainu (also Aino, Ayno, or Ezo) people, the indigenous population of Japan, making the unethical origin of those remains likely. Detailed provenience research and perspectives on the relation of the Ainu people to their stolen human remains are discussed in Makino (2015). In consequence, all remains that could have been associated with an Ainu origin were ultimately excluded from this study. The remaining specimens belong either to the RVS or S-collection. The provenience research for these specimens was carried out by Böttger (2021) and is summarized here: The inscription “*Igt Dönitz*” on the lateral left parietal bones of seven of the here-included Japanese skulls (S 4033 – S 4039) gives hints on their connection to the collector Friedrich Karl Wilhelm Doenitz (Dönitz, 1873-1876a, b), who seems to have rarely worked with or collected Ainu remains. According to the archival record, it seems likely that these remains belong to those of inmates who died in prison on Nippon Island and were then given to the medical department of Tokyo University. Whether they found their way to Berlin after that through trade or exchange between institutions and/or private collectors is still unclear. It was not possible to reconstruct

the exact history of acquisition for the other specimens. Based on the parietal bone inscription on S 4623, a 45-year-old Japanese individual from Kobe (Honshū), it can be concluded that it was donated to the collection by the German pathologist David Paul von Hanseman. As for the remaining cranial specimens, no unethical context or association with indigenous people could be identified. They are simply ascribed to Japanese origin (Böttger, 2021).

2.2.5 Europe – German Sample

The largest sample of newly collected data, with 49 individuals, are the German skulls from the RVS and the S-Collection. Unlike the other Berlin skulls included in this study, more information could be gathered for the German specimens, as Virchow often used them for various anthropological studies, mostly published in the *ZfE* (Virchow, 1874a, b, 1877, 1886, 1892). In addition, bone inscriptions often indicate the geographic origin, collector, year of collection of the specimens, and sometimes even personal biographic information such as name, sex, and date of death in the case of more recent individuals. RVS ID cards are not available for German skulls. The German skulls originated from different localities within the borders of Germany during the 19th century, when the skulls were collected. The main regions of origin are Baden-Wuerttemberg, Bavaria, Berlin, Brandenburg, Bremen, Lower Saxony, Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania, Saxony, and Saxony-Anhalt. Whereas some of the skulls come from pathological institutes, others were excavated from cemeteries that date to between the early to late medieval and early modern times. Based on the overall bone preservation and contextual information reported in the *ZfE*, it can be concluded that none of the specimens' dates significantly older than around 1000 AD. However, none of the individuals have been dated using radiometric methods.

2.2.6 Europe – Greek Sample

The second European sample of this study stems from Greece. The analyzed specimens are housed at the RVS and the RSK-Collections. For the RVS skulls, no detailed, published information was found. However, several ID cards for the Greek skulls of the RVS, as well as the usual inscriptions on the left partial bone, are present. These indicate that these skulls originate from the towns of Le(o)nidi and Prastos on the Peloponnese. According to the Berlin collection database, they come from archaeological sites but lack further contextual information. As noted by Czekanowski and Fütterer on the ID cards, they were not able to find any literature in which the Greek RV skulls are presented or discussed. For the Greek specimens of the RSK-Collection, matching entries could have been found in the so-called Broesike-Catalogue (Broesike, 1880), where their overall morphology is described. Despite indicating that the skulls originate from a cemetery in Athens, no information on the exact

location or their provenience history is given. Based on this information, it can be assumed that they are of pre- to early modern age.

2.3 Comparative 2D Reference Dataset

To gain further insights into the global trends of morphological variation within and between populations of the FM, more data from the literature was gathered. Only 2D reference samples could be compiled for this additional meta-analysis, since landmark-based GM analyses of the FM are still rare and based on different, incomparable landmark configurations. Due to the wide lack of coherent data sharing practices in physical anthropological research, osteometric raw measurements are generally not available. Virtually no FM studies have publicly shared their datasets. This study must therefore solely rely on the reported summary statistics of FM measurements taken from the published record. Consequently, the meta-analysis in this study will be kept at a more superficial, graphic-based level and thus will not apply more in-depth statistical hypothesis testing or modeling. The reference data was searched mainly using common online search engines as well as the literature list of the consulted FM studies. Although the aim was to collect as many publicly available FM studies as possible, it cannot be guaranteed that some studies were missed.

Studies were only included in the 2D reference dataset if they followed the general inclusion and exclusion criteria that have already been outlined and when the origin of the studied dataset was clear. Studies that analyzed sex-unknown samples were labeled as F/M (for Females/Males or pooled-sex samples); these datasets are consequently only used for the inter- but not for the intrapopulation meta-analysis. Sex-known subsamples of females and males have been labeled as such and treated separately in the intrapopulation analysis. At least the number of individuals (n) as well as mean values for FML and FMB must be reported in a FM study for it to be included. Standard deviation (\pm SD), minimum (Min), and maximum (Max) values were additionally collected if present. Otherwise, missing information was labeled as “not available” (N/A). Wherever present, the same statistical metrics were also collected for FMI, given that it has been calculated following the definition by Bräuer (1988), where FMI represents the aspect ratio of FMB divided by FML and multiplied by 100. Alternative FMI calculations are not considered here. For most studies where FMI was not calculated, the mean FMI was calculated here using the reported mean FMB and FML values of the respective studies. On the other hand, missing minimum and maximum FMI values were not calculated using the minimum and maximum FML and FMB values, even when reported, given the uncertainty of whether the values were paired, derived from the same individuals, or not. Studies with reported statistics that appeared questionable or false (e.g., interchanged values for FML and FMB) were also not included in the reference dataset. No differences were made between data collection methods, i.e., when the FM were measured physically, relying on dry

skulls, or virtually, using radiographic CT images or MRI scans. Measurements given in centimeters have been translated to millimeters and rounded to two decimals whenever necessary.

In total, FM summary statistics for 87 studies were compiled for the 2D reference dataset, as summarized in Table S3.20. Without counting the newly collected data for this study, these reference studies comprise 28 different human groups or geographically distant modern human populations, with a total of 9,974 individuals (3,236 females, 3,871 males, and 2,867 sex unidentified individuals) from all continents except Australia (Fig. 3). The reference dataset overall includes five samples from Africa (Egypt, Kenya, Nigeria, Sudan, and one general African sample), one from North America (United States of America (USA)), three from South America (Brazil, Chile, and Peru), ten from Asia (Bengal, China, India, Iran, Iraq, Malaysia, Nepal, Oman, Saudi Arabia, and Turkey), and nine groups from Europe (Britain, Bulgaria, France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Spain, and one general European dataset). Table S2.17 lists the sex information of the reference sample. The graphic distributions of individuals with known and unknown sex in the reference dataset are presented in Figures S2.19 to S2.23.

3. Methods

3.1 Biological Profile

3.1.1 Biological Sex Assessment

Many methods have been developed by physical anthropologists to infer and identify the sex of skeletal individuals using the morphological and morphometric characteristics of bones (for a comprehensive overview, refer to Dawson et al., 2011). The most reliable and, therefore, most favorable part of the skeleton for sexing is the pelvis (Bogin, 2020; Bruzek and Murail, 2006; Buikstra and Ubelaker, 1994; Dawson et al., 2011; Krogman and Isçan, 1986; Moore, 2013; Phenice, 1969). However, the anthropological Berlin collections mostly house isolated skulls. Postcranial elements are extremely rare, and none of the individuals included here had skeletal elements other than crania and mandibles available. Detailed biographic and clinical documentation is also extremely scarce. Furthermore, no genetic data, including chromosomal sex information, has been sampled or analyzed so far. Therefore, the morphological sexing of these specimens had to rely on the skulls alone. Following the recommendation by Ferembach et al. (1980), the morphognostic method after Acsádi et al. (1970) for the morphological sex assessment of the skulls from Berlin was applied. The method accounts for twelve non-metric traits of robustness of the calvarium and five of the mandibular (Ferembach et al., 1980). The current study utilizes the trait list by Sjøvold (1988) (Tab. S2.5), who modified it after Acsádi et al. (1970) and Ferembach et al. (1980). It must be kept in mind

at this point that each population differs in their spectrum of possible expressions of shape, form, and size dimensions. Methods for sexing or for other proxies of the biological profile were usually developed based on specific populations and therefore do not cover the entire human range of morphological variation. Illustration schemes are often published along the descriptive parts of methodological studies; therefore, they mostly represent the variation of the population used for the respective study and the building of the method. These schemata should therefore not be applied without caution to samples that are not the same or not closely related to the source population or reference sample (Dawson et al., 2011). Such illustrations can also be found in the adaptations by Ferembach et al. (1980) and Sjøvold (1988) after the method by Acsádi et al. (1970). One way to account for this problem is to get a sense of the actual morphological variation of the studied skeletal series to which an established morphological method was applied. Before each skull was examined and sexed individually, all specimens were carefully laid out on a table to get an overview of the population-specific variation of traits under investigation. When examining the cranial traits of each specimen using the method by Acsádi et al. (1970), one of five possible degrees of morphological trait expression, also called sex coefficient (x), ranging from -2 for hyperfeminine-expressed traits to +2 for hypermasculine traits, was assigned by the observer to each of the 17 traits according to their appearance (Tab. S2.6). Whereas negative degrees (i.e., -2 and -1) are associated with more 'feminine', or less 'robust' or marked traits, positive values (i.e., +1 and +2) stand for 'masculine' and more 'robustly' expressed traits. Traits that display an intermediate expression of the population spectrum are difficult to classify. They are therefore labeled as indistinguishable and assigned the value zero. Graphic representations and descriptions of the possible trait expression are reported in Acsádi et al. (1970), Ferembach et al. (1980), and Sjøvold (1988). Each trait has, by convention, a defined, fixed weight (w) ranging from 1 to 3 based on their relevance in sexing (Tab. S2.5). Both values, x and w, can then be inserted in the equation:

$$M = \frac{\sum(wx)}{\sum w}$$

to calculate the sexual degree or degree of sexualization (M). Lastly, when comparing the resulting M index value with the spectrum of sexualization degrees, the biological sex of the cranial specimens can be classified into female (F), male (M), or unidentifiable individuals (ind) (Tab. 2.7). Note that sex-unidentifiable individuals are labeled as 'indifferent' in the original German literature (personal communication with Prof. Dr. Katerina Harvati (KH), 2021). This term does not translate well to English, where terms such as 'indeterminable' or 'unidentifiable' are preferentially used. The terminology used in this study for sex-unknown individuals and sub-datasets (indeterminable, indistinguishable, sex-unknown, unidentifiable, etc.) will always

refer to the same, i.e., indifferent, individuals. To accelerate the sexing and minimize calculation errors, a coded version of the equation and classification were used. The script has been coded in Microsoft (MS) Excel (version Microsoft Office 365 ProPlus) by the author and has been applied and tested in a previous project (Göldner, 2020a).

Whenever possible, archival information and published results of past sex estimation attempts were used in addition to cross validating the new morphological sex assessments of the cranial specimens. When discrepancies between the new and older assessments occurred, the specimen in question was revisited. Because the methods applied here and by previous anthropologists are all morphognostic in nature, inherent systematic biases such as observer experiences could cause such diverging results, making it intrinsically difficult to come to a conclusion. The new sexing results were mostly favored over the older ones, given the circumstance that older studies did not account for the unfortunate fact that many mandibles were incorrectly sorted to crania in the Berlin collections. For the sake of this study, the sex of the dubious specimens using the applied sexing method by Acsádi et al. (1970) was calculated two times: first with the mandible, then by excluding it. It was found, although not separately reported here, that this might lead to completely opposite results where male specimens are classified as females and vice versa when false mandibles are included in the assessment. This can be related to the mathematical function of the used formula given that five traits are investigated in a single bone, i.e., the mandible, compared to the remaining twelve traits that aim to cover the entire calvarium. In cases where differences in sexing remain difficult to explain even after considering the potential bias of mandibular traits, the individual's sex is labeled as unidentifiable. Mismatched or questionable associations between mandibles and skulls were noted when present (Tabs. S2.8 to S.11). Criteria to decide whether a mandible and a skull matched included general correspondence in taphonomic alterations (e.g., discoloration, fragmentation patterns, and surface erosion), fitting articulation of the mandibular condyles and the craniomandibular fossae, as well as the match between wear facets of the lower and upper dental arches. Cases identified as being false or questionable matches were not included in the sex assessment. After examination, skulls and falsely assigned mandibles were put back together in their storage containers with a note for the awareness of future scientists. A list with all mandibles identified as uncertain or false assignments was handed over to the curators.

3.1.2 Age-at-Death Estimation

In this study, only adult individuals over the age of approximately 20 years have been included. Although the bony FM is known to be developmentally completed by the age of ten (Richards and Jabbour, 2011) with no obvious subsequent age-related changes (Gapert et al., 2013; Wescott and Moore-Jansen, 2001), no subadult individual was included in this study.

Sexing of such young individuals is generally considered much more difficult (Dawson et al., 2011; Scheuer and Black, 2000) since they have not yet completed their pubertal developmental transition to adulthood, in which the body undergoes significant secondary sexual changes (Dawson et al., 2011). A few skeletal markers of the skull are known to occur around the age of 20, helping to distinguish young adults from subadult individuals. All cranial individuals in this study were considered adults when:

- 1) the suture between the sphenoid and occipital bones was completely fused, also called spheno-occipital synchondrosis (Ingervall and Thilander, 1972; Konie, 1964; Melsen, 1972; Powell and Brodie, 1963; Sahni et al., 1998; Scheuer and Black, 2000),
- 2) the incisive suture of the hard palate showed advanced to completed obliteration (Mann, 1987; Mann et al., 1991; Mann et al., 1987), and
- 3) the third maxillary and mandibular molars were erupted (Haavikko, 1970; Liversidge et al., 1998; Smith, 1991; Ubelaker, 1979).

As the classification into more specific age classes was not considered relevant for the current analysis, it was not aimed at further narrowing down the actual age-at-death. Consequently, all specimens in this study are labeled as adults. As with the sexing, additional information from archival records or published literature on the age-at-death of the specimens was considered when available.

3.2 Study Data

All 2D osteometric measurements for this study have been measured in millimeters (mm) with two decimals. Likewise, and as mentioned before, measurements reported in centimeters (cm) in published literature and included in the reference dataset of the present study have been translated to millimeters and rounded to two decimals where necessary. All 3D cranial models have also been automatically scaled to millimeters by the Artec scanning software. For reasons of research transparency, the entire dataset of 2D osteometric raw data collected for this study and used throughout the analyses is attached in the supplementary materials (Tabs. S2.28 to S2.31). The same practice was applied to any obtained statistical results used to support the interpretations in here. However, it was not possible to print the collected 3D semilandmark coordinates due to the enormous size of this dataset. However, this data will be made publicly available once the results of this study are published.

3.3 Dataset Structure

Two different types of osteometric main datasets (Fig. 4) of traditional 2D osteometric as well as 3D sliding semilandmark data, all newly collected from the same cranial specimens from Berlin, are analyzed and compared against each other in order to evaluate their discriminating potential between sexes within each population and between populations to estimate the sex and population affinity of unknown human remains. The 2D osteometric dataset consists of two commonly measured FM variables and one index value derived from these two measurements.

Fig. 4: Graphic overview showing the general structure of the 2D and 3D sub-datasets used in this study, including the reference dataset of summary statistics published in the FM literature. See the text for further explanations. Note that the base dataset structure is the same for the intra- and interpopulation analyses. Here, only the composition of the samples may vary. lnCS = natural logarithm of the centroid size.

The 3D GM dataset contains a fixed-landmark/sliding-semilandmark configuration of 40 landmark points in total used in two kinds of GM analyses: to infer shape and form (size and shape) differences between sexes and/or populations. Note that the basic dataset structures of both original 2D and 3D sub-datasets as presented in Figure 4 are essentially the same for the intra- and interpopulation analyses, and only the composition and specimen selection of the analyzed samples differ as described below (Section 3.4.1). This means that both the analyses of sex and population differences in the morphology of the FM will follow the exact same working pipeline using the same overall methods. In addition to those two main datasets, a third FM dataset, representing a large compendium of already published 2D FM

summary statistic data from the literature, was collected for this study. This reference data will be used in this study in an additional meta-analysis that aims to present further insights into the global trends of the morphological FM variation in combination with the newly collected 2D FM data from the Berlin samples.

3.4.1 Sample Grouping of the Berlin Samples

The newly collected 2D osteometric and 3D landmark-based datasets were subset in different ways for the intra- and interpopulation analyses. However, no differences were drawn between the subsetting strategies between those two sub-datasets, meaning that both types of datasets have been subset according to the same principles as described in the following: for the intrapopulation analysis, each population was divided into a female and male subgroup. Individuals whose sex could not clearly be identified (ind) were not included in this analysis. A total of eight groups for the within-population analysis were used: two groups, females, and males, per population, which will be statistically compared with each other. For the interpopulation analysis, sexes were pooled for each population and added to the sex-unknown individuals to increase the number of specimens per population wherever possible. In total, four different groups are used for the between-population analysis – one sex-pooled group for each of the four populations.

3.4.2 Sample Grouping of the Reference Dataset

For the additional meta-analyses, the compiled 2D reference datasets also had to be grouped, as some populations were represented by numerous studies, whereas for others only a single or a few papers could be found. For example, India and Turkey are represented by 37 and 12 studies, respectively, whereas for most of the other populations, only a single or a few studies could have been found (Tabs. S3.20 and S3.21). Whenever summary statistic data from several studies was available for a single population, these data were summarized by averaging. When possible, overall summary statistics were separately calculated for each sex group. As is done with the main dataset of the Berlin samples, only the sex-separated subgroups are used in the intrapopulation meta-analysis. For the interpopulation perspective, the osteometric FM data of sex-known subgroups have been averaged together with the sex-unknown samples (labeled as F/M), if present, to derive an overall, sex-pooled population sample (labeled as ALL in table S3.21). An exception was only made for Zdilla et al. (2017), where broad-continental groups were included in the analysis (i.e., Africa, East Asia, and Europe) alongside individual geographical human populations (i.e., Bengal, Malaysia, and Peru). Such broader geographical groups are taken as they are. In addition to averaging FM data from the population-specific studies, continental means for Africa, North and South

America, Asia, and Europe have also been calculated to get insights into the overall continental comparison. The newly resulting overall summary values per population (and each continent) are summarized in Table S3.21.

3.5 Data Collection

3.5.1 Linear, 2D Osteometric Measurements

The first of the three main datasets (D.1) in this study comprises traditional, linear, or 2D osteometric measurements of the FM (Fig. 5). All 2D FM measurements were physically measured in millimeters only by the author and directly from the dry skulls using a digital sliding caliper (Aickar, 0.01 mm accuracy). All craniometric measuring points, linear measurements, and index values used in this study are commonly utilized FM metrics that follow the definitions given in Bräuer (1988). For the osteometric analyses of the FM, two measurements are of particular importance (Fig. 5):

- 1) *Foramen magnum length* (FML) – defined as the straight, sagittal distance of the FM; measured from *Basion* (ba) to *Opisthion* (o). This measurement usually represents the largest or maximum sagittal diameter of the FM (Bräuer, 1988, #7).
- 2) *Foramen magnum breadth* (FMB) – defined as the largest or maximum straight and transversal diameter of the FM (Bräuer, 1988, #16). Note that these two lateral FM measuring endpoints have not been given defined names, as was the case for the previous FM measurement.

FML and FMB measurements were physically taken twice (named FML/B_1 and FML/B_2) to evaluate the intraobserver rates of these measurements for more reliable subsequent analysis (see below). Both measurements have also been measured a third time (named FML/B_M), virtually on the post-processed 3D Artec models after loading them into the MeshLab software (Cignoni et al., 2008) (see below). To measure the sagittal and transversal FM distances, the software's Measuring Tool in the Toolbar has been used following the instructions given in an unpublished MeshLab user guide written by the author (Göldner, 2020b). The virtual measurement repetitions of both FM variables are, however, not used in the subsequent analysis. They were only meant to validate the correct size scaling of the 3D models, which, if incorrect, could negatively influence the later 3D form analysis, considering size as an additional variable. For the subsequent 2D analyses, only the average calculated from the two physical measurement repetitions of FML and FMB will be used.

Fig. 5: FML and FMB measurements. Ectocranial view. Anterior is facing upwards. ba = Basion, o = Opisthion. Pictured individual is the same as in Figures 1a and 1b and has not been included in this study.

These mean FML and FMB repetition values of each specimen were then used to calculate the *foramen magnum index* (FMI) of each individual. The FMI is calculated as the relative aspect ratio of the FM breadth divided by the FM length and multiplied by 100 (Bräuer, 1988, #133):

$$FMI = \frac{FMB}{FML} \times 100$$

In traditional physical anthropology, osteometric indices such as the FMI are considered descriptive shape indicators that are often used to study osteometric shapes based on 2D measurement data. Following Bräuer (1988), the FMI can be divided into three distinctive shape categories: *narrow* ($FMI \leq 81.9$), *intermediate* ($82.0 \leq FMI \leq 85.9$), and *wide* ($FMI \geq 86.0$).

3.5.2 3D Data Collection

3.5.2.1 3D Surface Scanning and 3D Model Post-Processing

To be able to collect 3D landmark data points, each skull from Berlin included in this study had to be 3D scanned to generate digital copies of the specimens. Due to the limited time at the Berlin collections, only a small number of skulls were completely scanned (Fig. 6b), namely all Japanese skulls as well as all German skulls from the S-Collection except for S 5164, that were also used by Leah Böttger in her thesis project (Böttger, 2021). To save time

by speeding up the scanning process and enabling the inclusion of more crania, only the cranial base focusing on the FM of the remaining cranial specimens was scanned and processed (Fig. 6c). All complete skulls and cranial bases were scanned using an Artec Space Spider single-hand scanner (Artec 3D Inc., Luxembourg), which has been thankfully provided by the Department of Early Prehistory and Quaternary Ecology of the Eberhard Karls University in Tübingen, Germany. The scanner uses structured blue light to produce highly accurate virtual 3D surface scans with an accuracy of 0.1 mm and a resolution of down to 0.05 mm, as reported on the producer's website (<https://www.artec3d.com/de/portable-3d-scanners/artec-spider>). When connected to a computer with the Artec Studio software, the specimens can be scanned in real-time, which makes the scanning procedure intuitively easy and fast. In the case of the FM, this is of particular importance, as the FM is one of the most difficult structures to access and capture with light- or laser-based scanning techniques (Katz and Friess, 2014).

During the scanning procedure in the Berlin collection, the software Artec Studio 13 Professional x64 (version 13.2.1.13) installed on a high-performance laptop was used. Every skull was placed on a manual turntable to be easily scanned from all sides. For the complete skull scans, at least three separate scanning rounds were necessary: first, where the skull was rested on its base, and second, where it was flipped over to rest on its cranial roof, which has been realized using an organic ring stand. During the first and second scans, the skull on the turntable was turned at moderate speed around its own axis until the 360-degree round was completed. At this point, the first scan was terminated, and the skull was flipped over to start the second round, which followed the same scanning approach. To ensure that all edges of the FM were captured accurately, each skull was repositioned on the ring stand to be scanned a third time by placing them on the back portion of their occipital bones while the viscerocranium was facing upwards. The scanner was then guided starting at the anterior portion of the FM and was slowly moved down and upwards by simultaneously slowly swinging the scanner to the left and right, whereas the turntable was rotated back and forwards around 50 degrees. This scanning technique of the third capturing round was also applied when only the cranial base of a skull was scanned and not the entire cranium (Fig. 6c).

Next, the individual sub-scans were checked in Artec Studio for larger areas that were missed during the initial scanning procedure or for the occurrence of other model inconsistencies. If such areas were identified, the affected sub-scan was deleted and rescanned, or an additional scan of the missing area was taken to fill gaps rapidly. In the *Align* menu, the *Auto-alignment* option was applied in the following to automatically combine all sub-scans together (Fig. 6a). To finally merge the sub-scans together, *Global registration* and *Sharp fusion* from the *Tool* menu were used without changing the default settings of both options. To clean and heal any surface model inconsistencies, *Small-object filter* (*Remove surfaces* set to: *All except largest*) and *Hole filling* (*Hole perimeter (max)*, mm set to 100) in the *Tool* menu were also used. Afterwards, by using the *Eraser* tool (*Rectangular selection*) in the

Editor menu, each model was cropped so that only the FM area remained to reduce the overall model and file size (Figs. 6d and 6e). In the final post-processing step, the mesh of each FM scan was simplified down to two million polygons using the *Mesh simplification* tool again in the *Tool* menu (*Target when simplifying: Polygon count; Polygon count: 2,000,000* (approximately 1,000,000 vertices); *Keep edges* not enabled). This polygon count represented the best solution to maintain high model quality and a small file size (approximately 0.05 Gigabyte per FM model) at the same time to ensure accurate representation of the specimen's anatomy and to be successfully loaded into the R package *geomorph* for landmark collection (see below).

After all post-processing steps, every 3D model was exported from Artec Studio as an STL file and saved on a computer. Likewise, the Artec project file (SPROJ file) has been saved along with the 3D model. For the next step, each STL model has been imported and opened into the MeshLab software. The unification of duplicated vertices was enabled. The opened model was rotated and translated to the center of origin before FML and FMB were virtually measured with the ruler tool (Section 3.5.1). Finally, the translated and measured model was exported as a non-binary encoded PLY file to be loaded and opened in *geomorph* in R (see below). All other saving options and parameters were left blank. Copies of the processed 3D models burned on a CD were handed over to the Berlin collection curators.

Fig. 6a to 6e: whole-cranium Artec scan of S 5165. a) Aligned but not yet merged and post-processed raw scans. Each individual's scan is represented in a different color. b) Finalized 3D model after all post-processing steps. c) to e) Cranium-base Artec scan of RV 514. c) Cranium base scan after all post-processing steps. d) Inverted eraser selection of the FM area. e) cropped and simplified FM area model that is ready for next step of landmark collection. Both individuals are included in this study. All models are shown in orthographic view in the Artec Studio 13 software. Figures are not to scale. 'Flat', smooth areas represent regional surface interpolations to fill holes and edges.

3.5.2.2 3D Landmark Configuration and Collection

Landmark-based approaches are the most widely used type of data in GM analyses (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009). Two basic categories of landmarks exist. The first are fixed or finite landmarks that have been defined by Bookstein (1991) as homologous or directly corresponding and clearly defined anatomical loci on biological structures across specimens with unique 2D (x and y) or 3D (x, y, and z) Cartesian coordinates. Fixed landmarks can be subdivided into three different principal types: type 1 corresponds to landmarks that are clearly defined as the meeting points or juxtapositions of three anatomical structures; type 2 is defined as the maxima or extremes of curvatures such as foramina or tips of bony processes; and type 3 represents landmark points that are locally constructed based on multiple anatomical curves

and symmetry (Bookstein, 1991; Weber and Bookstein, 2011). The second basic category of landmarks are the so-called sliding semilandmarks, which have been introduced to capture anatomical structures such as outlines, curvatures, or surfaces that traditional fixed landmarks are not able to account for (Bookstein, 1991; Bookstein, 1997; Green, 1996; Gunz et al., 2005). The use of semilandmarks therefore provides a much higher and wider ability to study the anatomical variation of biological structures. However, because semilandmarks cannot be concisely defined, they are prone to showing higher intra- and interobserver errors in their placement. Semilandmarks can therefore not be considered as correspondent which is not problematic as long as the curve or surface, they intend to capture is homologous across specimens. To establish geometric correspondence semilandmark usually must be slid, which equalizes their distances and eradicates the effect of arbitrary spacing. After this step, semilandmarks can be analyzed the same way as fixed landmarks (Gunz and Mitteroecker, 2013; Perez et al., 2006). Consecutive to the three fixed landmark types, semilandmarks are also categorized into three types: type 4) comprises curve semilandmarks, type 5) refers to surface semilandmarks, and type 6) comprise all constructed semilandmarks (Weber and Bookstein, 2011).

There are four Bookstein type 2 fixed landmarks present at the FM that are the same measuring endpoints used to take the two linear distances, FML and FMB. These distances are usually measured in traditional osteometry (Section 3.5.1). However, these four fixed landmarks are not sufficient to metrically describe the shape/form of the FM, which, as a foramen, represents a closed anatomical curve, making it necessary to utilize semilandmarks (type 4 landmarks). In order to capture and analyze the FM outline properly, a new fixed-landmark/sliding-semilandmark configuration has been defined for the purpose of the GM part of the current study. This configuration consists of 40 landmarks in total, which were tightly placed manually and in a virtual space (in geomorph; see below) around the interior-most outline of the bony FM. Four of these landmarks represent the already mentioned landmarks, which are the Basion (ba, LM1) point at the anterior-most portion of the FM, Opisthion (op, LM31) at the posterior most point of the FM, and the lateral left (LL, LM21) and lateral right (LR, LM31) most points of the FM. Throughout the entire analysis, these four landmarks are treated as fixed landmarks, meaning that they are not slid like the remaining semilandmarks. In-between each of these four pairs of fixed landmarks (ba-LL, LL-op, op-LR, LR-ba), an equal number of nine sliding semilandmarks have been placed (and slid), making a total of 36 curve semilandmarks. This way, the FM is split into four segments or quarters represented by an equal number of semilandmarks: the first, anterior-lateral left FM quarter (ba-LL) with the semilandmarks LM2 to LM10, the second, posterior-lateral left quarter (LL-op) with LM12 to LM20, the third, posterior-lateral right quarter (op-LR) with LM21 to LM30, and the fourth and last, anterior-lateral right quarter (LR-ba) with the semilandmarks LM32 to LM40 (Fig. 7). The semilandmarks of each of these four semilandmark segments slide only between each fixed landmark pair they are enclosed by. In other words, each pair of fixed landmarks, defining one

quarter of the FM, represents a boundary for the semilandmarks beyond which they cannot slide. The starting point for the landmark placing procedure was the Basion point, from which nine semilandmarks are placed in a clockwise manner. As the 3D models are observed from the caudal, and therefore the body sides, left and right, are mirror-inverted, the placing direction is counter-clockwise. The 11th point, LR, is then placed the same way the other semilandmarks and Basion have been placed before. Then, again, nine semilandmarks are placed towards the 21st point, Opisthion. To complete the FM, this placing procedure was continued without interruption for the other half of the FM until the curvature was closed with the last, 40th landmark, directly before the Basion starting point.

Placing of the semilandmarks at the two posterior quarter segments of the FM (between LL-op and op-LR) is generally easier due to the usually sharp and thin edge and therefore clearly defined inner bony rim. On the contrary, locating and placing semilandmarks between ba-LL and LR-ba, the two anterior segments, is, however, much less intuitive given the usual lack of a clearly defined bone ridge, which is due to the presence of the often protruding and overlying AOC. This leads to a situation where the inner FM edge is often not visible in this area. In many previous FM shape studies, this was not problematic as the FM was treated as a 2D structure, especially when standardized planar FM photographs are used as is, for example, the case in the GM study by Zdilla et al. (2017). Such approaches to collecting landmark data cannot control the shape effect of the two condyles on the FM, as it is virtually impossible to access the FM regions beneath (superior to) the covering AOCs. On first sight, it appears valid to also account for the shape influence of AOC protrusion into the FM space, as it is an important factor for FM shape considerations, especially when relying on 2D media. In these cases, it might be impossible to avoid the AOC influence when using planar FM images. However, when using 3D models, one must face another problem, namely, establishing landmark homology in these areas as related to the covariation between FM and AOC morphology: due to variation in the relative position of both condyles, they are not always protruding into the FM. It was also observed that, in some cases, the condyles barely reach the FM, if at all. Another factor lies in the high variability of the condyle height profiles, which was recognized during sample screening for the present study. This might not have a huge influence on the plane 3D FM shape per se, but rather on its height profile, especially when captured with landmarks in three dimensions. Lastly, although the FM and both condyles have a close spatial and functional relationship, they can still be considered separate anatomical structures worth separate, independent investigation.

Fig. 7: Schematic overview of the fixed landmark/sliding semilandmark configuration of the FM. LM = (semi) landmark. Note that the left and right sides are interchanged because the FM in dry skulls is usually observed from below (inferior to superior or from postcranial to cranial direction).

As the current study aims to study the ‘pure’ FM shape not markedly influenced by surrounding structures such as the AOC, a landmark configuration in the anterior areas is needed that aims to minimize the aforementioned influential factors as much as possible while preserving the overall FM shape at the same time. A proper and practical solution to compensate for this much more complex local anatomical topography was found in using the shortest line of sight between the clearly traceable posterior FM outline posterior to LL and LR and the few landmarks that can easily be placed at the anterior-most section of the clearly defined, short anterior FM rim around the Basion that is usually similarly sharply defined. The shortest line of sight running over the bony bulges beneath (superior to) the AOC was visually constructed and followed during semilandmark placing. As described, this approach arguably represents the best practical and anatomically homologous semilandmark line that can be applied in this FM area, which also mostly avoids the influences of the protruding and overlying AOC and their effect on the FM shape. In consequence, this gives a nice perspective on studying the ‘pure’ FM outline and shape/form. An exact example of the applied landmark configuration used in this study is given in Figure S2.32.

Fig. S2.32a to S2.32f: FM fixed landmark/sliding semilandmark configuration shown on RV 721 (included in this study). a) View towards anterior. b) View towards posterior. c) View towards lateral left. d) View towards lateral right. e) View towards anterolateral right. f) View towards anterolateral left. Red points = semilandmarks, green dots = Basion, yellow dots = Opisthion, violet dot = most lateral left point (LL), blue dot = most lateral right point (LR). 3D model shown in geomorph in orthographic perspective. Figures are not to scale. Landmarks are not slid in these figures.

The landmark data in this study was manually collected in the R (Team, 2020) (R version 4.0.3 (2020-10-10)) package *geomorph* (Adams et al., 2021; Baken et al., 2021) (version 4.0.0) using the function *digit.fixed*. This function, together with the R package *rgl* (Adler et al., 2021) (version 0.104.16), opens an interactive window showing the 3D model of the FM of an individual after loading it into the R environment. The window enables the operator to drag the 3D model around for inspection and to manually place landmarks in the regions of interest. Each opened 3D model was consistently viewed only from a standardized orthographic perspective to reduce landmark placement errors due to skewed perspectives. All fixed landmarks and sliding semilandmarks were collected in the same manner and placed in roughly equidistant locations (Gunz & Mitteroecker 2013), one after another, as just described. To ensure the accuracy of the landmark positioning and to immediately identify any landmarks that eventually “fall through” the 3D mesh, each landmark was checked individually after placement. Because R only opens the vertices point clouds of the 3D models and not a solid (closed) surface model, landmarks tend to ‘fall through’ the vertices mesh, especially when there are model areas ‘beneath’ the target region. Checking the landmark position was done from two different perspectives by rotating the model in the *rgl* view window. If necessary, a mispositioned landmark was immediately deleted and placed again. After the landmark placing was completed, the landmark data was automatically saved as NTS files in the working directory of the computer for the following analysis. As for all specimens, the same number of landmarks has been collected; no resampling of the FM landmark curves was necessary to equalize landmark numbers.

3.5.2.3 3D Semilandmark Sliding

After the landmark collection step was completed for all specimens, a sliding algorithm was applied to only the roughly equidistant sliding landmarks. This optimized and equalized their relative positions by removing any effect of arbitrary spacing to establish the geometric homology of the overall curve across the entire sample (Gunz and Mitteroecker, 2013; Perez et al., 2006). Semilandmarks were only slid within the FM quarter they were placed in. Therefore, they do not exceed any of the four delimiting fixed landmarks, which stay at their initially assigned location, as their name indicates. Fixed landmarks and sliding semilandmarks were then treated the same way in follow-up statistical GM analyses (Gunz and Mitteroecker, 2013).

Generally, two different computational approaches are used in GM to slide semilandmarks to minimize differences in shapes between all specimens and the mean sample shape and to reduce arbitrary spacing of semilandmarks. Both approaches differ not just in the way they quantify shape differences but also in what is minimized during the sliding process. Their major differences lie within the geometric-mathematical procedure of how they

establish geometric homology between landmarks (Gunz and Mitteroecker, 2013). The first and most often applied criterion is called *Minimum Bending Energy*. It was initially described by Green (1996), Bookstein (1996a; 1997), and later again by Bookstein et al. (2002), as well as Gunz et al. (2005). Here, the bending energy between the mean sample shape and each individual specimen of the same sample is minimized by iterative sliding. The second alternative approach is based on the perpendicular projection or minimization of the Procrustes distance instead of bending energy between each specimen and the sample mean shape and is therefore called the *Procrustes criterion* (Bookstein et al., 2002; Sampson et al., 1996; Sheets et al., 2004). By using the first criterion, all semilandmarks are slid locally parallel to the contour of the captured anatomical structure. Thereby, the minimum bending energy that is needed to change the sample mean shape as a reference form into each individual specimen outline is minimized by using the smoothest deformation possible (Bookstein, 1996a; Sheets et al., 2004). As all semilandmarks are allowed to slide together, their relative deformational location changes are influenced by the entire landmark configuration (Gunz and Mitteroecker, 2013). When applying the Procrustes criterion, all semilandmarks slide separately without the influence of other (semi)landmarks (Gunz and Mitteroecker, 2013). Here, differences in the direction tangential to the curve between the reference form (i.e., mean sample shape) and all specimens are estimated individually. Then, the component differences that lie along these tangents are removed (Sheets et al., 2004). In the final sliding step, all semilandmarks of each specimen are aligned in such a way that they lie perpendicular along the lines relative to the curvature that passes through the corresponding semilandmarks of the mean reference (Sampson et al., 1996).

With the Procrustes criterion approach, it is possible that semilandmarks will slide beyond the position of other semilandmark locations or even the endpoint of the curvature, which is almost impossible with the bending energy criterion. However, such a problem more likely affects landmark configurations of particularly large and/or complex anatomical structures where semilandmarks slide over wider distances or when these display a considerably large biological variation. In these cases, minimum bending energy usually reveals better results regarding biological homology. When variation is low and sliding distances are short, it is noted that both criteria yield overall similar results (Gunz and Mitteroecker, 2013). As the dense FM landmark configuration defined here can be considered as a simple and small circular curvature, the aforementioned problems related to complexity and sliding distances can be assumed to be negligible. Furthermore, Gunz and Mitteroecker (2013) recommend including traditional fixed type 1 to 3 Bookstein landmarks (Bookstein, 1991) for the entire configuration that constrains the sliding movement directions and distances of semilandmarks. This is achieved here by using four fixed FM landmarks in the landmark-semilandmark configuration, meaning all FM semilandmarks can only slide between and along the outline section of their assigned FM quarter (see landmark configuration description in Section 3.5.2.2). Semilandmarks therefore only slide over submillimeter to millimeter

distances, depending on the coordinate axis. Taken together, the minimum Procrustes distance criterion was preferably chosen to slide the semilandmarks of the FM landmark data set. In doing so, this study accounts for the concerns raised by Perez et al. (2006) but also remains in agreement with Gunz and Mitteroecker (2013), who argue that both criteria do not diverge significantly, especially when the above-mentioned requirements are fulfilled.

In geomorph (Adams et al., 2021; Baken et al., 2021), the sliding algorithm for the semilandmarks is implemented as argument *ProcD* in the Procrustes superimposition function *gpagen* (see next chapter). To apply the minimum Procrustes distance criterion, the logical value for *ProcD* was set to *True*. After successful Procrustes transformation, the Procrustes coordinates were then saved as an NTS file for subsequent analysis. To not cause biases throughout the GM analyses, two sets of landmarks had to be slid separately: one for the 83 sex-known cranial specimens included in the intrapopulation analysis and one for the 98 sex-known and unknown individuals in the interpopulation analysis.

3.5.2.4 3D Landmark Standardization using Generalized Procrustes Analysis

As mentioned above, shape reflected by landmark data is defined as the geometric information of an object or specimen of interest after the removal of differences caused by location (position in space), orientation, and scale or size, whereas the latter is preserved for the analysis of form or allometry (Bookstein, 1991; Bookstein, 1996b). Generally, these factors are removed using a landmark coordinate transformation procedure called partial Procrustes superimposition, which is a least-squares fitting-oriented approach to compute so-called Procrustes shape coordinates (Rohlf, 1999; Slice, 2001). This standardization of sets of landmark coordinates is achieved during the *Generalized Procrustes Analysis* (GPA) (Gower, 1975; Rohlf, 1990; Rohlf and Slice, 1990), which consists of three steps: 1) centring to the same center point, 2) scaling to the same size, and 3) rotation to the same orientation (Gunz and Mitteroecker, 2013). 1) In the first step of the Procrustes standardization, the location of each landmark configuration is translated to the cartesian origin ($x = 0$, $y = 0$, $z = 0$), meaning that all specimens share the same position, i.e., centroid. For this, all coordinates (x , y , z) of every landmark of each specimen must first be averaged to obtain the mean coordinate position, or centroid, which is then subtracted from all landmarks to center the entire configuration. This effectively removes any differences due to location (Gunz and Mitteroecker, 2013; Perez et al., 2006). 2) For the second step, the landmark configurations are scaled to the same centroid size (CS), which is calculated as the square root of the summed squared differences between the centroid minus all landmarks. By convention, the CS is set to 1 by dividing the specimen's coordinates by its initial centroid size. CS is used as a measure of size, which is approximately uncorrelated with shape (Bookstein, 1991; Dryden and Mardia, 1998). 3) To achieve the same orientation of all specimen landmark configurations, each of the

configurations must be rotated around its centroid until the sum of the squared Euclidian distances between all corresponding or homologous landmarks is minimal. This is realized using an iterative algorithm for the rotation step (Gower, 1975; Rohlf and Slice, 1990). First, all configurations are aligned to a single arbitrary reference specimen configuration of the same used sample set until the sum of squared differences between them is minimized. New coordinates for each configuration are obtained this way, which are averaged to a new reference form and then again rotated to fit this new consensus. To equalize the rotation of all specimens, this process is repeated until convergence is archived, and the mean shape does not substantially change (Gunz and Mitteroecker, 2013; Perez et al., 2006; Rohlf, 1999). Now, all specimens are partially Procrustes superimposed onto the mean shape configuration. The average or consensus configuration of all Procrustes coordinates represents the mean shape of the entire transformed landmark dataset (Dryden and Mardia, 1998). Differences of all coordinates from this mean shape configuration are labeled Procrustes residuals, and the Euclidian pairwise distance between two Procrustes shape configurations (i.e., between the standardized landmark sets of two specimens), called *Procrustes distance*, is calculated as the square root of the sum of the squared, coordinate-wise difference (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009). Procrustes distances are used as a measure of similarity and dissimilarity between two landmark configurations or between the mean configurations of two or more groups (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009). In a full Procrustes superimposition, the CS is allowed to vary from 1 to further reduce distances between the reference and all specimens (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009; Rohlf, 1999). However, partial superimposition is usually favored (Perez et al., 2006; Rohlf, 1999; Slice, 2001).

Because size information is effectively eliminated during the scaling step of the GPA, GM analysis of Procrustes shape coordinates can only infer information about shape but not form. However, size can often be considered an important factor in biological-morphological analysis, as already outlined. For example, size might be useful to consider when analyzing between-sex differences, as size is known to play an important role in sexually dimorphic species like *Homo sapiens* (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009), which is reflected in the intrapopulation analysis in this study. As demonstrated by Mitteroecker et al. (2004; 2005), the natural logarithm of the CS ($\ln CS$) can be used in combination with Procrustes shape coordinates to convert them from *Procrustes shape* to *Procrustes form space* (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009).

The GPA of the collected landmarks was done using the *gpagen* function in the geomorph package (Adams et al., 2021; Baken et al., 2021), which also includes the sliding function for the semilandmarks. The values for the CS of each individual used in the GM form analyses are obtained during the GPA process. The CS data was saved as a separate file, and their natural logarithms ($\ln CS$) have been calculated in MS Excel. As mentioned in the previous section, the entire landmark set does not have to slide together, as the number of

individuals between the within- and between-population analyses is not equal. As sliding and GPA are performed together in geomorph, this notion also applies to landmark standardization. To repeat the above-mentioned, this means that GPA was performed separately for 1) the sex-known sample altogether and then 2) the sex-pooled sample, including the sex-unknown individuals.

3.6 Measurement Error Analysis

Evaluating observer measurement error rates in quantitative research is an important task, as errors can never be completely avoided due to a wide variety of factors, which are either *random* or *systematic* in nature. The cause of random errors lies within the intrinsic biological variation of the measured variables or other measurement-related errors like deviations from the used protocol, instrument error, external environmental conditions, operator error, and so on. Systematic errors are caused by biases that are either constant, fixed, or proportional. In consequence, it must be evaluated whether the obtained data lies within an acceptable range of difference or not (Earthman, 2015). In general, there are two main effects of measurement errors on the quality of collected data: the first influences the extent to which repeated measurements lead to the same values (Habicht et al., 1979). Here, the conceptual terms reliability and unreliability, reproducibility and repeatability, undependability, precision, and imprecision play major roles in describing the origin and causation of measurement errors (Habicht et al., 1979; Heymsfield et al., 1984; Mueller and Martorell, 1988; Pederson and Gore, 1996). The second effect influences the extent to which a measurement diverges from a 'real' or 'true' value of the measured variable (Habicht et al., 1979). Concept terms important to the latter category of measurement error effects are accuracy and inaccuracy, bias, as well as validity (Earthman, 2015; Habicht et al., 1979; Heymsfield et al., 1984; Mueller and Martorell, 1988; Pederson and Gore, 1996; Ulijaszek and Kerr, 1999). It is crucial for any error analysis that these terms, their underlying key concepts, and their relation to each other are well understood. They are therefore briefly defined in the following:

Precision refers to the degree of agreement or consistency among repeated measurements using a particular method, or, in other words, how well the same results are produced by a particular method that is repeatably used at different times to measure the same variable on the same specimen (Earthman, 2015; Mony et al., 2016). The variability of repeated measurements due to intra- and/or interobserver errors is expressed as *imprecision* (Ulijaszek and Kerr, 1999). *Reliability* in this framework can be seen as within-subject variability due to factors not related to measurement error variance or variation in the physiology of the studied specimen. The variability here is affected by factors such as observer-related influences like difficulties in locating landmarks (Mony et al., 2016; Ulijaszek and Kerr, 1999). Both precision

and reliability are affected by random error (Ludbrook, 1997). *Unreliability*, on the contrary, represents the measurement error variance (Mueller and Martorell, 1988) and describes the exact opposite of reliability: within-subject variability due to only those two factors, making it a function of biological error (Ulijaszek and Kerr, 1999). *Undependability* is caused by physiological variation (e.g., body height changes across the day due to spinal column compression) (Ulijaszek and Kerr, 1999), which can arguably be almost completely negligible, as this may only apply for living biological structures and not for dead, osteological specimens whose biological-physiological structure does not significantly change after death (only if no major taphonomic alterations take place, e.g., shrinking due to heat exposure). Taken together, the sum of both imprecision and undependability results in an overall degree of unreliability (Ulijaszek and Kerr, 1999). A method is considered reliable if its precision is high and its imprecision low, meaning that its variability between repeated measurements of the same variable is considerably small (Norton and Olds, 1996; Ulijaszek and Kerr, 1999), leading to high levels of repeatability and reproducibility (Earthman, 2015; Ulijaszek and Kerr, 1999). *Repeatability* in this sense refers to variability between sets of repetitions of a variable measured by one observer using the same measuring device under the same conditions. *Reproducibility* only differs from repeatability in that a different observer remeasures the same variable on the same specimen (Earthman, 2015). This implies that only repeatability is considered in this study, as only one observer (the author) has measured and remeasured FM variables (and landmarks). In anthropometric literature, observer error also refers to the *technical error of measurement* (TEM), which is the most widely used measure of imprecision and measures the SD between repeated measurements (Goto and Mascie-Taylor, 2007; Mueller and Martorell, 1988; Ulijaszek and Kerr, 1999). Methods with high technical observer errors usually reveal lower levels of precision (Earthman, 2015). Despite the technical error, other commonly applied statistics to access the random error-related aspects of reliability and precision are *test-retest correlation coefficients*, *intraclass correlation coefficient* (ICC), *standard deviation* (SD), *reliability coefficient* (R), and *coefficient of variance* (CV) (Earthman, 2015). Before the second main type of measurement errors is presented, note that there is another, less commonly used definition of the precision concept used in the calculation of the limits of agreement in the Bland-Altman method (Altman and Bland, 1983), which is described further below. Here, precision is defined as the closeness of repeated measurements between one method compared to a gold standard or reference method used as such (Earthman, 2015).

The second type of measurement error effect, which aims to approach the 'true' value, involves concepts of accuracy and bias (Earthman, 2015). As it seems, according to the literature, there are at least two definitions of *accuracy*: 1) the closeness of agreement of a measured variable using two methods (Earthman, 2015), and 2) the extent to which a measurement approaches the 'real' or 'true' value (Mony et al., 2016; Mueller and Martorell, 1988; Ulijaszek and Kerr, 1999). *Inaccuracy* refers to the systematic bias caused by either instrument error or error in the applied measurement technique (Ulijaszek and Kerr, 1999). It

describes the differences between one method and the reference approach and is usually calculated as the mean of the differences of the measured variable between two methods. In general, there are two schools of thought when it comes to how to address accuracy: the first demands an average of all measurements close to what the reference method means for a method to be accurate. The difference between both means should be close to zero. Proper statistical methods to establish accuracy following this aim are paired t-tests and correlation statistics. On the other hand, it is also possible to seek high levels of closeness of all individual measurements between two measuring approaches before a method can be considered accurate. A commonly used approach to establishing accuracy following this line of thought is the Bland-Altman analysis (Altman and Bland, 1983), which uses limits of agreements as well as the calculation of different error terms (Earthman, 2015). As in the last term, *validity* is used to describe whether a measurement is suitable to measure a trait (Norton and Olds, 1996). As noted by Ulijaszek and Kerr (1999), validity is conceptually close to accuracy in that the 'true' or 'real' value of a variable cannot be captured exactly.

It should be noted that many statistics to infer metrics of accuracy, precision, and so on are based on similar mathematical principles, often only slightly adjusted (Earthman, 2015). By repeating measurements and quantifying the above-mentioned aspects using proper metrics, unavoidable measurement errors can be minimized and quantified (Langley et al., 2018; Mony et al., 2016). Besides general measures taken to ensure high levels of data quality and transparency (Goto and Mascie-Taylor, 2007; Mony et al., 2016), several of the mentioned error estimation methods are applied to the new osteometric FM data, which are presented in the following. Note that all these methods are parametric; hence, they demand specific data characteristics, such as normality, to be fulfilled. Although these methods are represented in the next chapters and, therefore, before the statistical data analyses, including checking for parametric requirements, they have been tested and assessed before the error analyses were conducted.

3.6.1 General Aspects of Data Quality Controls

To reduce the occurrence of potential typing errors, data has been copied instead of manually written whenever possible. Likewise, and wherever possible, the entire dataset was copied all together. To check for typographical errors in labels and measurements, pre-version boxplots of the raw data were produced (not reported here). Although being a graduate student in his master studies at the time this study took place, the author already had five years of experience in anthropological data acquisition in both traditional osteometry and landmark-based GM approaches. In the framework for this study and due to contact restrictions because of the current Sars-Covid-19 pandemic, osteometric error estimations were only conducted on an intraobserver (one measuring subject, the author) and not on an interobserver (between

different subjects) basis. Before data collection, a measuring tool (digital sliding caliper, Aickar) was chosen with measurement accuracy (0.01 mm) far below the generally accepted osteometric measurement error of 2 mm. This measuring tool was always kept well-maintained and was cleaned of dust after every use to maintain accurate measuring abilities. Before the first use as well as after every single measurement was taken, the digital sliding caliper was slid to its starting position and then manually set to zero using its inbuilt reset function. Regular calibration and resetting to zero also ensured quick identification of potential program and measurement errors. Before the first use, the zeroed caliper was tested against a standardized metric ruler (i.e., a measuring distance of 45 mm). All these steps followed the recommendations for anthropometric measuring practices published in Mony et al. (2016).

3.6.1 Intraobserver Error in the 2D Osteometric Dataset

3.6.1.1 Acceptable Osteometric Error for Linear Measurements

To obtain more valid results FML and FMB of each specimen from Berlin have been physically measured two times with the digital sliding caliper on two different occasions at the Berlin collections, with more than six months between both dates. As per convention, a difference of 2 mm is generally accepted between osteometric measurement repetitions (Bräuer, 1988; Katz and Friess, 2014). To determine whether each pair of physical measurements per individual lies below this 2 mm threshold, the second repetition was subtracted from the first one. The resulting difference or residual values were labeled FML_Δ1 and FMB_Δ1. Whenever a pair of physical measurement repetitions displayed a value above this 2 mm threshold, the respective measurement of the individuals in question would have been measured physically a third time. If the error continued to lie above 2 mm, the individual would have been ultimately excluded from further analyses. In cases where the third physical remeasurement would be smaller than the excessively large first or second repetition, this new measurement would have been used to replace the high-erroneous value.

Although the scanning error of the Artec Space Spider scanner is known to be extremely small, with a resolution of 0.05 mm and an accuracy of 0.1 mm, an attempt was also made to validate the correct scaling of the produced 3D surface models by using a physical-to-virtual measurement comparison of the FML and FMB variables. This was mainly done to rule out the possibility of potentially occurring changes in the scaling of the 3D models during post-processing steps in Artec Studio or MeshLab, as only the physically gathered measurements are used in the 2D analyses. Although isometric size-related scaling of the models would not affect the GM shape analysis, where the size variable is effectively ruled out, scaling errors would have caused significant troubles in GM form analyses where the size components are maintained. Therefore, both FML and FMB measurements were also measured virtually on each of the PLY models in MeshLab using the software's ruler tool, as

described in the methods. To check whether the virtual measurements would fall beneath the accepted threshold margin of 2 mm, the MeshLab measurements (FML_M and FMB_M) have been subtracted from the mean of both physical measurement repetitions (\bar{X}) to calculate the difference between the physical and virtual repetitions (Δ_2).

To identify residual values in Δ_1 and Δ_2 above 2 mm, the osteometric dataset was copied to a MS Excel sheet where the advanced searching tool was applied to visually highlight values above a specific value, in this case the 2 mm threshold (*under MS Excel \ Start \ Conditional Formatting \ Highlight Cells Rules \ Greater Than \ Highlight Cells that are greater than: 20* [for millimeter units]). Calculated differences (Δ_1 and Δ_2) as well as the mean value for FML and FMB repetitions one and two are reported in Tables S2.28 to S2.31. Note that this threshold also plays an important role in the application of the Bland-Altman analysis presented in the next section.

3.6.1.2 Bland-Altman Analysis

A simple, parametric approach to visually detecting dispersion among paired differences of repeated quantitative measurements is the limits of agreement (LoA) method proposed by Altman and Bland (1983), which takes the relation between the mean of each pair of measurements as the best possible approximation of the unknown 'real' or 'true' value of their respective differences or residuals into account (Sedgwick, 2013). The Bland-Altman analysis represents an alternative approach to correlation-based methods such as LCCC or TEM (Parker et al., 2020), presented below. The LoA can simply be calculated using the mean of all paired measurement differences (i.e., bias) \pm 1.96 standard deviations (SD) to obtain its lower and upper 95% confidence interval margins. The range of LoA has been described as a measure of repeatability and precision, following the above-mentioned alternative definition of that term (Altman and Bland, 1983; Earthman, 2015). All this information can be graphically presented in a so-called Bland-Altman plot, or BA-plot (XY-scatter plot). In practice, the BA-plot is similar to common residual plots after model-fitting and can be used to easily estimate the magnitude of disagreement (error and bias) in repeated data and to detect outliers and trends in the repeated datasets (Altman and Bland, 1983). Error in this case refers to the SD of the differences due to systematic measurement errors, whereas their mean represents the relative bias. The calculated means of all repeated measurement pairs are drawn on the X-axis and plotted against their difference or residual scores shown on the Y-axis. In addition to the individually calculated mean versus residuals data points for each measured pair, the mean of all residuals or bias is plotted as a horizontal mean line, also called the line of equality (Sedgwick, 2013), enclosed by its lower and upper 95% confidence interval margins at the bottom and top of the plot, outlining the LoA in the plot (Altman and Bland, 1983). For better visual representation and subsequent interpretation, the individual error margins of each of

these three lines can also be calculated and added to the BA-plot. From a general point of view, it can be concluded that a set of repetitions is more dissimilar the wider the range of the LoA is (Parker et al., 2020). However, to properly interpret the plot, an acceptable error range (also called clinically acceptable difference or CAD) must be defined a priori, which refers to a range in which differences can be considered negligible and which must be inferred according to a variety of external factors and considerations discussed in the respective scientific discipline (Kalra, 2017; Parker et al., 2020). Sets of repetition can be considered in overall agreement and therefore interchangeable when the LoA range lies within these CAD limits (Parker et al., 2020). For craniometric data, a CAD of ± 2 mm from the residual mean can be set as appropriate following the above-mentioned threshold for acceptable measurement errors in osteometry (Bräuer, 1988; Katz and Friess, 2014). Following the general expectations for uniformly normal-distributed data, it is recommended that 95% of the data plots in a BA-plot should lie within the limits of agreement range (Earthman, 2015; Kalra, 2017; Sedgwick, 2013). For this study, BA-plots for both separated sets of repeated physical measurements of FML and FMB were produced using the R packages *BlandAltmanLeh* (Lehnert, 2015) (version 0.3.1) and *ggplot2* (Wickham, 2016) (version 3.3.2).

3.6.1.3 Technical Error

To further quantify the intraobserver error, more specifically, the variability of the observer's (the author) measurement repetitions, the absolute and relative technical error of measurement (aTEM and %TEM, respectively) are used (Mueller and Martorell, 1988). The TEM represents an index metric or measure of imprecision that measures the standard deviation (SD, square root of variance) between sets of measurement repetitions (Goto and Mascie-Taylor, 2007; Ulijaszek and Kerr, 1999). For this study, TEM is calculated for 1) only the two physical measurement repetitions (aTEM₁) as well as 2) for all three repetitions – the two physical and one virtual MeshLab measurement (aTEM₂). A step-by-step instruction to calculate aTEM and %TEM is reported in Oliveira et al. (2005). In theory, the aTEM₁ for only two measurements carried out by one observer (also called intraobserver TEM or intra-TEM) is calculated as:

$$aTEM_1 = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_1^N \Delta^2}{2N}}$$

where Δ^2 represents the squared difference between the first and second repetitions (of either the FML or FMB variables) and N is the sample size (of all included cranial specimens, N =

98) (Goto and Mascie-Taylor, 2007). The aTEM₂ for more than two repetitions is calculated using the following equation:

$$aTEM_2 = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_1^N \left[\sum_1^K M(n)^2 - \frac{\sum_1^K M(n)^2}{K} \right]}{N(K-1)}}$$

where N stands again for the sample size (N = 98), K for the number of repeated measuring rounds of the single observer (K = 3, physically measured repetitions one and two as well as the virtual MeshLab measurement), M for the measurement (either FML or FMB), and lastly M(n) for the nth repetitions of the respective measurement (Goto and Mascie-Taylor, 2007; Langley et al., 2018; Mony et al., 2016; Oliveira et al., 2005). aTEM values do positively correlate with the size of the measurement, meaning that larger mean values of those measurements are associated with higher aTEM metrics and vice versa. In consequence, this leads to the problem that the aTEM of different variables, with or without the same scale or units, and from different populations are not directly comparable. For this reason, aTEM is usually converted into %TEM to measure the precision or imprecision unaffected by scale, type, unit of variable, or sample size (n) (Norton and Olds, 1996). Other than the aTEM, %TEM represents a measure of coefficient of variation (CV) without unit and can therefore be used to directly compare all types of different osteometric measurements (Langley et al., 2018; Mony et al., 2016; Ulijaszek and Kerr, 1999). %TEM has also been described as an estimate of error magnitude relative to the size of the measurement, which is analogous to the coefficient of variation (R; see next section) (Goto and Mascie-Taylor, 2007). %TEM is calculated by the division of the aTEM by the mean of the variable and multiplied by 100 to be expressed in percentages (%):

$$\%TEM_{(1\ or\ 2)} = \frac{aTEM_{(1\ or\ 2)}}{Variable\ mean_{(1\ or\ 2)}} \times 100$$

The %TEM in this study has been calculated separately for the two and three repetition datasets, using aTEM₁ and aTEM₂, respectively. No defined acceptable intraobserver range of aTEM for osteometric measurements could be found. In general, the lower the aTEM value, the better the reliability of the repetitions (i.e., more similar measurements). As reported in the literature, the acceptable range for the %TEM of a single observer in osteometry lies below (<) 1.5% (< 2% for the interobserver range) (Goto and Mascie-Taylor, 2007). In practice, the

aTEM₂ and %TEM₂ for the present 2D FM data were calculated using the available pre-coded MS Excel spreadsheet by Langley et al. (2018) (DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2018.04.148>). Codes and columns within this spreadsheet had to be manually adjusted by the author to fit the counts and repetitions of the present data as well as the number of observers that had to be reduced to one. The base structure of the codes and their calculations, however, have not been altered. Although it would have been possible to also adjust Langley et al.'s codes for the aTEM₂ and %TEM₂ calculations, for aTEM₁ and %TEM₁, the author programmed a new set of codes in Excel following the formula given by Goto and Mascie-Taylor (2007) for a set of only two repetitions as described above.

3.6.1.4 Coefficient of Reliability

The coefficient of reliability (R) represents another measure of imprecision, which is the most widely used error metric in anthropometric population studies (Mueller and Martorell, 1988; Ulijaszek and Kerr, 1999). It is used to obtain information on the comparability of osteometric measurement error by revealing the proportion of within-population between-subject variance excluding measurement error (Ulijaszek and Kerr, 1999). See Ulijaszek and Kerr (1999) for a more detailed explanation of the mathematical background of R and its relation to TEM. R can be determined using aTEM and divided by the squared standard deviation (SD) based on all values of the respective variable (inter-subject variance, including measurement error) (Goto and Mascie-Taylor, 2007). Like with the aTEM and %TEM, R was also calculated for the two-repetition set and the three-repetition set:

$$R_{(1 \text{ or } 2)} = 1 - \left(\frac{(aTEM_{(1 \text{ or } 2)})^2}{SD^2_{(1 \text{ or } 2)}} \right).$$

This formula was adapted and coded in the same Excel spreadsheet in which the aTEM and %TEM have also been calculated (see above). The value for R ranges from 0 (not reliable) to 1 (completely reliable) (Goto and Mascie-Taylor, 2007). Although there is no consensus on how to interpret R, Ulijaszek and Kerr (1999) and Ulijaszek and Lourie (1994) suggest that a cut-off value of 0.95 (i.e., an observer measurement error of up to 5% while the remaining 95% of the variance can be explained by other factors than measurement errors) can be used to decide whether a set of repetitions is imprecise or not.

3.6.1.5 Lin's Concordance Correlation Coefficient

Another index metrics that can be used to evaluate the intraobserver error or amount of agreement of the repeated linear measurements FML and FMB is Lin's concordance correlation coefficient (LCCC, also called ρ_c) (Lin, 1989). When investigating the agreement between two sets of repetitions, the LCCC has an advantage over other validation statistics (e.g., Pearson's correlation coefficient, paired t-tests, least squares analysis with a slope of one and an intercept of zero, coefficient of variation, or the intraclass correlation coefficient), as they cannot fully quantify the reproducibility characteristics of a set of repetitions, especially in certain cases discussed in Lin (1989). Here, the LCCC is used as a standardized coefficient and measure of accuracy and precision of repeated, bivariate (two repetitions) data (Carrasco et al., 2013; King and Chinchilli, 2001; Lin, 1989; Oliveira et al., 2020). In this case, accuracy refers to Pearson's correlation coefficient, which measures how far each measurement repetition deviates from the best-fit line of the entire sample. Precision refers to the so-called bias correction factor, which is a measurement of how far the line of best fit of all repetition data points diverges from a 45-degree angle through the origin in a cartesian coordinate system or line of perfect concordance (Lin, 1989). Refer to Lin (1989) and Oliveira et al. (2020) for the exact mathematical derivation of the precision term and its relation to the following equation. The sample version of LCCC is calculated as:

$$LCCC = \frac{2s_{xy}}{(\bar{x} - \bar{y})^2 + s_x^2 + s_y^2}$$

where s_{xy} represents the covariance of all first (s_x) and second (s_y) repeated measurements (multiplied with Pearson's correlation coefficient (r)), s_x^2 and s_y^2 their respective variances, and \bar{x} and \bar{y} their respective group means (Carrasco et al., 2013; Lin, 1989; McBride, 2005; Oliveira et al., 2020). Like for the TEM, the LCCC and its lower and upper 95%CI margins were calculated here for all measured FM distances taken together of both physical repetitions of FML and FMB separately using a MS Excel code posted on the internet at www.real-statistics.com (<https://www.real-statistics.com/reliability/interrater-reliability/lins-concordance-correlation-coefficient/>, accessed: January 2022). The only adjustment necessary was the conversion of the population variance formula (= *var.p* (Excel function), squared variable deviation from the population mean divided by n) to its sample counterpart (= *var.s* (Excel function), squared variable deviation from the sample mean divided by $n-1$). The MS Excel codes to calculate the LCCC, and their 95%CI are summarized in Table S3.4.

The LCCC output can range from -1 to +1, which is similar to other correlation coefficients such as Pearson's r . Negative values close to -1 indicate perfect disagreement

between the two repetitions; values near 0 indicate no concordance (independence situation where all readings are random and there is no correlation); and values approaching +1 reveal perfect agreement (Carrasco et al., 2013; Oliveira et al., 2020). According to McBride (2005), the LCCC near 1 can be more specifically interpreted as follows: < 90 = poor concordance; 0.90 to 0.95 = moderate concordance; 0.95 to 0.99 = substantial concordance; > 0.99 = almost perfect concordance.

3.6.2 3D Landmark Measurement Error and Placement Precision

Like any measurement, the positioning of fixed landmarks and semilandmarks is associated with inter- and intraobserver measurement error (von Cramon-Taubadel et al., 2007). Measurement error in landmark data and GM analysis can lead to substantial problems with the interpretation of the generated results, especially if the morphological variation is relatively small, like in phenotypic shape differences (Arnqvist and Mårtensson, 1998). Whereas estimations of error rates for traditional measurement are simple and straightforward (see methods listed above), this is not the case for landmark data. There are different sources of error in landmark acquisition that depend not only on applied digitization and collection methods but also on the types of landmarks that are being collected. For instance, intra- and interobserver error rates of Bookstein Type I landmarks have been shown to be lower than those of the more ambiguous Type II and III landmarks (von Cramon-Taubadel et al., 2007).

3.6.2.1 Error Shape-PCA

To estimate and evaluate the degree of intraobserver landmark placement error, landmark coordinate data of three randomly selected individuals per population (twelve individuals in total) were repetitively collected five times over a period of several weeks. To visualize the landmark repetition error, all the landmark configurations of each repetition together with the entire non-repeated specimens of all populations were subjected to a principal component analysis (PCA; see below) after the landmarks had been transformed to shape coordinates by GPA. The resulting principal component (PC) scores were then visualized in a bivariate error-shaped PCA score plot (PC 1 versus PC 2). The repetition variation of the sets of corresponding repetitions is visually highlighted using convex hulls. Ideally, the repeated landmark configurations should cluster closely together relative to other individuals in the dataset, i.e., the within-repetition variation should not exceed and interfere with the biological variation between different specimens and vice versa (O'Higgins and Jones, 1998). No other individuals should therefore fall within the constructed convex hull enclosure between the repeated landmark configurations. This approach relies on the GPA-transformed landmark configuration as a whole and therefore cannot provide information on the exact precision of individual landmarks. This is problematic, as the effect of single error-prone

landmarks can be diminished by more precisely placed landmarks (von Cramon-Taubadel et al., 2007). This method should therefore rather be considered a visual assessment of the self-referred affinity of each of the specimen's repetitions and the "overall effect of landmark error" (Lockwood et al., 2002). How the error shape-PCAs were coded in R is described below. Twelve error PCAs were computed, one for each set of individual repetitions of the single repeated specimen in relation to its whole population sample, including the repetition centroid-nearest configuration of the two other repeated individuals of that population. From the repetition landmark configurations of each repeated individual, only these ones were chosen to be included in the further analyses that lie closest to the centroid of the repetition cluster in their respective error shape-PCA plot.

3.6.2.2 Centroid Radius Approach

To quantify the precision in terms of the relative repeatability of individual landmarks (von Cramon-Taubadel et al., 2007), the centroid radius approach introduced by Singleton (2002) was used. The centroid radius in this case refers to the Euclidian distances between each of the repeated landmarks and the centroid or mean of the entire configuration. Mean deviations and percentage error of the centroid radius distances of each set of repeated, individual landmarks are computed (Singleton, 2002; von Cramon-Taubadel et al., 2007). A relative SD below 5% is considered acceptable, and divergence can be explained by a minor random error in locating the respective landmarks (Singleton, 2002; personal communication with Dr. Alexandros Karakostis, January 2022). Results above this threshold, however, are considered more problematic. Affected landmarks should be re-evaluated and excluded as a whole if the error cannot be substantially reduced. As stressed out by von Cramon-Taubadel et al. (2007), the centroid radius method has difficulties accurately detecting large errors under specific circumstances. As the error is calculated as the distances from each landmark to the overall configuration centroid, the obtained relative error highly depends on the absolute Euclidean distances. Landmarks close to the centroid consequently exhibit higher relative error rates, whereas landmarks further away have smaller errors. Especially small configurations where the radii have smaller magnitudes and those landmark configurations that deviate from circular or spherical shapes due to larger radii variation are most likely affected by that problem. Another problem lies in the fact that only those erroneous landmarks are fully detected whose error is collinear with the original centroid vector. Errors in landmark positioning in any other directions are therefore underestimated, especially when the target area is spherical with the same Euclidian surface-to-centroid distances for all radii (von Cramon-Taubadel et al., 2007). It is therefore advisable to not only rely on this approach when evaluating landmark precision. Using an error-shape PCA in addition, as described before, can help to undermine the results obtained from the centroid radius method. The centroid radius approach was performed in a pre-coded, semi-automatic MS Excel spreadsheet, which was thankfully provided by one of

the supervisors (AK). The centroid radius approach was conducted two times for each repeated specimen, first for the non-Procrustes transformed and non-slid coordinates and then for the slid landmarks after GPA. Only the five corresponding configurations of each of the twelve repeated individuals were subjected to GPA and sliding in R.

3.7 Statistical Analyses of the 2D Measurements

All statistics mentioned in the following were calculated using the programming language and environment *R* (Team, 2020) and package extensions for specific steps if needed. Graphs have been plotted using *ggplot2* (Wickham, 2016) (version 3.3.6) and extension packages including *ggforce* (Pederson, 2021) (version 0.3.3), *ggthemes* (Arnold, 2021) (version 4.2.4), *ggpubr* (Kassambara, 2020) (version 0.4.0), *gridExtra* (Auguie, 2017) (version 2.3), *ggstatsplot* (Patil, 2021) (version 0.9.1), *cowplot* (Wilke, 2020) (version 1.1.1), as well as packages to wrangle, sort, and subset data frames such as *dplyr* (Wickham et al., 2020) (version 1.0.2), *plyr* (Wickham, 2011) (version 1.8.6) and *tidyverse* (Wickham et al., 2019) (version 1.3.0).

3.7.1 Parametric Test Assumptions and Hypotheses Testing

One of the main principles of empirical research is the testing of hypotheses derived from research questions, both of which must be formulated before the actual analysis begins (Banerjee et al., 2009). The research questions and underlying hypotheses in this study are noted in the last section of the introduction. Their aim is to explore testable differences in the morphology and osteometry of the FM between sexes within a population ($H_{0.1}$) and between entire populations ($H_{0.2}$) (Fig. 2). These null hypotheses (H_0), which represent the formal basis for the statistical testing of significance, are formulated in such a way that no differences between groups are expected, i.e., there is no association between the outcome variables and their predictor in the population. The counterpart of the null hypothesis is the so-called alternative hypothesis (H_1), which refers to a situation where an association or difference is present. It is not possible to test the alternative hypothesis directly, and it must therefore be accepted upon exclusion based on the rejection of the null hypothesis. As no direction of the association is specifically assumed in advance, i.e., one direction is not considered to be biologically more meaningful than the opposite one, the formulated hypotheses are two-tailed. As it is virtually impossible to measure entire populations, samples are analyzed. By chance, however, this might lead to a situation where the analyzed sample might not be representative of the population, leading to wrong inferences due to random error. One kind of error is the false rejection of the null hypothesis and the acceptance of its alternative, although H_0 is true in the population. This scenario is called a Type I error (α) or false-positive. A false-negative

Type II error (β) would occur if the null hypothesis was not rejected, which is false in the population. Both errors can generally be reduced by increasing the overall sample size, as it becomes more likely that the sample is more representative of the actual population. Another reason for the occurrence of Type I and II errors is the presence of biases related to measurement errors, for instance. The proportion of tests that will reject the null hypothesis when sampling multiple times from the same population, although there is no true effect in the population, is expressed in the Type I error rate (α). The Type II error rate (β) describes the proportion of the tests that failed to reject the null hypothesis when, again, sampling multiple times forms the same population when there is a true effect present. In advance, a maximum chance of making either of these two error types must be defined. The probability of falsely positively rejecting H_0 when it is true is called the level of significance, which is often arbitrarily set by convention (Fisher, 1954) as $\alpha = 0.05$, meaning that there is a 5% maximum chance of incorrectly favoring the alternative over the null hypothesis. The probability of committing a Type II error is usually set to $\beta = 0.2$, or a 20% chance of missing an association. This translates to a statistical power of 0.8 or 80%, which is calculated as $1 - \beta$ and represents the proportion of tests that correctly reject the null hypothesis when there is a true effect within the population when sampling many times from the same population.

P-values and effect sizes are important outputs of statistical tests. The p-value represents the probability of the observed differences in the data of the sample if H_0 is true in the real or whole population. The p-value, therefore, does not directly represent the probability that H_0 is true. Conversely, 1 minus the p-value does not equal the probability of H_1 , but the likelihood of not obtaining these data and results under H_0 . A value of p smaller than α , the predefined level of significance ($p < 0.05$, for instance), is considered to be significant. Larger p-values above $\alpha = 0.05$ are consequentially considered to be insignificant or nonsignificant. This, however, does not imply that there is no association present in the population but does indicate that the association or difference that has been observed in the studied sample is relatively low compared to what could have occurred due to chance alone. Therefore, the p-value does not guarantee the right conclusion, i.e., whether H_0 should be rejected and H_1 should be accepted or not. It can only be used as a supportive probability metric to draw a conclusion. Because the p-value only helps to judge whether an association or difference might be statistically significant or not, it does not tell anything about the magnitude of the observed difference or association. Here, the concept of effect sizes is used as a quantitative measure of this magnitude. The larger the effect size, the larger the differences between the two groups. There are different methods to calculate the effect size, such as Cohen's d, standardized mean differences, and Pearson r correlation, among others. The effect size is unknown on the first hand and often difficult to infer. It can, however, be inferred or derived from previous studies of the same or similar subjects, if reported. Otherwise, it must be reasoned based on information gained from the reference literature compendium, or it must be evaluated based on the newly obtained results of the present study (Banerjee et al., 2009; Delacre et al., 2019).

Given that effect sizes are not systematically reported in FM research, the latter approach must apply here. Reported mean values of sex-known subgroups and sex-pooled population samples are used as references to approximate a reasonable effect size for differences between sexes and between populations. Following the just-mentioned conventions, the level of significance for statistical hypotheses testing in this study was also set to $\alpha = 0.05$, and the probability for Type II errors was likewise set to $\beta = 0.2$.

Many of the statistical hypotheses testing and modeling methods that are intended to be used in this study are parametric and require specific assumptions to be met, such as normality and homogeneity of variances (homoscedasticity) of the raw data residuals, balanced sample sizes, independent samples, and the absence of outliers (Delacre et al., 2019; Yap and Sim, 2011). Residuals in this study have been calculated for all three 2D variables as the positive or negative differences of each measurement from the respective subgroup mean (i.e., females mean, males mean, and sex-pooled population mean of each population group). Residual raw data values are not separately reported in this study. However, as it cannot *a priori* be judged whether the present data fulfills the requirements for statistical hypothesis testing, non-parametric equivalent tests are mentioned and briefly described as well. The consequences of normality and homoscedasticity violations with regards to Type I and Type II errors in hypotheses testing are summarized in Delacre et al. (2019). For instance, when sample distributions are slightly skewed or tailed, the rate of Type I error is considerably closer to the assumed expectations, even with smaller sample sizes. Likewise, violations of normality do not heavily affect the statistical power of the test results with regards to Type II error rates. In this regard, the asymmetry of the distribution displays a somewhat higher impact on the power compared to higher skewness. Sample size is another important factor that influences the statistical power in cases of non-normality, which increases when unequal sample sizes between groups are smaller but decreases when sample sizes become larger. Parametric test statistics such as those used in the F-test of the standard ANOVA are sensitive to unequal variances with regards to committing Type I errors, i.e., the more unequal variance and SD between subsamples, the higher the negative impact on the statistical power and the likelihood of a Type I error. This impact is smaller when only two groups are compared with each other but is larger when more groups are analyzed, even with similar sample sizes. In cases of unequal sample sizes, the effect of sample size and variance pairing is considerably stronger. Here, the Type I error rate decreases if the larger samples also have a larger variance (positive pairing) but increases when the larger samples have a smaller variance (negative pairing). Regarding the Type II error rate, the impact of heteroscedastic variances is small in cases of equal sample sizes but high in cases of a positive pairing of sample size and variance. On the other hand, the Type II error rate decreases and the power increases when there is a negative pairing present. It has also been shown that there is no interaction between cumulative violations of both normality and homoscedasticity with regards to Type I and II error

rates and that, independent of the distribution shape, the effect of heteroscedasticity is mostly constant (Delacre et al., 2019).

To gain a first, visual idea of whether the requirements for parametric statistics are fulfilled or not, histograms as well as Q-Q (Quantile-Quantile) plots of the variable residuals of FML and FMB from the respective groups are generated (Langley et al., 2018; Yap and Sim, 2011). In addition, skewness and kurtosis are also calculated for each subsample. Both metrics are used to quantify important shape properties of the data distribution and estimate their normality (Delacre et al., 2019; Hair et al., 2017; Joanes and Gill, 1998; Mayers, 2013; Westfall, 2014). Skewness quantifies the degree of sample distortion and indicates whether a distribution is asymmetric or symmetric. Skewness values above +1 (positive or right-sided skew) and below -1 (negative or left-sided skew) indicate a skewed or asymmetrical and therefore non-normal distribution (Hair et al., 2017). A skewness of zero represents a perfectly normal, distributed sample. As mentioned before, skewness values between -0.4 and +0.4 have been noted as reflecting considerably small departures from the normal distribution (Delacre et al., 2019). Kurtosis, on the other hand, measures the tailedness, often also mistakenly referred to as flatness or peakedness, of the distribution (Westfall, 2014). The kurtosis, or percentile coefficient of kurtosis, of the standard normal distribution is 3. By subtracting 3 from the kurtosis calculation, the classical kurtosis metric is usually transformed to the so-called excess or simply kurtosis (also called Fisher's coefficient of kurtosis) (Fávero and Belfiore, 2019), where the normal distribution has a kurtosis value of 0, which is also referred to as the mesokurtic distribution according to the classical categorization by Pearson (1905). When the kurtosis is positive or leptokurtic with values above +1, the sample distribution is characterized by longer, fatter tails, indicating the presence of outliers. A platykurtic distribution with negative kurtosis values below -1 indicates short, thin tails where the sample lacks outliers. Others, however, have also reported higher maximum kurtosis values to indicate normality, such as two times the standard error (SE) for the z-transformed or standardized variables (i.e., $1.96 \cdot SE$) (Coolican, 2009; Mayers, 2013). As skewness and kurtosis values appear to be the same for the residual raw data and the z-standardized equivalents, the residuals were not z-transformed in this study. Kurtosis values of the response variables approximately outside these margins and not above or below these limits can be consequently considered to be non-normal (Delacre et al., 2019; Hair et al., 2017).

Plotting the residual data in Q-Q plots and histograms can help to decide which statistical methods are appropriate to use for the subsequent analyses. However, it has been noted that graphical exploration of the requirements alone is insufficient, as they are too subjective and do not provide any formal conclusive evidence for proper decision-making. To compensate for these two problems, it has been argued to use appropriate statistical tests to formally confirm the conclusions drawn from graphical representations (Yap and Sim, 2011). However, applying statistical tests to sub-datasets with extremely low subsample sizes (e.g.,

Japanese females and males with only four individuals per group) will potentially result in unreliable results with lower statistical power (Delacre et al., 2019), although it might be theoretically possible to calculate tests for even smaller sample sizes like the Shapiro-Wilk test for normality, which requires at least three cases (Yap and Sim, 2011). For these reasons, statistical testing to check the fulfillment of parametric assumptions will only serve as an additional or secondary approach in the present study. Therefore, more emphasis is placed on the graphical exploration of the data and their distribution characteristics.

Q-Q probability plots (Wilk and Gnanadesikan, 1968) represent an effective, visual approach to assessing whether a set of the raw data distributions of continuous measurement variables assumingly emerges from a theoretical distribution, e.g., the standardized normal distribution. To construct such plots, the theoretical quantiles, in the present case the standard normal variates of the standard normal distribution with a mean of zero and SD of one shown on the X-axis, are plotted against the ordered, ascending measurement values or sample quantiles whose distribution is checked for normality on the Y-axis. In addition, a 45-degree reference line, which represents the line of best fit or the theoretical distribution ($x = y$), also named the line of identity, is added to the plot. The greater the visual and vertical deviations of the data points in the Y direction, the more the datasets diverge from the normal distribution. In cases where the empirical distribution is consistent with the theoretical (e.g., normal) distribution, the points of each measurement shown in this kind of graph will fall closely on the best fitting line, hence the data distribution approaches normality (Loy et al., 2015; Varshney, 2020). The strength of the Q-Q plot lies in its capability to also visually indicate trends of skewness and kurtosis embedded in the sample data distribution. For instance, if only the bottom end of the data distribution deviates from the straight line but not the top end, the dataset is clearly negatively or left-skewed, and vice versa. With regards to the kurtosis of a sample, distributions with a wide tail have both ends of the Q-Q plot deviate from the straight line, whereas its center remains in agreement and therefore follows this line. Thin-tailed, narrower distributions that are approaching the perfect fit of the normal distribution will only deviate at a very low level from this line (Varshney, 2020). To support the visual evaluation of the Q-Q plot and the degree of measurement divergence from the line of the theoretical distribution, it is recommended to add the 95% pointwise confidence interval region to the graph (Davison and Hinkley, 1997). To construct Q-Q plots for the present data plotted against the normal distribution quantiles, the *ggqqplot()* function of the *ggplot2* extension package *ggpubr* (Kassambara, 2020) (version 0.4.0) has been used. For the intrapopulation analysis, Q-Q plots have been plotted based on both sexes taken together but not including the sex-unknown individuals. Q-Q plots were also plotted based on all sex-identified and unidentified specimens for the interpopulation analysis.

The Shapiro-Wilk test of normality (SW-test) (Royston, 1982; Shapiro and Wilk, 1965) is the most widely used statistical analysis to test for normal distribution, i.e., whether the data

distribution is Gaussian or bell-shaped. It is a regression-based goodness-of-fit test that shows high levels of power, even in cases of low sample sizes, where the data is asymmetrically distributed (i.e., if the distribution is skewed to either side) or when the distribution is symmetrical with high or low sample kurtosis (either long- or short-tailed data distributions) (Yap and Sim, 2011). Proper alternative solutions for the best choice of tests for normality when neither of these situations would apply for the present data are listed in Yap and Sim (2011). When using the SW-test, data can be considered to follow a normal distribution when the obtained p-values do not fall below $\alpha = 0.05$. This test was calculated using the base R function *shapiro.test()*. As normality of the residuals is one of the main assumptions of ANOVA and regression analysis (Delacre et al., 2019), the normality of the variable's residuals from the mean per group is tested instead of the raw data points. SW-tests were performed separately for each of the three 2D FM variables of each sex-known subgroup per population for the intrapopulation analysis, not considering the sex-unknown individuals. For the interpopulation analysis samples, SW-tests were run on the residuals of all three individual variables for the entire, sex-pooled samples of the four studied populations, including the sex-indeterminable individuals.

Next to normality of the data distributions, equality of the sample variances is important for many statistical procedures where groups are compared, like in ANOVA (Delacre et al., 2019). A widely applied, very robust test statistic to evaluate the equality or homogeneity of variances of the measured independent, continuous variables between each pair of compared subgroups is the Levene's test (Gastwirth et al., 2010; Levene, 1960). Sample pairs are considered to have equal, homoscedastic variances when the calculated p-value is greater than $\alpha = 0.05$; the null hypothesis would not be rejected in this case (Team, 2022). In cases where the variances are not equal, where the alternative hypothesis of Levene's test would be accepted, it is possible to use the so-called Welch's ANOVA (also called the W-test) as an alternative to the classical ANOVA test to compare group means for more than two groups (Delacre et al., 2019). In R, the package *car* (John and Weisberg, 2019) (version 3.0.10) is needed to use the *leveneTest()* function in order to apply the test statistic. The Levene tests were calculated based on all sex-known individuals per variable as well as the entire sex-pooled sample for each variable separately.

3.7.2 Statistical 2D Osteometric Data Analyses and 2D Meta-Analysis

All descriptive statistics were calculated using the R package *psych* (Revelle, 2021) (version 2.1.9) and its function *describe()*. To statistically describe the 2D morphometric characteristics of the measured and calculated FM variables, FML, FMB, and FMI, the sample mean, sample median, sample standard deviation (SD), minimum (min) and maximum (max) values, and range for each population and their respective subgroups are calculated and

reported. To further estimate the properties of the entire population, the standard error of the mean (SE) and the 95% confidence interval (95%CI) of the mean, as well as skewness and kurtosis values (see Section 3.7.1), are calculated.

XY-scatter plots with marginal boxplots are generated to visually compare the raw data distributions of the continuous, non-transformed FML versus FMB variables between sexes within each of the Berlin populations. The marginal boxplots are used as an additional visualization aid for the raw data distribution range for more intuitive interpretation of the scatter plots. Scatter plots were also produced for the pooled population samples to explore the raw data distribution among the populations. FMI information was included in all plots to gain information on the categorical shape distributions within and between subgroups.

To statistically test for significant mean differences between sex groups within each population (intrapopulation analysis, $H_{0.1}$) as well as between each population as a whole (interpopulation analysis, $H_{0.2}$), parametric testing was performed after the assumptions for parametric analysis had been confirmed (Section 3.7.1). In cases where homogeneity of variances for all or at least some subsamples is not given, Welch's variant of ANOVA can be used, which is not sensitive to the unfulfilled parametric test requirement of equal variances (Delacre et al., 2019). If neither homogeneity nor normality of the variable residuals would be fulfilled, a non-parametric test alternative such as the Kruskal-Wallis test that uses rank scores of the non-normally distributed variable can be applied (Kruskal and Wallis, 1952; McKight and Najab, 2009). Univariate one- and two-way or -factor analysis of variance (ANOVA) on each of the three 2D FM variables separately was used. ANOVA represents a multi-predictor model and is a groupwise parametric comparison test that tests for significance based on the F-statistics when more than two groups are included. In cases where the variance within groups is smaller than the variance between groups, a higher F-value will be obtained, which also increases the probability that the observed differences are not due to chance alone (Delacre et al., 2019). In R, the ANOVAs were calculated based on preformulate linear models of the respective sub-datasets using the *lm()* function, which were then subjected to the *Anova()* function of the car package (John and Weisberg, 2019) (version 3.0.10) to obtain ANOVA (Type II test) tables summarizing the test results, including the sums of squares, degrees of freedom (Df), F-values, and p-values.

For the intrapopulation analysis, the continuous FM variables (FML, FMB, and FMI) are treated as numeric, univariate response variables. Sex and population represent the independent categorical predictor variables (factor vectors) in the two-way ANOVA. The interaction term of both factorial predictor variables, population, and sex, was also considered in the two-way ANOVA to test whether the combination of both factors affects the dependent variables. Therefore, a two-way ANOVA tests three different null hypotheses at once, i.e., assuming that there are no significant group mean differences at any level of the first and second independent variables as well as that the effect of one of them does not depend on the

effect of the other, i.e., the interaction, and vice versa. With the two-way ANOVA, both study hypotheses $H_{0,1}$ and $H_{0,2}$ are equally addressed, as all possible pairs of groups included in this study are being compared. At the same time, expect between-population comparisons, including the sex-unknown individuals in sex-pooled, overall population samples. To test also for between-population differences, population assignment (sex-pooled sample) represents the only predictor variable in the one-way ANOVA to test whether the means of sex-pooled population samples significantly differ from each other ($H_{0,2}$). Here, only one null hypothesis is tested, i.e., there is no statistically significant difference among group means. For both ANOVA variants, the null hypothesis can be rejected when the p-value is smaller than the predefined significance level ($p < 0.05$). In this case, it can be assumed that the group means significantly differ from each other and that the independent variable or the combination of two has a significant effect on the dependent measurements.

ANOVA results alone do not reveal which levels diverge from each other in cases where significant mean differences ($p < 0.05$) were found by the test. A significant p-value in the ANOVA output only indicates that at least one group significantly differs from the others. To obtain detailed information on the pairwise differences, multiple pairwise comparisons between the group means in the form of post-hoc tests such as *Tukey-Kramers's Honestly-Significant-Difference* (Tukey-HSD) test can be performed. During this testing procedure, the significance level is adjusted by an increase to reduce the likelihood of risking a Type I error. The test calculates the least squares or smallest absolute differences between group means that reveal statistically significant results by correcting for multiple testing at the same time. In the results, differences in group means, their 95%CI and adjusted p-values for all possible pairwise comparisons are given (Abdi and Williams, 2010). The difference in mean levels of the groups, their 95%CIs and the adjusted p-values of the pairwise Tukey-HSD results will be reported accordingly. To compute Tukey's post hoc test in base R, the *TukeyHSD()* function was used.

In cases where the ANOVA and Tukey-HSD results reveal overall significant FM mean differences between groups and thus support the rejection of the null hypotheses, linear discriminant function analysis (LDA) can be used to assess the magnitude and accuracy rate of FM measurement disparity between compared groups, i.e., whether they are significantly different. In other words, LDA can be seen as a measure of biodistance or relationships among different groups, which can be, for example, sexes or populations. LDA can also be used to predict or classify unknown human remains with a certain probability and accuracy (Ousley, 2016). It is the first multivariate method that was invented by Fisher (1936) and was introduced to osteometry over the course of the 1950s and 1970s (Giles and Elliot, 1963; Henke, 1974). Since then, the method has been widely applied in anthropological and forensic studies, such as in the FORDISC software (Jantz and Ousley, 2017; Ousley and Jantz, 1996; Ousley and

Jantz, 2012; Ousley and Jantz, 2013), which is used to determine population affinity, sex, and/or stature using linear cranial or postcranial distance measurements (Ousley, 2016).

The aim of the LDA is to calculate a discriminant function (DF) or determination formula that represents the linear combination of the independent, numeric variables (e.g., FML, FMB, and/or FMI) that best separates between the dependent categorical variables (e.g., sex- or population-groups). In this sense, univariate LDA can be viewed as a reversed ANOVA or reversed MANOVA (multivariate ANOVA) when multiple numeric variables are used to predict the group membership of individuals (Brunner and Giannini, 2011). When LDA is used to distinguish between more than two categorical groups (e.g., between several populations), the analysis is often called *Canonical Variant Analysis* (CVA) (Ousley, 2016). However, it has also been noted that there are minor computational differences between CVA and multiple LDAs (personal communication with Dr. Alexandros Karakostis, January 2022). The number of DFs equals the number of categorical dependent groups minus one. Note that more DFs per group can be generated when different combinations of multiple numeric measurement variables used as independent predictors are considered. When more measurement variables are subjected to a multivariate LDA, iterative stepwise selection procedures can help to determine or at least approximate the variable combination with the highest accuracy rate. This is a vital step, as it is one of the goals of LDA to identify these variables that are most useful in classifying unknown individuals with the highest accuracy or that reveal the largest group differences, which is usually expressed as Wilks' lambda. When only one variable is subjected to the DF, this stepwise procedure does not apply as only one function can be calculated (Ousley, 2016).

The LDA method computes uni- or multivariate between-group distances based on group-specific means and a pooled within-group variance-covariance matrix, which represents the relationships between measurements within groups (Ousley, 2016). LDA is comparable to principal component analysis (PCA; see below) in the sense that both aim to reduce the high dimensionality of multiple measurements. However, other than PCA, which aims to maximize variances between individuals within groups, DFA maximizes the variation (differences) between groups to find the best possible separation. As LDA is a mean-based and therefore parametric method, several strict assumptions, such as multivariate normality, absence of outliers, and homogeneity of variances, must be made in order to obtain reliable results, which have already been addressed above with assumption evaluation for the ANOVA. Furthermore, a suitable ratio of measurements to the overall sample size must be considered to avoid overfitting, which can have negative effects on the classification accuracy and consistency of the method. The number of variables must not exceed the number of observed specimens and should therefore always be smaller. If the required assumptions are fulfilled, LDA has been noted to perform overall better and reveal higher accuracy rates than its alternatives, such as logistic regression or quadratic discriminant function analysis (Ousley, 2016). The classification

accuracy rate is of particular importance in forensic science as it represents a measure of validity and method error (Dirkmaat et al., 2008; Ousley, 2016). In other words, the accuracy rate of a LDA reflects the percentage of individuals that have been correctly classified into its group (Giles and Elliot, 1963). According to the Daubert Standards, the accuracy rate of a method should be high and range within the 90% to 100% spectrum to be considered reliable and applicable in medicolegal contexts (Casado, 2017a; Casado, 2017b; Cheng and Yoon, 2005; Christensen, 2006; Grivas and Komar, 2008). There are different approaches to accessing the accuracy of a LDA, as summarized in Ousley (2016). Ideally, when the sample size is large enough, the DF is calculated based on a sufficiently large sub-dataset. This cohort represents the reference or training sample, which often comprises around 75% of the entire sample. The remaining 25% of the sample is the validation sample, based on which the function is tested to calculate the accuracy rate. However, many human osteological samples and subsample sizes, such as in the present study, are small. Splitting and further decreasing the number of individuals in each group of these datasets appears to be counterintuitive, as it would reduce the applicability of the method. One often-applied solution to this problem is to use a resampling method known as leave-one-out cross-validation or jack-knifing. Here, the accuracy rate of the LDA of a given sample is repeatedly calculated by excluding only one individual each time. The obtained sub-accuracy rates are then summarized (Ousley, 2016). It must also be noted that DFs are population-specific and cannot be applied to other, distinct populations without great caution. Group-specific reference samples of different osteometric measurements are therefore needed (Kemkes-Grottenthaler, 2005).

The frequencies of FMI shape categories across sex or whole-population groups can theoretically be tested for significant differences using *Pearson's χ^2 Test of Independence* (Pearson, 1900). However, this test requires at least five observations per level of the response variable (i.e., the FMI shape category) and a sufficiently large sample size (circa 20 to 50 minimum observations) to be reliably applied (Rana and Singhal, 2015; Yates, 1934). As will be shown, this assumption cannot be fulfilled with the present subsamples sizes. It is thus not advisable to perform such frequency tests on the present data. Differences in absolute and relative frequencies are therefore only accessed visually using advanced contingency tables and graphical distributions of FMI shapes in relation to group assignments and the two 2D FM distance measurements, FML and FMB.

As it was only possible to collect summary statistical data from the published FM literature, reliable in-depth statistical meta-analysis using the compiled reference sample cannot be conducted. For this reason, the reference dataset was only used as an additional means to observe global trends in the average FM osteometry. Here, the mean, SD, and range information of all three FM variables are plotted against those obtained from the four new populations using suitable plot types, such as scatter or univariate range plots. No advanced statistical modeling or hypothesis testing was conducted for the reference summary data.

3.8 Statistical 3D Semilandmark Data Analyses

The statistical analysis of the 3D landmark configurations, used to estimate shape and form differences between sexes and populations, closely followed the analytical pipeline applied in the 2D analysis. After sliding and Procrustes superimposition (GPA) of the landmarks, the standardized coordinate data could be statistically analyzed (Gunz and Mitteroecker, 2013). However, the statistical analysis differs between traditional osteometry and GM. Whereas multivariate analysis of traditional measurements involves measurements of different units and variances, which must first be equalized and standardized, landmark variables in GM all have the same units. Therefore, the analysis of traditional osteometric measurements usually relies on correlation matrices, and most multivariate methods and tests can be applied without restrictions, given that the parametric assumptions are met. Moreover, GM data analysis is based on the covariation matrix of the measured variables, as the landmark coordinates all possess the same metric unit. Not all statistical procedures, such as multiple regression, canonical correlation, or variate analysis, preserve the well-defined Procrustes metric and relational shape and form information, which represents a strength of GM. In cases where variance-covariance matrices of data must be inverted, specific methods cannot be applied to GM landmark data at all or, when applied, produce unreliable results. This happens when there are more measured variables than studied specimens from which the measurements have been collected (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009). This imposes an inherent problem to GM studies, as many (semi)landmark configurations can consist of a high number of coordinate variables, which together exceed the number of specimens subjected to the analysis (i.e., overfitting; see Section 3.7.2) (Ousley, 2016), and that can be highly correlated, especially in the case of semilandmarks (Gunz and Mitteroecker, 2013; Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009). This problem is highlighted when considering that 3D landmarks consist of three coordinates per landmark (i.e., x, y, and z), which multiplies the number of variables by a factor of three. A high correlation of landmark variables results in a singular, irreversible covariance matrix. From there, any results related to shape or form changes and differences become increasingly difficult to interpret and visualize.

To tackle the problem of high data dimensionality, which is typical in GM, methods that are not affected by this ratio of fewer specimens in relation to more variables can be used. Examples of this are a *Partial Least Squares Analysis*, *Between-Group PCA's*, and *Permutation Tests* (Gunz and Mitteroecker, 2013). Otherwise, landmark data can be subjected to dimension reduction techniques such as PCA (Hotelling, 1933; Pearson, 1901). PCA reduces and decorrelates large sets of variables to a smaller number of dimensions that explain most of the variance observable within the data (Gunz and Mitteroecker, 2013; Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009). In respect to GM analysis, this method is especially valuable as landmark data is rarely considered independent (Zelditch et al., 2012). The obtained and transformed data, such as PC scores and Procrustes distances, can then be used in

subsequent statistical analyses without experiencing problems related to data overfitting. However, PCA is not just an effective method to decrease dimensionality by reducing the number of variables. As a standard method in GM analysis nowadays, PCA is also used to visually compare differences and similarities between groups and individual specimens. Additionally, shape and form comparisons of the landmark configurations along the principal components can be made, which are used to detect trends, gaps, clusters, outliers, etc. (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009).

In GM, PCA is used as a multivariate ordination eigenanalysis method of the covariance matrix of Procrustes coordinates. It calculates the orthogonally rotated axes of maximum variance for large datasets of several interdependent and partially redundant numeric shape variables. In other words, PCA reduces the dimensionality of large datasets while aiming to retain as much of the original variation as possible. This is done by transforming the data using the singular value or eigendecomposition of the covariance matrix to generate a new set of uncorrelated and ordered variables, which are called *principal components* (PCs). Each individual, previously described by multiple variable data points, is now represented by a single point. In doing so, the Procrustes distance metrics are preserved as valuable relational shape information across the sample of specimens (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009). Ordered, in this case, means that the first PC (PC1) accounts for the most variation in the dataset. While the second PC (PC2) accounts for the second most variation, and so on and so forth. PCs are calculated as the linear combinations or functions of an eigenvector of the covariance matrix or sum of squares and cross products matrix from the GPA-transformed variables. The eigenvalues of each component represent its variance. During the projection of the original data onto the line of best fit for each PC, each measurement point can be expressed with its newly obtained coordinate value along this PC line, also referred to as a PC score (Jolliffe, 2002; Savriama, 2018; Tabachnick et al., 2007). Considering GM, PC scores are shape/form projections on the low-dimensional space or axes spanned by the nonzero eigenvectors. PC scores can be visualized using PC score plots in two (e.g., PC1 vs. PC2) or three dimensions (e.g., PC1 vs. PC2 vs. PC3) (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009; Singleton, 2002).

PCA on the Procrustes coordinates as multivariate variables was computed using the *gm.pcomp()* function in geomorph. Overall, two types of PCAs were performed: 1) using Procrustes variables for the shape-only aspects of FM variation (shape-PCA) and 2) using Procrustes landmark data in combination with log-transformed CS (lnCS) to estimate allometric shape changes of the FM with respect to changes in size (form-PCA) (Bookstein, 1998). For both approaches, the entire sex-known-only subsamples were used to study intra-population differences. The sex-pooled subsamples per population were used to estimate differences between all four populations. As the Procrustes landmark coordinate data has consistent units, PCA could be performed on the covariance instead of the correlation matrix by using the default FALSE setting of the *gm.pcomp* function argument scale. Using the correlation matrix

(i.e., *scale = TRUE*), standardize each variable to unit variance with a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. Therefore, when relying on the covariance matrix, the Procrustes variables are not standardized (Gunz and Mitteroecker, 2013).

From the PCA results, *scree-plots* can be generated that summarize the eigenvalues or how much variation is explained by each PC. For each of the different computed PCAs, *scree-plots* were generated using the *screeplot()* function in *geomorph*. With reference to the loss of seven degrees of freedom after the GPA of 3D landmark data, the last seven PCs are always excluded by default (Reyes-Centeno et al., 2016). As exactly 98 and 83 PCs are generated for the present sample sizes of 98 and 83 individuals, this selection approach, however, is somewhat negligible, as it can generally be expected that the last PCs account for an extremely small amount of variation that is close to zero. Generally, eigenvalues with a variance larger than 1%, i.e., those that explain high proportions of the sample variation that is not random, are considered statistically meaningful. Accordingly, components that account for less than 1% of the explained variation are not extracted from the PCA results. These explain less of the variance than the original shape variables because the variance that each projected variable contributes to the PC extraction is equal to 1 (Reyes-Centeno et al., 2016; Tabachnick et al., 2007). However, this approach could be interpreted as counterintuitive as it implies the selection of a higher number of single, redundant PCs that explain just above 1% of the variance. There are different statistical modeling methods available to decide which PCs should be selected and extracted as ‘meaningful’ components. The PC scores can be used as low-dimensional, definite, uncorrelated variables in subsequent analyses such as DFA or multivariate allometric regression (see below). In this study, the broken stick approach (Frontier, 1976; MacArthur, 1957) was chosen as it represents a robust and quantitatively objective, though slightly conservative, estimation method. Following BSM, PCs that explain more of the captured variance than would be expected when randomly dividing the variance into *p* parts are considered meaningful (Wicklin, 2017). Observed PCs are retained whenever their explained percentage variation of the eigenvalues exceeds the portions according to the broken stick criterion. The broken stick model was computed using a non-functionally adjusted base R code, which is provided online on Github (https://github.com/mohanwugupta/Machine-Learning-Neuroimaging-Tutorial/blob/master/Broken_Stick.R, access: January 15, 2022).

PC score scatter plots are used to show the raw data PC score distribution of the sample. All variables of each individual are summarized in a single data point. Additional information about factorial variables such as sex- or population-group affinity can be added to score plots to help with the further interpretation of the data distribution. To evaluate the shape changes associated with each of the meaningful PCs or their ‘meaning’, wireframe shape deformations and vectors along each component axis have been generated and then plotted alongside the PC score. Visualizing these changes can aid in interpreting the meaning of a PC. As a reference for this procedure, the overall mean shape configuration, or consensus

shape, was used. This has been obtained from the Procrustes-aligned shape coordinates, which were subjected to the *mshape()* function in geomorph. Shape deformations for each PC were generated using the geomorph function *plotRefToTarget()*, in which vectors have been defined as the applied visualization method. The function *define.links()* was used to define the outline of the wireframe models in which each of the 40 landmarks was connected to their nearest neighbor following the procedure described in the initially defined landmark configuration.

After the visual assessment of shape differences across the subsamples using PCA, Procrustes ANOVA, also called Goodall's F-test for pairwise group comparisons, was used to statistically test for significant shape differences between groups (Goodall, 1991). This test takes the Procrustes distances among specimens derived from Procrustes-aligned shape variables as dependent numeric response variables and quantifies the relative amount of shape variation to one or more independent, discrete, or continuous factor variables in a linear model. Via resampling permutations, distributions are generated that are used to estimate the probability of this variation (i.e., the 'significance') for a null model. The tests reveal Z-scores as alternatives to the F-value, p-value, as well as the sum of squares (SS; of all Procrustes differences from the mean, including SS of the residual error) and mean squares (MS; SS divided by the degrees of freedom, i.e., number of groups minus 1) for each of the included groups (Baken et al., 2021; Karakostis, 2017). A two-way shape ANOVA was performed using sex and population assignments as two factors for the sex-separated samples, while excluding the sex-unknown individuals. A one-way shape ANOVA on the sex-pooled subsample per population was used to test for shape differences between populations. In both procedures, Procrustes distances were used as response variables. To see which of the compared groups in the two-way shape ANOVA significantly differed, a pairwise comparison post-hoc procedure for all possible group combinations was necessary. The Procrustes shape ANOVA was performed using the linear model-based geomorph function *procD.lm()* with 1.000 permutations (i.e., *iter = 999*).

In the case of significant shape differences between subgroups, the obtained scores of the most informative PCs would have been extracted and subjected to two DFAs (see Section 3.7.2). The first DFA would have been used to evaluate the magnitude of differences between sexes and the classification accuracy of unknown individuals using PC score variables. The second DFA would have been conducted to evaluate the difference between the populations and to estimate the classification accuracy rates of unknown individuals in these population groups. In both cases, the PC scores derived from the GPA-transformed landmark coordinate data would represent the independent, numeric predictor variables. Dependent factorial variables in these analyses would be either the female or male sex subgroups or the four populations.

Multivariate Allometric Regression was used to test for the linear relationship between shape and size (Mitteroecker and Gunz, 2009). This was implemented to account for size information, or the GM analysis of form or allometric effect, in the study of morphological FM differences between the sample subgroups. In other words, the influence of size on shape is estimated in a regression analysis where Procrustes shape variables are treated as the dependent, numeric variables and the natural logarithm of the centroid size (lnCS) per individual as the independent, numeric factor (Mitteroecker et al., 2004; Mitteroecker et al., 2013). As previously mentioned, CS represents the favored, explicit size metric in GM as it is approximately uncorrelated with all remaining shape variables after GPA for small isotropic variation at each landmark (Bookstein, 1991; Bookstein, 1996c; Dryden and Mardia, 1998; Mitteroecker et al., 2013; Savriama, 2018; Singleton, 2002). By augmenting Procrustes shape coordinates with log-transformed CS, it is guaranteed that the form space distribution for the underlying isotropic landmark variation is also isotropic. Furthermore, shape and size loadings and coefficients obtained from methods like PCA, or multivariate regression can be directly and easily compared and interpreted. The distance metric in form space that describes form differences between varying form configurations is the Euclidian distance. As landmark data does not have a natural zero point because it lies on an interval and not on a ratio scale, Procrustes shape coordinates cannot be subjected to a log-transformation. Therefore, allometry is often expressed as the linear function of Procrustes shape coordinate data, which is estimated by its multivariate regression on lnCS (Mitteroecker et al., 2013). There are different approaches to visualizing allometry, i.e., allometric trends, differences, and deformation vectors. The first option, as discussed above, is with the form-PCA of Procrustes shape coordinates and lnCS. Next, the *Two-Block Partial Least Squares (PLS) Analysis* of the entire dataset was used (*two.b.pls()*) to estimate the association (correlation) or the covariation axis between FM size and shape based on the eigenvalue decomposition of its cross-products (Rohlf and Corti, 2000). This major covariation axis is often also referred to as a common allometric component (CAC) (Mitteroecker et al., 2004). In PLS, the observed values are compared against the distribution of values obtained by random permutations of individuals in one block relative to those in the other partition. In the results of a PLS, the Pearson correlation coefficient (r-PLS), multivariate effect size, and p-value are reported. The r-PLS represents the correlation coefficient between the projected eigenvalue scores of both blocks. The p-value obtained from the resampling procedure becomes significant when the correlation is large relative to the distribution. PLS differences between groups can only be visualized using group-specific color codes in the PLS plot, as this method and form-PCA are not associated with a model of allometric shape change, especially not between different subgroups (Adams et al., 2021; Collyer, 2021). To better compare differences in FM group allometries, one full explicit linear model had to be defined using geomorph's *procD.lm()* function. This model included 1) a *Simple Allometric Model* comprising the Procrustes FM shape coordinates (dependent response variables) as a function of FM lnCS (independent predictor), 2) a *Common Allometry*

Model separating between groups (e.g., sexes among populations (intra-inter-population analysis) or just sex-pooled population groups (interpopulation analysis)) and 3) a *Unique Allometries Model* including the interaction term of the same subgroups used in the previously defined common model. To test which of these methods is most appropriate to describe allometric changes, the *RRPP* (residual randomization by permutation procedures) package variant of the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) embedded in the *anova()* function within geomorph can be used, which reports DF, SS, MS, R^2 , F, Z, and p-values. Significance in this case is evaluated using Goodall's (1991) F-statistic. In the case of significant results ($p < 0.05$), the *pairwise()* function would have been used as post-hoc test for pairwise subgroup differences among least-squares means or regression. To account for multiple tests in this pairwise procedure, α was reduced to 0.01 (Marcy et al., 2020). The analytical pipeline for the allometric regression analysis followed the codes provided by Collyer (2021).

4. Results

4.1 Demographic Profile

4.1.1 Demographic Profile of the Berlin Datasets

Results of the morphognostic sexing and final sex estimations are reported in the supplementary materials (Tabs. S2.8 to S2.11 and S2.12 to S2.15, respectively). Most skulls showed minor to no post-mortem damage, providing a reliable basis for morphognostic examinations for sex estimation. Only the German sample displayed a larger number of skulls with advanced stages of taphonomic alterations. In most cases, this could be related to the burial contexts, as many of the skulls come from archaeological sites of medieval to early modern cemeteries. There were no cases in which the skull was in a state of degradation so severe that sexing was impossible or not reliable. Only 24 (24.49%) of 98 mandibles were available for examination (Eritrea = 5, Japan = 5, Germany = 13, Greece = 1).

According to the results of the morphognostic sex estimation of the Berlin specimens, 37 cranial specimens, or 37.76%, are female and 46 specimens, or 46.94%, are male (ntotal = 98). The sex of 15 individuals, or 15.31% of the entire dataset, could not be determined. Seven (33.33%) of the Eritrean individuals are female, twelve (57.14%) are males, and the biological sex of the remaining two specimens (9.52%) could not be reliably identified (nEritrea = 21). In the Japanese sample (nJapanese = 11), females and males are equally represented by four individuals per sex (36.36% for each group), while three Japanese individuals (27.27%) are of unknown sex. In the largest group, the Germans (nGermany = 49), 19 individuals (38.78%) are female, 23 (46.94%) are male, and seven (14.29%) are undetermined. Lastly, in the Greek sample, females and males are equally represented (nGreece = 17), with seven individuals (41.18%) for each group. Three cranial specimens (17.65%) could not be sexed.

Table S2.16, Figure S2.18, and Figure 8 provide overviews of the absolute and relative frequencies of all sexes in each population. Despite low numbers of individuals per sex in most populations, the frequencies between both sexes in almost all population groups appear balanced overall (Fig. 8). The largest offset of five individuals can be found in the Eritrean sample, with almost double the number of males (57.14%) compared to females (33.33%). This is followed by the German dataset, with a difference of four individuals between sexes. In the Japanese and Greek samples, there are no differences in the counts of females and males. Taken together, a total of 83 individuals (100%), with 37 females (44.58%) and 46 males (55.42%), are available for the intrapopulation comparison. The relative frequencies of sexes between the populations are approaching balance overall, although the male subgroups tend to be slightly overrepresented in the Eritrean and German samples (45.41% on average) relative to the female groups (37.41% on average). Larger deviations from the balanced sample sizes, such as in the case of the Eritrean male subgroup, which has the highest relative frequency of 57.14%, could be explained by the effect of small sample sizes.

Tab. S2.16: Absolute and relative frequencies of sex identified and unidentified individuals per population from the newly collected samples from the anthropological Berlin collections.

Population	Females	Males	Unidentifiable (ind)	Total (Population)
Eritrea	7 (33.33%)	12 (57.14%)	2 (9.52%)	21 (21.43%)
Japan	4 (36.36%)	4 (36.36%)	3 (27.27%)	11 (11.22%)
Germany	19 (38.78%)	23 (46.94%)	7 (14.29%)	49 (50.00%)
Greece	7 (41.18%)	7 (41.18%)	3 (17.68%)	17 (17.35%)
Total (Sex)	37 (37.76%)	46 (46.94%)	15 (15.31%)	98 (100%)

ind = indifferent. Values in () represent relative frequencies referring to the total count of each population. Bold values in () in the last column and last row with the total counts of each population or sex group refer to the overall total count of the entire dataset (n = 98).

Of the total 98 specimens available for the interpopulation analyses, the sex of 15 individuals (15.31%) from all four populations could not be determined. Only in the Japanese group, consisting of almost one-third of the subsample, is the frequency of sex-unknown specimens slightly higher. However, again, this could be attributed to a small sample size and chance. Whether this Japanese sample tends to include fewer sexually dimorphic individuals cannot be reliably judged based on the small number of individuals. When sex-known and sex-unknown subgroups are pooled per population to form the dataset for the interpopulation

analyses, balance between those groups is not given. Germany accounts for exactly half of the sample (50.00%), whereas Japan makes up approximately one-tenth (11.22%). Only the total counts of the sex-pooled Eritrean (21.43%) and Greek samples (17.35%) tend to be close to balanced.

Figure 8: Absolute number of individuals per population (black values) with indication of the sex-known and sex-unknown specimens (white values) of the newly collected data from the Berlin samples.

4.1.2 Demographic Profile of the Reference Datasets

Absolute and relative frequencies for the sex distribution of the reference dataset of 2D FM measurements are reported in Table S2.17. In summary, reference data from all inhabited continents could be gathered, except for Australia. Regions with good sample coverage are north-eastern Africa, western and central Asia, central and western Europe, as well as western South America (Fig. 3). Geographical regions for which no FM studies could be found are Central America, including the Caribbean region, most parts of South-Eastern Asia, the Oceanian and Pacific region, the higher latitudes of North America, Central, Southern, and Western Africa, as well as Siberia. Although it has not been specified by the respective authors, it should be noted that the reference sub-datasets from North and South America most likely do not contain osteometric data from indigenous people but rather consist of measurements derived from non-native Americans of African and/or European ancestry (Berge and Bergman, 2001; de Lucena et al., 2019; Lopez-Capp et al., 2018; Pires et al., 2016; Suazo et al., 2009; Wanebo and Chicoine, 2001). The only exception represents the South American sample set from Peru (Pachacamac, Inca culture), which consists of 59 individuals with artificially

deformed skulls. Note that this is the only subsample that consists of intentional cranial deformations.

On the continental level, sexes appear to be equally distributed. On average, 34.90% of the overall continental datasets are female. The average relative frequency for male subgroups per continent is 40.09%, which is slightly higher, similar to the differences in frequencies present in the newly collected datasets reported above. The mean relative abundance of the sex-unknown subgroups per continent is 34.17%. The only exception, with almost completely balanced samples, is from Europe, where most studies utilized clinical data with known sex information. Note that the sex distributions may differ drastically when considering populations individually. Here, populations that are represented by several studies or where the study was designed with balanced subgroup sample sizes from the beginning tend to have better overall balanced groups.

Regarding sample distribution between populations, the total frequencies are not balanced, as is the case with the newly collected datasets described above. For the reference datasets, the sample size per population strictly depends on how many studies have been previously published for the respective populations. Whereas most populations are represented by only a few studies, some have gained significantly more attention, and, therefore, more data has been collected on these population groups. With a total of 4,085 measured individuals, India is the most extreme example, accounting for almost 70% of the entire Asian sample set and 40.96% of the entire 2D reference data set. This also leads to the extremely low relative abundance of other populations from Asia, which barely exceeds 2% within this group. Fortunately, some populations from other continents outside Asia, such as Egypt for Africa, Brazil for South America, or Greece for Europe, also reach relatively high frequencies.

Figure 9: Absolute number of all individuals per population (black values) with indication of the sex-known and sex-unknown specimens (white values) of the entire 2D FM reference dataset. Population sex-subgroups have been summed per continent. The newly collected data from Berlin is not included here.

4.2 Error Analysis

4.2.1 2D Measurement Error Analysis

All statistical methods applied to evaluate the intraobserver error rates of the measured FML and FMB variables consistently revealed near unanimous agreement between the sets of repetitions. None of the calculated differences between the first and second physically measured repetitions or between their averages and the third virtual remeasurement revealed an error value above the defined maximum threshold for osteometric measurement error, or CAD, of 2 mm. As visualized in the Bland-Altman plots for FML and FMB (Fig. S3.3), it can be observed that none of the physical repetitions had a difference larger than 1 mm and that only five different measurement repetitions per variable fall outside the LoA. This is expected for normally distributed data where 95% of all points usually fall within the 95%CI LoA range around the repetition sample mean (Earthman, 2015; Kalra, 2017; Sedgwick, 2013). The third virtual repetition measured on the 3D models in MeshLab was only evaluated and compared with the physical repetitions using the TEM. Both aTEM and %TEM for the dataset, including

the MeshLab measurement, were slightly higher for both variables compared to the repetition comparison of only the physical measurements. However, with %TEMs of 1.02% and 1.01% and R values of 0.9804 and 0.9833 for FML and FMB, respectively (Tabs. S3.1 and S3.2), it can be concluded that the virtual repetitions revealed similar results to the two physically repeated measurements.

As expected, based on the high-resolution of the Artec scanner, the generated 3D models represent an accurate virtual surrogate of the real specimens, and no errors due to incorrect scaling (which could negatively influence the 3D GM form analysis later) were detected. The fact that the virtual measurements display slightly higher offsets could be explained by the less intuitive nature of taking distance measurements in a virtual space than in reality, where the physical boundary of the specimen clearly delineates where measuring points can be set. Therefore, the operator has no intuitive reference as to where to precisely place the measuring endpoint. Consequently, this may lead to higher error levels compared to physical measurements. The physical repetitions of FML and FMB revealed %TEMs of 0.41% and 0.64%, respectively. They are below the recommended maximum acceptable %TEM value for a single observer of 1.5% and can be considered reliably low (Goto and Mascie-Taylor, 2007). The derived coefficient of reliability R values are 0.9969 for FML and 0.9932 for FMB (Tabs. S3.1 and S3.2), which indicates that less than 0.01% of the measured variability in the data can be explained by the observer measurement error. These values are far below the suggested threshold value for R, which is set to 0.95 (i.e., $R > 0.95$) (Ulijaszek and Kerr, 1999; Ulijaszek and Lourie, 1994). In conclusion, the extremely low R metrics for FML and FMB indicate that the repetitions are mostly reliable and precise (Goto and Mascie-Taylor, 2007).

Findings of the %TEM and R coefficient are further supported by the calculated LCCC values of 0.9969 for FML and 0.9932 for FMB, which implies extremely high and significant Pearson's correlations in both cases (both times $p < 0.05$). Pearson's correlation coefficient of the FML repetitions is $r(96) = 0.9969$ and $r(96) = 0.9933$ for both FMB repeated remeasurements (Tab. S3.5). As can be seen in Figure S3.6, the individually repeated data points barely diverge from the line of best fit through the point cloud, which itself is almost identical with the 45-degree reference line. According to the classification of the LCCC by McBride (2005), both values can be considered to show 'almost perfect concordance', i.e., high levels of accuracy and precision between the repetitions.

Based on the results, it can be concluded that the intraobserver error rates of FML and FMB are considerably small and repeatable in this study. Although only the intraobserver error was evaluated here, similar results can be expected between repetitions among different observers given that the FM is an easily accessible and measurable structure of simple overall anatomy.

4.2.2 3D Measurement Error and Landmark Placement Precision

The FM landmark configuration of twelve individuals was collected five times over several weeks. Each set of five repetitions per individual was subjected to an error shape-PCA and centroid radius analysis. Overall, the repetitions form distinct clusters in the PCA shape space, indicating close correspondence or similarity (Figs. S3.8.1 to S3.8.12). In almost all cases, none of the other sample individuals fall within the shape area of the repetitions constructed by the convex hulls. The only two exceptions are RV 379 (Germany, Fig. S3.8.7) and RSK 502 (Greece, Fig. S3.8.10), where one other individual is located within the repetition space or clusters at least extremely close to its boundaries. One reason for that could be explained by the overall small morphological shape variation between specimens along the first and second PCs, where most individual landmark configurations cluster relatively close together, which is also discussed later. In contrast to that, the repetitions often span a wide area, showing that the repetition variation is relatively high compared to the actual biological FM variation of the whole sample, which supports the notion of relatively low sample variation.

Regarding the centroid radius approach, most repetitions performed comparably well (Figs. S3.7.1 to S3.7.12). Before semilandmark sliding to ensure equal interlandmark distances, the error rates of the fixed landmarks tend to be the lowest. This is expected because these are the best defined and locatable points. The semilandmark of the posterior left and right FM segments had smaller errors than their anterior counterparts most likely due to the fact that the interior bony rim of the FM is more sharply and distinctly defined in this area. This gives less spatial freedom for the observer to place landmarks. This is not the case for the anterior sections, where typically no clearly visible FM ridge exists due to the presence of the AOC and its bulging effect and protrusion into the FM space. Hence, error rates are usually slightly higher in this area. Single anterior semilandmarks of some individuals (RV 1293 (Eritrea), S 4585 (Germany), RSK 502, and RV 1122 (both Greece)) even reached relative error rates above the threshold of 5% but never exceeded 9%. Affected landmarks are usually furthest away from a fixed landmark on either side, i.e., the middle semilandmarks of a FM quarter. This observation is supported by the similarity of internal error patterns across many sets of repetitions, where the error rate of semilandmarks increases as the distance to the two fixed landmarks that enclose each of the four FM quarters increases. This can be interpreted as increasing and decreasing observer uncertainty and may be unavoidable using a manual 3D FM landmark collection protocol as defined in this study. Visually, this phenomenon is represented as a wave-like distribution in the heights of relative error bars, best represented by the error pattern of RV 1122 (Greece, Fig. 10, same as Fig. S3.7.11).

Fig. 10: Results of the centroid radius approach calculated for the five landmark repetitions of the entire landmark-semilandmark configuration ($n = 40$) show the relative standard deviations or percentage (%) error of each landmark before (left) and after (right) semilandmark sliding and Procrustes superimposition (GPA). The non-standardized landmarks before GPA and sliding in this example illustrate well the wave-like error pattern with higher relative percentage errors in the anterior FM quarters (LM2 to LM10 and LM32 to LM40) compared to the posterior semilandmark segments (LM12 to LM20 and LM22 to LM30). Labelled x-axis ticks represent the only fixed landmarks (LM1 (ba), LM11 (LL), LM21 (op), LM31 (LR)). Blue dotted line = 5% threshold.

As all subsequent analyses were performed only on Procrustes transformed (GPA) and slid (semi)landmark data, the centroid radius approach for the repeated landmark configurations of the twelve individuals was also computed based on their standardized shape coordinates (Figs. S3.7.1 to S3.7.12). After GPA and semilandmark sliding, the landmark placement error was equally spread over the entire landmark configuration, or more precisely, over the respective FM quarter between the four non-slid, fixed landmarks. Although the error rates overall in almost all landmarks and semilandmarks slightly increased due to the GPA and the sliding steps, this can be neglected as none of the individuals displayed highly erroneous landmarks with a relative percentage error above 5%. The obtained results of the intraobserver 3D (semi)landmark precision and error analysis show that the suggested landmark configuration reveals repeatable and precise results, justifying its use in subsequent analysis. However, it is recommended to evaluate interobserver differences in the newly defined landmark configuration in the future. Among the five repetitions of each of the twelve repeated landmark configurations, the following were chosen as they are visually closest to the repetition centroid in the error shape-PCAs: Eritrea (RV 1285 and RV 1293 – both fifth repetitions, RV 1304 – first repetition), Japan (RV 2148 – fourth repetition, S 4035 and S 4039 – both second repetitions), Germany (RV 879 – fourth repetition, RV 1616 – third repetition, S 4585 – second repetition), and Greece (RSK 502 – second repetition, RV 1122 – fourth repetition, and lastly, RV 1847 – third repetition).

4.3 2D Osteometry

4.3.1 Evaluation of Parametric Assumptions

The distribution of the two FM variable residuals was graphically visualized with Q-Q plots and histograms. They were quantified using skewness and kurtosis metrics and tested

by performing the SW-test and Levene's test to evaluate whether the required assumptions, such as normality and homogeneity of variances for parametric statistical analyses, were met. As the residuals can be obtained from the FM raw data, the residuals are not separately reported in this study. According to the Q-Q plots (Figs. S3.10.1 to S3.11.12), most residuals of the analyzed subgroups tend to be normally distributed and are either close to or within the 95%CI of the line of best fit. Only in a few cases did distribution tails slightly diverge, resulting in more 'heavy-tailed' distributions. It should be noted that the largest deviations from normality are seen in samples with a lower number of individuals. Samples with more data points (e.g., the German sample) show slightly better fits. Distributions were also closer to normality in the case of the sex-pooled population groups (Figs. S3.11.1 to S3.11.12). However, minor divergences still occurred here as well. Residual histograms with density curves appeared to be a less intuitive option for the interpretation of residual normality given the overall small sample sizes and, consequently, the small number of histogram bars. When sexes were pooled, the population-wise residual histograms revealed that the data was more normally distributed. Skewness values for all variables consistently ranged within the acceptable limits of above or below ± 1 , which can be taken as support for symmetric, normally distributed subsamples (Hair et al., 2017). Regarding kurtosis, most subsample distributions have negative values and can therefore be considered platykurtic with short, thin tails. This implies the absence of outliers. Neither the negative nor the positive kurtosis values exceeded the acceptable margins of ± 2 (Coolican, 2009; Mayers, 2013). Skewness and kurtosis values are listed in tables S3.9.1 to S3.9.3. Shapiro-Wilk tests systematically resulted in p-values above the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$; Tab. S3.14), providing grounds to reject the null hypothesis of non-normally distributed data and support the notion that the residuals of all three FM variables in each subgroup are normally distributed. Furthermore, according to the results of Levene's test (all p-values > 0.05 ; Tab. S3.15), it can be accepted that the residual variance among all groups is equal, and that homoscedasticity is given.

The problem that arises is one of sample size and balance. The number of individuals per subgroup clearly differs and is, for example, in the case of the Japanese sub-dataset, extremely small. Japanese females, males, and the overall population subsample appear to be insufficiently representative of the actual Japanese population. This is supported by the distinctive sample standard deviation and minimum to maximum range patterns shown in Figures S3.46 to S3.48. Usually, minimum-to-maximum FML and FMB value ranges exceed the SD around the mean, which itself appears to be somewhat consistent across populations, regardless of whether they are sex-separated or -pooled. However, this is not the case for the small Japanese sample, especially its male subgroup, where the SD exceeds minimum and/or maximum limits. The Eritrean and Greek samples, which are also rather underrepresented, tend to show similar data distribution patterns, where the lower and/or upper SD margins closely approach the minimum or maximum range limits but never exceed them as in the Japanese subsamples. Only the German sample set, represented by more individuals, shows

similar distribution characteristics to other, well-representative reference sample sets. Despite their small subsample sizes, all affected subgroups aligned well with the observed 'normal' osteometric variation of the FM reference data. Given that the residual data distributions appear to be normally distributed and have equal between-group variances, it can be concluded that the assumptions of parametric statistical methods have been met.

4.3.2 Descriptive Statistics, Group Comparison and Meta-Analysis of the 2D Measurements

Tables summarizing the full descriptive statistics, including all metrics calculated from the FML, FMB, and FMI raw data per sex and population, are reported in the supplementary materials of this study (Tabs. S3.16 to S3.18). The population-wise FML means, and their SD are: 35.36 mm \pm 2.90 mm (Eritrea), 35.07 mm \pm 1.94 mm (Japan), 36.11 mm \pm 2.46 mm (Germany), and 35.40 mm \pm 3.04 mm (Greece). The obtained mean FMB and SD values per population are: 28.54 mm \pm 2.36 mm (Eritrea), 30.18 mm \pm 1.92 mm (Japan), 30.55 mm \pm 2.17 mm (Germany), and 29.96 mm \pm 2.38 mm (Greece). Lastly, by using FML and FMB, the following population FMI mean values and their SD were calculated: 80.88 \pm 4.99 (Eritrea), 86.08 \pm 3.98 (Japan), 84.79 \pm 5.71 (Germany), and 84.83 \pm 4.91 (Greece). In all populations, average FM metrics appeared to be slightly larger in males than in females. Although the means of the sex groups are close to each other in most populations (Figs. S3.49, S3.51, and S3.52). Interestingly, males across the newly studied populations tend to exhibit wider FML and FMB ranges than females and often comprise some of the smallest measured individuals of the present subsamples (e.g., Eritrean, German, Greek, and overall population-pooled sample in Fig. S3.53). The exception is the Japanese sample, where both sex groups are almost completely separated, most likely due to the lack of additional data points (Fig. S3.50). The ANOVA results revealed no significant mean differences ($p > 0.05$) for any of the three 2D FM variables between sexes or for the interaction terms between population and sex across all populations (Tabs. S3.32 to S3.34). The study's null hypothesis that there are no intrapopulation mean differences in 2D FM variables ($H_{0.1}$) can therefore be retained. The large degree of overlap in FML and FMB between sexes across population sub-datasets from Berlin (Figs. S3.49, S3.51, S3.52, and S3.53) and the reference data from the literature (Figs. S3.46 and S3.47) support this conclusion. As a result, the visually large divergence between female and male population means in Figure S3.56 should not be overinterpreted, as their group ranges are not shown in this graph. The female convex hull cluster lies towards the smaller FM measurement spectrum, which is mostly driven by the exceptionally small female subgroups of the Chinese (Song et al., 1992) and Nepalese (Maharjan et al., 2018) reference samples. Most of the other female subsamples either plot close to the male cluster or overlap with it. Sex differences in calculated FMI measurements were found to be not significant according to the ANOVA results of the sex-known-only sample (Tab. S3.34). Visually and

numerically, no substantial sexual differences or trends could be detected between the frequencies of FMI shape categories across all four populations from the Berlin dataset (Figs. S3.49 to S3.53, S3.60, and Tab. S3.61). When compared with the reference dataset, it can be observed that the FMI ranges between sexes vary greatly across the globe without apparent sex-related trends. Most sex-specific and sex-pooled population FMI means lie within the intermediate shape range (Fig. S3.48).

Figure 11: Scatter plot and marginal boxplots for all averaged physical FML versus FMB measurements and their population-wise group means (x-dots) with relation to FMI shape category distribution. Sex-known and sex-unknown individuals were included. Convex hulls enclose each population separately.

As with the small differences between sexes, there are large overlapping areas in the FML and FMB dimensions between the sex-pooled population-wise subgroups (Fig. 11). The FM data from Germany and Greece is virtually indistinguishable and spans approximately the same FML and FMB range. Although their means in both measurements and their FMB medians are slightly different. The convex hull coverage areas of both European populations completely enclose the Japanese sex-pooled sample, whose group mean is close to the Germans – in fact, it is closer to the German average than the German mean is to the Greek. As seen in Figure 11, the Eritrean mean differs more substantially from the other three populations, although only in FMB. With respect to FML, there are almost no differences between the Japanese and German means but rather between their medians, as shown in the marginal boxplots in Figure 11. When considering convex hull clusters, the most noticeable trend in interpopulation differences is found between Eritrean and Japanese skulls. Eritrean individuals tend towards the longer but narrower FM spectrum, whereas the Japanese's FMs appear to be shorter but wider.

This pattern can also be seen when considering FMI shape categories, as displayed in the advanced contingency table in Figure S3.58. More than half (52.38%) of the Eritreans and only around 9%, or one individual, of the Japanese skulls have a narrow FM ($FMI > 82.0$). On the contrary, only three Eritrean individuals (14.29%) have a wide FM ($82.0 \leq FMI < 86.0$), and the remaining seven (33.33%) have an intermediate foramen shape ($FMI \geq 86.0$). In the Japanese population, more than half of the sample has an intermediate shape (54.55%), and four (36.36%) have a wide shape (see also Tab. S3.59). Although both subsamples are represented by a few individuals, this trend is similar to that of the reference FM mean data distributions (Figs. S3.54 and S3.55). There is again a considerable degree of overlap between the mean reference data from Asia and Africa. African FMs tend to be long and narrow, and those of Asians tend to be shorter but wider. Furthermore, there appears to little overlap between the African and South American samples and between the African and European groups. European and American groups cluster closely together. Despite the mentioned Chinese and Nepalese offshoot samples, Asian groups overlap widely with the average American and European data points. Note that these are only trends in mean values whose differences become relativized when the group ranges are considered (Figs. S3.46 and S3.47). On this basis, differences between populations and their sex subgroups become widely negligible.

The results of both ANOVAs based on the entire dataset, as well as on the sex-known samples, revealed significant mean differences between populations ($p < 0.05$) for FMB (Tabs. S3.33 and S3.38) and FMI (Tabs. S3.34 and S3.39) variables, but not for FML (Tabs. S3.32 and S3.37). Note that the exclusion of the sex-unidentified individuals did not change the significance of the test results. Tukey-HSD post-hoc tests for the significant sex-known and sex-pooled sub-datasets were performed. This revealed that the difference in FMB between

Figure S3.46: Univariate plot showing the spectrum of FML means (centre points), standard deviations from the means (dark grey lines) and minimum to maximum ranges (coloured lines) across all ordered FM reference summary statistics including the new Berlin data (blue filled point shapes: triangle (up) = female group, triangle (down) = male group, square = sex-pooled group). Blue filled point shapes represent mean values of the newly analysed Berlin samples. Sex-pooled samples included sex-unknown individuals in the newly analysed populations.

Eritreans and Germans was significantly different in both subsamples ($p = 0.0256$ and 0.0043 , respectively; Tabs S3.35 and S3.40). The FMB mean difference for the cropped, sex-known sample was 1.72 mm ($95\%CI = 0.15$ mm to 3.29 mm), which is similar to the results obtained for the sex-pooled population sample with a difference of 2.01 mm ($95\%CI = 0.50$ mm to 3.53 mm) between the means of Germany and Eritrea. This result is consistent with the visual observation of FMB mean differences described previously (Fig. 11). Although Eritrea did not

Figure S3.47: Univariate plot showing the spectrum of FMB means (centre points), standard deviations from the means (dark grey lines) and minimum to maximum ranges (coloured lines) across all ordered FM reference summary statistics including the new Berlin data (blue filled point shapes: triangle (up) = female group, triangle (down) = male group, square = sex-pooled group). Blue filled point shapes represent mean values of the newly analysed Berlin samples. Sex-pooled samples included sex-unknown individuals in the newly analysed populations.

significantly differ from Japan or Greece, its mean differences were still relatively large (1.42 mm and 1.64 mm, respectively) compared to group combinations that did not include Eritrea (Tab. S3.40). According to the pairwise post-hoc test for FMI in the sex-known dataset (Tab. S3.36), only Japan and Eritrea differed significantly from each other ($p = 0.0351$) with an FMI difference of 6.15 (95%CI = 0.31 to 11.98). This result is consistent with previously described relative frequency differences in derived FMI shape categories between both populations

Figure S3.48: Univariate plot showing the spectrum of FMI means (centre points), standard deviations from the means (dark grey lines) and minimum to maximum ranges (coloured lines) across all ordered FM reference summary statistics including the new Berlin data (blue filled point shapes: triangle (up) = female group, triangle (down) = male group, square = sex-pooled group). Blue filled point shapes represent mean values of the newly analysed Berlin samples. Sex-pooled samples included sex-unknown individuals in the newly analysed populations. Vertical grey-dotted lines enclose the intermediate FM shape spectrum, narrow FM's are to its left, wide to the right.

(Figs. S3.58 and Tab. S3.59). Results for this pair persisted to be significant ($p = 0.0451$) with similar mean differences and 95%CI in the sex-pooled dataset including all individuals (Tab. S3.41). Other than the ANOVA results of the sex-known dataset (Tab. S3.36), FMI mean differences between Germany and Eritrea in the sex-pooled dataset became significant ($p = 0.0271$) with a difference of 3.91 (95%CI = 0.32 to 7.51; Tab. S3.41). Although the divergence

between Eritrea and Greece was not significant with a p-value of 0.1045 in this analysis, their actual FMI difference of 3.96 is almost identical to the significant mean difference of 3.91 between Germany and Eritrea. As in the one-way ANOVA results for FMB, all remaining pairwise group combinations that did not include Eritrea were insignificantly small (Tab. S3.41). From this observation, it could be concluded that significant differences and trends in the differences between populations were mostly driven by the FMB variable, which likely led to significant differences in FMI measurements. However, as mentioned before, any significant differences are less practically meaningful when the large interpopulation overlaps are taken into consideration. For this reason, no DFA was performed on any of the FM measurements, as their results most likely would not have revealed a good separation and classification accuracy between the subgroups.

4.3.3 Further Notes on the Reference Sample

The relationship between sample SD and range in the univariate reference data plots has already been mentioned above in reference to sample coverage and representativeness (Section 4.3.1). However, more results can be visually drawn from the plots shown in Figures S3.46 to S3.48 to gain further insights into global trends in FM osteometric characteristics as well as reference data integrity. In contrast to the groupwise SD spectra, variable ranges from minimum to maximum values display a much higher and less consistent interpopulation variation. As no raw data information was available for any of the included reference studies, it is not certain that these reference datasets did not include some excessively large or small sample outliers (or erroneous measurements) that could cause the observable major divergences in range patterns of some reference populations (e.g., FML: Saudi Arabian females as well as Egyptians and Polish males; FMB: Saudi Arabian and Polish females as well as Portuguese males). Interestingly, the affected groups also have the largest FMI group means (all within the wide FM shape category) and ranges (Fig. S3.48). As FMI is calculated as an aspect ratio of FMB divided by FML in all the selected reference studies, excessively large or small (outlier) foramina could cause distortions of the 'normal' FMI mean distributions. Therefore, the distribution of FMI means in Figure S3.48, especially in the higher range spectrum, should be treated with caution.

In both linear measurements, FML (Fig. S3.46) and FMB (Fig. S3.47), including their aspect ratio (Fig. S3.48), the mean values across sexes and populations are similar. It becomes clear, especially when these values are sorted in ascending order, that the FM variables only cover a narrow morphometric spectrum of a few millimeters. Although the ascending group order within the univariate range plots is not necessarily bio-geographically meaningful, their cross-population dispersal can be considered representative of the global FM variation in modern humans. Here, most mean data points closely align with each other. These,

when taken together, form a normally distributed sample without large gaps. Only at the minimum and maximum ends of this distribution do larger discrepancies occur that resemble a heavy-tailed normal distribution. These gaps could either reflect data gaps, i.e., data that is missing from other populations, or sample biases. The latter might apply for the small, continent-wide datasets analyzed in Zdilla et al. (2017). When using such a geographically wide-ranging continental group of sub-samples, it can be expected that their mean values would plot somewhere in the middle of the overall FM variable distribution. However, their summary statistic values for FML and FMB make up the largest groups with respect to FM group means. This unexpected offset could either be caused by a sample bias, as their study was based on only a few individuals per continent, or a population subgroup. Another explanation could be that their applied method to calculate standard FM measurements from their semilandmark data overestimates the absolute Euclidean distances, as they used photographs. At this point, it remains unknown how these photographs were scaled and if this scaling was reliable. It is also not mentioned how or if these photos were taken in a standardized manner. Whether these aspects of a small sample size or the data collection procedure led to these large, potentially erroneous measurements cannot be concluded, given that their raw data measurements are not published, and their applied data collection procedure was insufficiently described. However, their subsequent 2D GM shape results are not affected by this, given that size does not play a factor in GM shape analysis.

4.4 3D Geometric Morphometrics

4.4.1 Shape-PCA and Shape Group Comparison

The results of the 3D GM shape analysis using shape-PCA and wireframe deformations led to similar results as those obtained from the previously summarized 2D analysis. According to the broken stick model, the first eleven PCs cumulatively accounted for 80.66% of the total variance of the dataset, including the sex-unknown individuals (Fig. S3.22.1 and Tab. 3.22.12). The first nine PCs of the sex-known dataset explained 75.59% of the variance (Fig. S3.23.1 and Tab. S3.23.2) and can be considered most meaningful and retainable. The PC score values of these PCs are listed in Tables S3.26 and S3.27. The following description will only focus on the results drawn from the larger dataset, including all individuals, as there are almost no apparent differences between the PC score plots and wireframe deformations along the maintained PCs of the sex-known-only and entire dataset (Figs. S3.62 to S3.65). The mean shape configuration of the 98 individuals is very symmetrical in planar orthographic view and mostly straight in a lateral perspective with a convex (towards inferior or postcranial) anterior and concave (towards superior or cranial) posterior bulge or vaulting in the left and right anterior FM quarters at the level of the AOCs (Fig. 12). The posterior part of the consensus landmark configuration is rounder than the anterior section and resembles the elongated

circular shape of a semi-oval. The shape of the anterior FM part appears close to that of a shorter semi-oval with straighter, bilaterally curved sides that merge in a smooth anterior curvature.

Fig. S3.62: Unstandardized Procrustes shape PC score plot of the entire, sex-pooled sample showing PC1 (accounting for 22.89% of the explained variance) and PC2 (accounting for 12.94% of the explained variance) and minimum and maximum wireframe deformations of the landmark configuration from the mean shape along each axis. Convex hulls enclose each population. X-hollow scatter points represent PC score population group means.

Figure 13 summarizes shape changes from the mean shape of the first four PCs in positive and negative directions. The first PC explains 22.89% of the variance and is mostly associated with shape deformations from the mean shape along the longitudinal or sagittal axis of the FM. Negative PC deformations along PC1 result in an inward (medially) projection of the most transversolateral landmarks (i.e., narrowing of the FM width) and a relatively small shortening of the anterior length and a larger extension of the posterior length, both in a posterior direction. These changes are inverted along the positive PC1 axis. The lateral profile becomes more convex (i.e., towards superior) in the positive and more convex (i.e., towards inferior) in the negative PC directions. Mean shape changes along PC2 that explain 12.94% of the

Fig. S3.63: Unstandardized Procrustes shape PC score plot of the entire, sex-pooled sample showing PC3 (accounting for 9.70% of the explained variance) and PC4 (accounting for 8.25% of the explained variance) and minimum and maximum wireframe deformations of the landmark configuration from the mean shape along each axis. Convex hulls enclose each population. X-hollow scatter points represent PC score population group means.

morphological sample variance are characterized by length extensions (positive) and contractions (negative) of the landmarks of the two anterior FM quarters. The observable shape changes in the posterior-most curvature are very small. The FM width becomes wider towards negative PC2 values and narrower along the positive spectrum of the PC axis. This pattern represents an inversion of the width shape changes observed in PC1, while the length shift remains the same, although smaller in magnitude. In a lateral view, negative PC2 shape deformations lead to an inward projection of the lateral most landmarks to form a concave profile similar to the shape deformation along the positive PC1 axis and vice versa. PC3 accounts for 9.70% of variance and describes proportional shape deformations of the FM width-to-length ratio. The negative projection is associated with a wider and shorter FM, while it becomes narrower but longer in the positive direction. The profile of the outline is quite flat along the negative axis of PC3. The anterior-most part around the Basion landmark slightly superiorly projects into the skull space. Shape deformations in the central profile part resemble

the same behavior as observed along PC1 and are therefore the inversion of PC2. With PC4 accounting for 8.25% of the captured variance, the first bilaterally asymmetrical shape changes of the FM occur, which essentially describe a deformation in an oblique direction relative to the mid-sagittal plane. Negative changes are associated with a narrowing of the posterior right to anterior left FM diameter and a widening of the posterior left to anterior right diameter. Positive changes along PC4 thus behave inversely: the posterior left to anterior right distance becomes wider, whereas the posterior right to anterior left distance gets narrower. Positive PC deformations in profile view are overall similar to those seen in the positive PC3 direction, and vice versa. Like PC3, PC5 explains 7.21% of the variance and describes small shape changes in the FM width, affecting mostly the lateral most landmarks (not shown in Fig. 13). Positive shape deformations result in an inward (medial) projection of the lateral landmarks, whereas negative changes lead to their outward projection. In the lateral view, the positive PC5 shape changes lead to an inward bulging of the posterior quarter semilandmarks and a downward shift (towards inferior) of the posterior most landmarks. Negative changes lead to a convex outward bulging of the middle and lateral most landmarks and an inward displacement of the posterior most landmarks. The anterior landmarks are not affected by any changes on the fifth PC. The following PCs account for less than 5% of the total sample variance and are thus not separately described as the shape changes are mostly of a small magnitude and restricted to specific landmark configuration areas, often located within the AOC region.

Fig. 12: Fixed landmark/sliding semilandmark configuration after Procrustes superimposition (GPA) of the entire sample ($n = 98$; left figures). GPA-alignment was performed using the minimum Procrustes distance criterion. Mean (consensus) shape configuration of the whole sample shown on the right. Anterior is facing upwards. Planar view from caudal. Lateral profile view from lateral left. Orthographic perspective.

Fig. 13: Wireframe shape deformation of the foramen magnum along the first four PCs (PC1 to PC4). Deformation vectors were generated using the whole sample ($n = 98$). Wireframe outline represents the mean (consensus) shape configuration, whereas landmark points represent the minimum or maximum deformed shape of the respective PC axis. Connection lines between the landmark points and the wireframe represent the deformation vectors. Blue arrows represent the deformation vector directions of the landmarks in planar view. Anterior is facing upwards. Orthographic perspective.

3D and 2D scatter plots of the first four PCs were created to observe trends in Procrustes shape data distributions. Figure 14 shows the distribution across the first three PCs in three dimensions. Two-dimensional PC plots that present the distributions of the first versus the second and the third against the fourth PC are shown in the supplementary material appendix (Figs. S362 to S3.65). Visualizations of these shape deformations using wireframe models were plotted alongside the component axis of the shape-PC score scatter plots to help

interpret the graphs (Figs. 14, S3.62 to S3.65). When PC1 is plotted against PC2, they together account for 35.83% of the variance (sex-pooled sample). All populations cluster closely together and overlap to wide extents (Fig. S3.62). Only the Japanese cluster and its mean differ from the other populations along the negative axis direction of PC2. The group shape means that the remaining groups cluster close together and are almost perfectly identical to the dataset consensus shape. Note that all population group means interfere with the convex hull-shaped clusters of each population along PC1 and PC2. Means and clusters of the sex-known subgroups show slightly higher divergences from the PC plot center but are still overall identical (Fig. S3.64). Slightly higher differences can be seen in the next plot showing PC3 (accounting for 10.57% of the explained variance) versus PC4 (accounting for 8.84% of the explained variance) as the third component describes shape changes and associated deformations from wide and short (negative) to narrow and long (positive) FMs (see above). Here, the Eritrean cluster and mean tend towards the positive extreme along PC3. The Japanese move slightly along the negative axes of PC3 as well as PC4, while remaining similar to the German and Greek groups, which do not substantially vary from the overall mean and show almost identical distributions in the shape space (Fig. S3.63). This pattern is also reflected in the sex-known dataset, although the differences between Japanese females and males appear to be large upon first inspection. However, this may be caused by the small sample size of this population. Shape differences along PC3 are overall similar to the 2D size variances shown in Figure 11.

The results gathered from the visual assessment of 3D shape differences are consistent with those of the Goodall's F-test or shape ANOVA of the Procrustes distances. The one-way Procrustes ANOVA resulted in a non-significant p-value ($p > 0.05$), indicating that there are no significant mean differences between Procrustes distances between all four populations (Tab. S3.42). Likewise, the results of the two-way ANOVA of the sex-known dataset, including sex as a factorial, independent predictor variable, as well as the interaction term between sex and population, lead to overall insignificant results ($p > 0.05$, Tab. S3.43). From this, it can be concluded that neither sex, population, nor their combined effect have a significant influence on differences between the analyzed groups. Therefore, the null hypotheses of no differences in the shape of the FM between sexes ($H_{0.1}$) and populations ($H_{0.2}$) cannot be rejected. No DFA-based extraction of the PC scores of the (semi)landmark was performed because the 3D shape differences between most groups are not significant and would therefore arguably not have resulted in a highly accurate classification rate.

3D shape PC score plot and FM shape deformation of the entire sex-pooled sample

Fig. 14: The unstandardized 3D Procrustes shape PC score plot of the entire, sex-pooled sample shows PC1 (accounting for 22.89% of the explained variance), PC2 (accounting for 12.94% of the explained variance), and PC3 (accounting for 9.70% of the explained variance) and the minimum and maximum wireframe deformations of the landmark configuration from the mean shape along each axis. Marginal 3D PC score plots are rotated to show only two PCs for better assessment of the data distribution in the 3D space. Refer to the PCA plots in the supplementary materials for better visualization (Figs. S3.62 to S3.65). Ellipsoids represent the probability data distribution around the group mean (set to level = 0.5). The 3D plot was generated using the *scatter3d()* function of the *car* and *rgl* packages. Orthographic perspective.

4.4.2 Form-PCA and Form Group Comparison

In GM, form is often considered a function of centroid size in Procrustes shape coordinates (Mitteroecker et al., 2013). To evaluate whether the CS of the FM has an influence

on FM shape and drives group differences between sexes and/or populations, form-PCA, two-block PLS, and allometric regression analysis were performed. Form-PC score values of the most meaningful PCs are reported in Tables S3.28 and S3.29. Tables S3.30 and S3.31 list the InCS values. For the entire dataset, ten PCs that cumulatively explain 80.19% of the variance (Tab. S3.24.2) should be retained according to the broken stick model (Fig. S3.24.1). Likewise, nine form-PCs of the sex-known sub-dataset can be considered meaningful enough to be kept (Fig. S3.25.1). Together, they explain 77.70% of the observed sample variance (Tab. S3.25.2). Again, the results of the form-PCA between the entire, sex-pooled (Fig. S3.66) and smaller, sex-known (Fig. S3.67) datasets were similar and are therefore reported mostly together. As InCS is usually highly correlated with the first PC (Mitteroecker et al., 2013), form-PC score plots were generated showing only PC1 versus PC2 (Figs. S3.66 and S3.67). InCS represents the variable that causes the most variation along the first component (explaining approximately 20% of the variance), as demonstrated by the biplots alongside the form-PC scatter plots in Figures S3.66 and S3.67. Both PC plots show almost no distinct separation between sex and/or population groups. In fact, the overall population group means are almost completely identical. Only the German group's mean slightly differs from the rest, although mostly along PC2 (explaining around 15 to 18% of the variance). The overlap between all the population's clusters remains large (Fig. S3.66). On the contrary, a small separation along the size-related PC1 between sexes is visible in the form-PCA plot of the sex-known dataset. Whereas the females of the Eritrean, Japanese, and Greek groups spread more along the negative axis of PC, the males move towards positive eigenvalues. The Eritrean males are the only exception, as their group mean is closer to the female group means. Nevertheless, the form-space distributions of all sex groups remain mostly identical. Both sex subgroup means of the German population are identical along PC1 but slightly differ along PC2, indicating that there is no substantial difference in size within this population. Again, the overlap between all groupwise convex hull areas and the mean value approximated between all sexes are close (Fig. S3.67).

The subsequent two-block PLS analysis with 1,000 random permutations of the entire population-separated dataset revealed a weak, non-significant correlation between Procrustes shape coordinates and InCS across all four populations ($r\text{-PLS} = 0.321$, effect size (Z) = -0.3741, $p\text{-value} = 0.637$). The PLS regression slopes and group means of all population groups are slightly positive (ascending), similar, and parallel (Fig. 15). As expected, based on the PLS results of the entire dataset, the sex-known subsample with fewer individuals revealed a slightly poorer and likewise non-significant correlation ($r\text{-PLS} = 0.292$, effect size (Z) = -1.666, $p\text{-value} = 0.957$, 1,000 random permutations; Fig. S3.68). The means between sexes across populations vary to a small extent along both blocks. Their slope inclinations and parallelism are very similar among each group and relative to the overall population regression slopes in

figure 15. The only departure from the rule is seen in the sparse distribution and opposing negative slope of the Japanese males, which can be explained by the overall small subsample size of this group. PLS score values per block are presented in Tables S3.30 and S3.31.

Fig. S3.66: Unstandardized Procrustes form PC score plot and biplot of the entire, sex-pooled sample showing PC1 (accounting for 19.23% of the explained variance) and PC2 (accounting for 17.76% of the explained variance). Convex hulls enclose each population. X-hollow scatter points represent PC score sex-group means.

The ANCOVA test of the defined full allometric model revealed no significant differences in the associations between shape and size ($p > 0.05$) between populations (Tab. S3.44). The null hypothesis of no differences between allometric regression slopes or means among populations ($H_{0.2}$) can therefore not be rejected, and no post-hoc test was performed. Likewise, no significant ANCOVA result ($p > 0.05$) was found for the full allometric model of the sex-known dataset, including sex and population and their interaction terms as predictor factors (Tab. S3.45). Thus, the null hypothesis of no form differences ($H_{0.1}$) between sexes among populations or their combined effect cannot be rejected. Overall, based on the results of the PLS analysis and linear allometric regression, it can be concluded that centroid size

does not significantly affect Procrustes shape coordinates and that it does not signify a considerable factor driving FM shape differences between the studied groups.

Figure. 15: Two-block partial least squares analysis plot and test results. X-hollow points = population means. Colored lines = individual group regression lines.

Figure. S3.68: Two-block partial least square analysis plot and test results of the sex-known dataset. X-hollow points = sex means. Note that the reported test statistics refer to the overall sex-pooled regression line that is not shown here. Coloured lines = individual sex-group per population regression lines.

5. Discussion

5.1 Literature Review of FM Research

As mentioned, the osteometric and morphognostic characteristics of the FM have been widely studied in bioarcheology, forensics, and medical sciences. During extensive bibliographic and online searches, approximately 130 osteometric-morphognostic studies about the FM could be found, of which 81 have been included in the reference sample for the brief meta-analysis in the present study (see Tab. S3.19 for all references). In these studies, anatomical data about the FM was mainly collected for three different reasons:

1) Firstly, to study human bipedal evolution in relation to upright body posture and the relative position and angle of the FM (Dean and Wood, 1981; Landi et al., 2020; Suazo et al., 2009), as well as its anatomical association to other bone structures. In this framework, the FM has been compared with closely related structures of the cranial base such as the AOCs, the mastoid processes, the palatine and jugular foramen (Avci et al., 2011; Luzzi et al., 2019; Sheta et al., 2015), brain size (i.e., endocranial volume) (Radinsky, 1967), the atlas vertebra (Ibrahim, 2019), the orbitals (Pires et al., 2016), the nasal breadth in relation to latitude (Tran, 2020), the mandible (Gillet et al., 2020; İlgüy et al., 2014; Van Vliet et al., 2019), and body height (Gilbe et al., 2020; Röthig, 1971). Whereas positive correlations between the FM and less related structures such as the orbitals have been found to be weak to moderate (Pires et al., 2016), brain size and body height are strongly positively correlated with the FM (Gilbe et al., 2020; Radinsky, 1967), indicating that large individuals also have larger FMs and vice versa (but see Röthig, 1971).

2) A second objective was to estimate intrapopulation differences between sexes. Studies focusing on this topic comprise the majority of FM research. It is often mentioned within the clinical literature that knowledge about the population-specific variation of the FM might be useful to neurosurgeons (Radhakrishna et al., 2012; Sharma et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2019a; Singh et al., 2019b; among others). Although this may be the case for pathophysiological aspects and in attempts to distinguish between the 'normal' FM variation and particular anatomical anomalies and diseases (Tellioglu et al., 2018), the value of differences in FM shape frequencies and osteometric variability on a population-wide basis for surgical practice appears to be rather limited. This view is supported by the weak comparability of FM studies, as outlined in the following: Within forensics, FM studies are usually conducted to evaluate their potential and applicability to estimate the sex of unknown, fragmented human cranial remains. Statistical analysis of FM across age groups (< 50 and > 50 years of age) showed no significant effect of an individual's age on FM variables, suggesting that it is valid to use age-pooled samples to study FM variability, which has been the norm in the field of osteometric research (Gapert et al., 2013). Whereas most studies found significant sex differences in the means of most common 2D osteometric FM variables (Abo El-Atta et al., 2020; Akay et al.,

2017; Burdan et al., 2012; Gapert et al., 2009; Shepur et al., 2014; Tran, 2020; Zdilla et al., 2017; and many others), a smaller number of studies reported insignificant results (Gruber et al., 2009; Günay and Altinkök, 2000; Macaluso, 2011; Singh and Talwar, 2013; Zdilla et al., 2017).

3) The last reason for collecting the anatomical data on the FM was to study interpopulation variability. Studies comparing osteometric data from the FM are rare (Zdilla et al., 2017), and many have opposing views on the applicability of FM measurements to estimate population differences. While some argued against its use altogether (Gruber et al., 2009), others found reasons to do so (Tran, 2020; Zdilla et al., 2017). Many studies have occasionally included comparative osteometric FM data in their discussion but fail to deliberate reasons for differences or similarities among human populations and/or sexes (e.g., Ashwini and Khona, 2018; Chandekar and Jiwane, 2017; Chethan et al., 2012; Cirpan et al., 2016; Devadas et al., 2017; Ukoha et al., 2011). The same holds true for the inclusion and quick evaluation of differences in frequencies of visual FM shape categories among populations. Other than osteometric data, comparisons of visual FM shapes are rather difficult to interpret. This is because the selection of comparison studies appears to be arbitrary and the differences are only discussed in terms of relative frequency varieties of the classified shapes (e.g., Chethan et al., 2012; Sharma et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2019a; Singh et al., 2019b). Further examples of their methodological invalidation are discussed below.

As it stands, not a single in-depth meta-analysis of the FM literature has been conducted. This is not unexpected, given that raw data is not systematically shared, although there are many published studies. Similarly, general FM review studies and reference databases are rare. The two studies that could be found that list statistical summary data of common 2D FM measurements from a fairly comprehensive number of studies were published by Burdan et al. (2014, n = 41) and de Lucena et al. (2019, n = 23). However, upon further inspection of the table published by Burdan et al. (2014), a high number of small but influential typing errors and interchanged measurement data could be identified. This makes it particularly difficult to extract reliable information. The second reference table was not checked in detail. Note that the new reference database compiled for the meta-analysis of the present study includes double the number of studies compared to the list in Burdan et al. (2014) and almost three times the number of studies compared to the table in de Lucena et al. (2019).

5.2 Data Collection Methods and Osteometric Variables of the FM

Most of the osteometric FM studies so far have relied on traditional measurements. They were taken physically, directly from dried skull specimens using calipers, or virtually from digital photographs, including conventional X-ray images, raw CT, or MRI (magnet resonance tomography) image slices, as well as 3D surface reconstructions from medical volume scans

(see table S3.19 for the individual approaches per study). No study could be found that used photogrammetric-, light-, or laser-scanner-based 3D models, as applied in this study. Even when 3D reconstructed volume scans are used, only linear distances are usually measured. Due to this, the FM is usually reduced to a 2D structure. Although this does not necessarily reflect morphological reality (Crider, 2010). As has been noted by Crider (2010), Richards and Jabbour (2011), and Toneva et al. (2018), the FM represents a 3D structure that shows considerable patterns of anatomical variation in its lateral profile. The most variation in the profile outline was found in the inward (concave) and outward (convex) bulging of the FM relative to the cranium and the position of the anterior- and posterior-most landmarks. Due to the lack of reference data on this phenomenon, the question of how these observations can be interpreted in a morphological context cannot be currently addressed.

Most FM studies measured and analyzed the three traditional osteometric variables: FML, FMB, or FMI. However, it appears that there is no consensus about the nomenclature for FML and FMB. Numerous different, although similar, names and abbreviations have been used for these two variables thus far. This lack of standardized terminology in the two most basic FM measurements can cause confusion; it would be better practice to commit to one set of terms, such as those that are most applied, like FML and FMB.

The third most important FM variable is FMI. Different approaches exist to calculate index values based on FML and FMB. The first approach that has been applied in this study is calculated as $FMI = FMB/FML \times 100$, as defined in the classical anthropological literature (Bräuer, 1988; Martin and Saller, 1957). In addition to the common nomenclature of the distinct FMI shape groups listed in the methods section, Richards and Jabbour (2011) mention alternative category labels and shape descriptors: 'oval' or 'dolichotrematous' ($FMI < 81.9$), 'flattened oval' or 'mesotrematus' ($82.0 < FMI < 85.9$), and 'round' or 'brachytrematous' ($FMI > 86.0$). Surprisingly, this classical FMI type is infrequently applied (e.g., Bräuer, 1988; Chandekar and Jiwane, 2017; Erdil et al., 2010; Pires et al., 2016; Vinutha et al., 2018). The second option to calculate FMI is an inversion of the first option, which is often, but not always, divided by 100: $FMI = FML / FMB (x 100)$ (Burdan et al., 2014); Burdan et al. (2012) classify this particular (relative) FMI quotient into three distinct shape categories: a longitudinal oval-like type with $FMI < 0.9$ (90%), a round-like type with $0.9 < FMI < 1.1$ (90% to 110%), and a horizontal oval-like type with $FMI > 1.1$ (110%). From this information alone, it is not easy to identify which anatomical directions 'longitudinal' and 'horizontal' are being referred to. Practically, no other study besides that of Burdan and peers (2012) could be found that has used this classification key. There is an additional classification threshold of 1.2 for the second FMI approach. FMI values smaller than 1.2 represent an ovoid or oval shape ($FMI < 1.2$) and larger ones, a round shape ($FMI \geq 1.2$) (e.g., Alves et al., 2020; Cirpan et al., 2016; Muthukumar et al., 2005). This second classification option is the one that seems to be most utilized in osteometric FM studies (Avci et al., 2011; Chethan et al., 2012; Cirpan et al., 2016;

Darwish et al., 2014; Ficke and Varacallo, 2021; Muthukumar et al., 2005; Vinutha et al., 2018; Zdilla et al., 2017; among others). All three classification approaches and keys differ from one another in such a way that their thresholds and threshold ranges are not concordant or interchangeable, which raises problems, and their inconsequent usage might lead to confusing results. For example, a hypothetical individual with FML = 36.80 mm and FMB = 33.40 mm would be classified as having a wide FM shape using the first FMI approach, which translates to a round or brachytrematous shape according to Richards and Jabbour (2011) (FMI = 90.76). Instead, when using the second FMI formula, the FM of this individual would be classified as being either horizontal oval-like or simply oval (FMI = 1.10 or 110%), depending on whether the first or second classification key is used. Additionally, Burdan et al. (2014), who mention both FMI calculations, do not make a clear distinction between FMB/FML and FML/FMB indices in their explanation of this metric variable, which may lead to further confusion with respect to FMI. Future studies should aim to use a single method. Due to reasons of convenience, the first, traditional FMI metric and shape categories as defined in Martin and Saller (1957) and Bräuer and Knußmann (1988) should be used. However, the practical value of the FMI metric and its reliability in capturing the 'real' shape variation have not been tested before. Criticism has also been raised. Firstly, two measurements alone cannot be considered effective proxies to represent the shape of the FM (Toneva et al., 2018). Second, the cut-off points to differentiate between index shapes are set arbitrarily and therefore not necessarily in a biologically meaningful manner (Martin, 1928a). As a result, it may be argued that the low number of FMI shape categories may not be sufficient to identify, capture, and subsequently differentiate between 'actual' FM shapes. Especially regarding the higher number of used visual FM shapes, FMI may appear to oversimplify FM shape variability in the comparison of both approaches.

By using shape-PCA of FM (semi)landmark data, this study shows that FMI shape categories along PC1 and PC2 are not substantially separated (Fig. S3.62). Only along PC3, which describes mean shape deformations from narrow and long (positive) to wide and short FMs (negative), the three FMI shape categories tended to separate accordingly (Fig. S3.63). However, the overlap between all three shape classes remains large in the shape space, in a way that some FMI-wide individuals interfere with FMI-narrow ones along the positive part of the PC3 axis and vice versa. PC3 accounts for only 9.70% of the captured sample variance, meaning that 90.30% of the remaining variance is explained by other shape variations and deformation vectors. This may lead to the conclusion that although there are some biologically meaningful aspects in the shape changes from narrow-long to wide-short FMs, they are not the most important ones. Thus, the notion by Bräuer (1988) can be partially supported, whereby osteometric indices do not necessarily explain more of the captured osteometric variation than is already done by the underlying variables (i.e., FML and FMB in the present case) used to calculate these aspect ratios. For instance, FML and FMB plotted against one another in Figure 11 provided sufficient information to identify slight differences between

groups, namely between the wider and shorter FMs of the Japanese individuals and the somewhat longer but narrower Eritrean FMs. However, ANOVA and post-hoc tests revealed significant group-wise differences almost exclusively for FMI data. This aligns well with the visual observations of the studies' raw data, as well as mean reference data distributions and related ideas in the literature (de Lucena et al., 2019; Zdilla et al., 2017). If applied consistently, FMI can help to reveal and characterize group relationships to some degree that may be of interest for further investigations from a population history perspective. Its biological meaningfulness, however, should not be overestimated (Martin, 1928b). Overall, given the persisting biases in FMI analysis, it appears to be better to favor GM approaches instead.

Another variable that is often considered is the FM area (FMA). Similar to FMI, FMA is usually calculated based on FML and FMB variables using various formulas. The two most common equations are those published by Teixeira (1982) ($FMA = \pi \times \{(FML + FMB)/4\}^2$) or Radinsky (1967) ($FMA = 1/4 \times \pi \times FML \times FMB$). Note that the second FMA formula is frequently called Routals' formula (Routal et al., 1984), for reasons unknown, although the Radinsky publication appeared much earlier. Catalina-Herrera (1987) used an even simpler version of the Radinsky method: $FMA = \pi \times FML \times FMB$. In addition, a more recent and less frequently applied FMA calculation was proposed by Gapert et al. (2009). This formula relies on circle geometry utilizing the FM circumference (FMC; see below) and its radius (r) ($C = 2 \times \pi \times r$), from which r is calculated and inserted in the second formula: $FMA = \pi \times r^2$. All the FMA calculations utilize basic geometric equations that assume a perfect, symmetrical circular shape as an approximation to the roundish FM shape. Consequently, these approaches cannot account for any natural divergence from the unidirectional symmetry and circularity of the FM. Comparative studies of geometric area calculations revealed significant discrepancies between these methods (Beger et al., 2019). It can be concluded that they are not comparable to each other or able to reliably produce precise and accurate area estimates. Therefore, their use cannot be recommended, not even as rough area approximations (Burdan et al., 2014; Zdilla et al., 2017). If FMA is of interest, more advanced geometric methods should be used.

The circumference or perimeter of the FM, often labeled as FMC, is another occasionally employed variable (Akay et al., 2017; Gapert and Last, 2005; Zdilla et al., 2017). Like FMI and FMA, FMC is mostly calculated using the breadth and length of the foramen and is therefore also not reliable. Another analogous technique was proposed by Gapert and Last (2005), who used calibrated paper strips to measure the FMC (see also Devadas et al., 2017). Although this represents a more precise way to capture FMC, higher rates of measurement error due to various external factors must be expected for this method. An effective and reliable way to (semi)automatically obtain FMA and FMC measurements is to use different computer-based software solutions and 2D or 3D image data of the FM that measure these metrics directly instead of calculating them based on a few distance variables as proxies (e.g., Beger et al., 2019; Burdan et al., 2012; Toneva et al., 2018; Vinutha et al., 2018). The most reliable

and advanced technique to virtually calculate FMA and FMC that has been formulated was proposed by Toneva et al. (2018).

Other less frequently taken linear measurements of the FM are the distance between the anterior pole of the foramen and the bi-interoccipital anterior measurements (Ba-BiSam), the posterior pole and bi-interoccipital posterior measurements (O-BiSpm), as well as the bi-interoccipital anterior measurements (O-BiSam) (Burdan et al., 2014; Richards and Jabbour, 2011). Thus far, they have been used mostly in ontogenetic studies to trace relative size increases in different parts of the FM in early life stages (Richards and Jabbour, 2011). Considering the fact that the FM consists of two functional anterior and posterior matrices (Richards and Jabbour, 2011), these measurements might reveal more distinct results when used in standard osteometry studies of the FM. This is supported by the GM findings that the current shape-PCA and corresponding shape deformation visualizations often show local shape changes restricted to either the anterior or posterior matrix.

To account for the flaws of traditional visual shape estimations and FMI shape assessments, Zdilla et al. (2017) applied new shape descriptors as objective alternatives to mathematically describe the shape of the FM. These include circularity, solidity, aspect ratio of the best-fit ellipse, and roundness (Zdilla et al., 2016). Circularity represents the degree of similarity to a perfect circle and is calculated as $\text{circularity} = 4 \times \pi \times (\text{area})/(\text{perimeter})^2$. Solidity is the quotient of FMA divided by the area within a convex hull that surrounds the FM and describes whether a shape is more concave or convex. The aspect ratio of a best-fit ellipse is the major axis divided by the minor axis of the same best-fit ellipse. Lastly, roundness is like circularity but not as sensitive to irregular shapes. It is calculated as $\text{roundness} = 4 \times (\text{area})/(\pi \times [\text{major axis of a best-fit ellipse}]^2)$. In their study, Zdilla and his co-authors did not find significant differences using these variables between sexes but rather between the artificially deformed Peruvian crania and those from Bengal and Africa in roundness and the ellipse aspect ratio (Zdilla et al., 2017). Unfortunately, the authors did not discuss their statistical findings for these measurements in relation to the more traditional ones and as applied to their sample in more detail. Future research should attempt to incorporate and evaluate the usefulness of these variables while noting that their application may be limited to 2D analysis of the FM.

Landmark-based GM studies of the FM are rare, and only two papers utilizing such techniques could be found (Toneva et al., 2018; Zdilla et al., 2017). In the study by Toneva et al. (2018), 3D models reconstructed from CT images were used to estimate intrapopulation differences of the FM between sexes in a Bulgarian sample. Although they relied on 80 3D semilandmarks per individual, they did not aim to use this kind of data to quantify the shape of the FM. Instead, they used Procrustes coordinates to calculate accurate 3D and projected 2D FMC and FMA values, the latter using polygonal geometry. In accordance with a number of previous studies, their results indicated that FM semilandmark data are not sufficient to

distinguish between females and males. Zdilla et al. (2017) applied GM in a similar framework as the present study to estimate interpopulation differences. To do so, they collected 150 2D semilandmarks per specimen from digital photographs of 152 individuals from different populations in Africa, Asia, Europe, and South America. As they relied on images to collect coordinate data, they were not able to control for any AOC protrusion influence on the shape of the FM, nor could they address variation in the third dimension. The results by Zdilla and peers revealed no significant differences between populations with a 'normal' cranial and FM morphology. The Peruvian group was the only one that significantly differed, consisting of artificially deformed skulls. Interestingly, their results are somewhat different from those obtained in the present GM study; for example, the first three PCs in Zdilla's study together explain 66.69% of the variance, whereas the PC1 to PC3 of the entire, sex-pooled dataset of the present study cumulatively account for 45.53%. The shape deformation patterns of PC1 in both studies are similar but inversed along the component axis. The changes in shape of PC2 and PC3 as observed in the present study are not similar to those in PC2 and PC3 in Zdilla et al. However, shape changes along PC4 of this study appear similar to those described along PC2 in Zdilla's study, although they are, again, inversed along the component axis. This offset might result from 1) the methodological differences between both studies, i.e., the use of 2D GM versus 3D GM landmark data. 2) As a result of this, Zdilla et al.'s approach inevitably accounted for any influence of the protruding effect of the AOCs on the shape of the FM. By using a 3D (semi)landmark configuration as defined for this study, this influence was reduced as far as possible. 3) The 'normal' morphological shape variance of the FM is likely to be overestimated by the PCA in Zdilla et al. as their sample included significantly different, artificially deformed skulls from Peru as well as individuals that possess Basion tubercles. The current study did not include any artificially deformed skulls and excluded individuals with large Basion tubercles. The overlap between the remaining set of their studied populations appears to be similarly large as that seen in the present dataset of non-intentionally deformed crania. The different numbers of landmarks between both studies (40 vs. 150 semilandmarks) may not be considered a substantial factor causing the differences in PCA results. Employing a much smaller landmark configuration in this study still revealed sufficient results to describe reasonable shape changes relative to the much larger configuration of 150 landmarks in Zdilla et al. This suggests that such a large configuration is not necessary to capture the shape and form information of the FM, although it has not been explicitly tested here (Watanabe, 2018).

5.3 Non-Metric Shape Analysis of the FM

In many previous papers, FM shape has been studied using a large and highly variable number of non-metric, visual categories (Zdilla et al., 2017). Figure 16 gives a summary of the differences in number and type of employed FM shapes collected from a compilation of published FM articles ($n = 32$; Tab. S3.21). The most commonly employed set of shape

categories contains *Round, Oval, Egg, Tetragonal, Pentagonal, Hexagonal, and Irregular [A?]* shapes (Akay et al., 2017; Chethan et al., 2012; Kumar et al., 2015; Mittal et al., 2018; Murshed et al., 2003; Pires et al., 2016; Radhakrishna et al., 2012; Radhakrishnan et al., 2012; Sampada et al., 2017; Sharma et al., 2015; Singh et al., 2019a; Vinutha et al., 2018). Other shapes that are more rarely used are *Rhomboid, Trigonal, Diamond* and an additional subvariant of the irregular shape called *Irregular B* (Kumar et al., 2019; Natsis et al., 2013; Singh et al., 2019a; Tubbs et al., 2010a). Lastly, some studies defined partly or completely different sets of FM shapes, including *Circular, Two Semicircles, Heart-like, Wide Oval, Bi-rounded Oval, Ventrally Wide Oval, Bi-pointed Oval, and Dorsally Convergent Oval* (Burdan et al., 2012; Govsa et al., 2011; Richards and Jabbour, 2011; Tubbs et al., 2010a).

Figure. 16: Relative frequencies in percentages (%) of used FM shape categories across different FM studies (n = 32). The category ‘Other/Additional’ refers to alternative sets of categories such as those used in Burdan et al. (2012), Govsa et al. (2011), Natsis et al. (2013), Richards and Jabbour (2011), and Tubbs et al. (2010a). The counts of used shape categories per study are summarized in Table S3.21.

The high levels of variation and inconsistencies of proposed and used shape types are problematic as they limit the comparisons of FM shapes between studies (Zdilla et al., 2017). Within the most used set of shape types, some variation exists as specific categories are sometimes excluded or added. The reliability of the visual shape classifications of the FM must be further questioned because the many categories are continuous subvariants of the roundish to ovoid shape of the FM, which arguably makes it more difficult to distinguish ‘angular’ or ‘polygonal’ shapes. Therefore, high interobserver error rates are likely. There is also a wider range of published reference images that visualize the FM shapes used according to the respective author’s idea of what the categories look like (Akay et al., 2017; Burdan et al., 2012;

Kumar et al., 2015; Kumar et al., 2019; Mittal et al., 2018; Murshed et al., 2003; Natsis et al., 2013; Pires et al., 2016; Radhakrishnan et al., 2012; Sampada et al., 2017; Sharma et al., 2015; Singh et al., 2019a; Vinutha et al., 2018). Upon closer inspection of these schemata, it can be concluded that the presented holotypes of the distinct FM shape categories vary substantially across studies, which adds to the confusion. Lastly, assigning FM shapes and categorizing them into discrete groups is problematic as biological structures are naturally continuous. Any section points and thresholds used to differentiate between shapes are arbitrary and may lead to the artificial creation of biologically unmeaningful groups, as is the case for FMI shape categories discussed previously (Martin, 1928b). Based on these fundamental critiques, it seems appropriate to avoid the morphognostic classification of visual FM shapes. Even though metric indices are less imposed by subjective biases (Toneva et al., 2018), given the concerns raised above, FMI cannot be considered a reliable alternative to estimate FM shapes. Therefore, it is recommended to use GM methods instead, as this represents a more reliable way to capture and quantify the overall shape of anatomical structures (Toneva et al., 2018; Zdilla et al., 2017).

5.4 Synthesis

Although many studies have found significant differences between sexes on intrapopulation levels, the biological meaningfulness and practicability of these results must be questioned, as the difference between means is fairly small and ranges overlap widely (Fig. S3.46 to S3.48), which is consistent with the low degree of sexual dimorphism expressed at the cranial base (Gapert et al., 2009; Gapert et al., 2013; Zhang and Schepartz, 2021). Average sex classification accuracy rates derived from stepwise univariate and multivariate DFA and regression approaches based on different 2D FM variables barely exceed 75%, most of which do not even reach 70% (Abo El-Atta et al., 2020; Chovalopoulou and Bertatos, 2017; Edwards et al., 2013; Gapert et al., 2009; Kamath et al., 2015; Madadin et al., 2017; Seifert et al., 2017; Singh and Talwar, 2013; Suazo et al., 2009; Tambawala et al., 2016; Tellioglu et al., 2018; Toneva et al., 2018; Uthman et al., 2012; Van Vliet et al., 2019; Vinutha et al., 2018). Only a few studies have revealed higher sex-averaged results, ranging between 75% and almost 90% in rare cases (Darwish et al., 2014; Holland, 1986b; İlgüy et al., 2014; Raghavendra Babu et al., 2012; Toneva et al., 2018; Uysal et al., 2005). The discrepancies in accuracy rates between studies may result from the number of variables that were subjected to statistical analysis or due to the degree of sexual differentiation, which might vary between populations (Toneva et al., 2018; Vinutha et al., 2018). Note that some of these studies included other linear measurements from the cranial base (e.g., of the AOC) or from the mandible (İlgüy et al., 2014; Van Vliet et al., 2019), which together led to higher correct classification rates than the (combined) FM distances alone (e.g., Uthman et al., 2012). Therefore, traditional osteometric data from the FM does not fulfill the requirements of the

medicolegal system, whereby a method must yield a correct classification rate above 95% to be labeled and used as a primary discriminator (Lewis, 2007; Toneva et al., 2018). As a result, many authors conclude that osteometric FM data should only be utilized as a supportive, secondary trait for sexing unknown individuals or in cases where only the cranial base has been preserved (Edwards et al., 2013; Singh and Talwar, 2013; Toneva et al., 2018; Ukoha et al., 2011). This view is not shared by the author based on the present results. Primarily due to the overall large inter-group overlap, no DFA was performed on the new data of the present study that would convey the impression that FM variables might be somewhat useful to distinguish between groups and classify unknown individuals. Given that FM measurements have been shown to be highly intercorrelated (Toneva et al., 2018), the application of DFA must further be questioned as the requirement of no data collinearity is violated (DiGangi and Hefner, 2013).

Differences in means and variances between sexes per population appear to be relatively small. These may be explained by the overall similar pattern seen in growth trajectories and the early ontogenetic completion of the FM around the age of ten years old in both sexes, after which no secondary sex- as well as age-related changes occur (El-Barrany et al., 2016; Gapert et al., 2013; Richards and Jabbour, 2011; Toneva et al., 2018; Ukoha et al., 2011; Wescott and Moore-Jansen, 2001). Parts of the cranial base, including the FM, are the first structures in the human body to reach maturity. The majority of the basicranial complex reaches 90% of its adult size around the age of five (including the FMB dimension), with the remaining 10% of small changes occurring over a relatively long period of time until the age of fifteen years old (Cendekiawan et al., 2010; Currie et al., 2017; Richards and Jabbour, 2011). Secondary sexual differentiation of the basicranium during puberty and early adolescence is therefore small to negligible, as documented by Gapert et al. (2013). This pattern of weak sexual difference is consistent with results from similar studies of the basicranium and other basilar bone structures (Bigoni et al., 2010; Zhang and Schepartz, 2021). However, growth patterns between and within different basicranial structures are not consistent. For example, FMB attains its adult dimensions (around five years old) earlier than FML (around ten years old). Furthermore, differential growth rates between individuals and populations can have a substantial effect on the final FM shape. Young individuals with a relatively long FM at the age of five will likely attain a narrower transversal dimension with relatively approximated, more obtuse curvature, and vice versa (Zdilla et al., 2017).

Compared to the intrapopulation aspects of the FM, systematic interpopulation studies are infrequent. Some authors have argued that FM dimensions are insufficient for utilization in population affinity estimations (Gruber et al., 2009; Toneva et al., 2018). The 2D GM results by Zdilla et al. (2017) and the 3D GM results of this study did not find significant differences between the different populations with a 'normal' FM morphology. Only the Peruvian population, with documented artificially deformed skulls, showed significant compression of

the foramina in the anterior-posterior direction (FML) that was different from all other studied groups (Zdilla et al., 2017). Part of these differences in FML is related to the higher incidence of Basion tubercles which the authors assume to be one of the consequences of the cranial deformation. Their overall results agree with patterns found in other morphometric studies of intentional cranial vault body modifications, showing that deformation practices are not just confined to the calvaria (Cendekiawan et al., 2010; Püschel et al., 2020). This observation points towards the importance of ontogenetic growth factors during the early postnatal stages of the cranial base and related soft tissues in the constitution of FM shape and form. The repeatedly documented patterns of asymmetric, oblique shape variation (along PC4 in this study and along PC2 in Zdilla et al. (2017)) have been linked to shape covariation between the cranial base and neurocranial vault as distinct but integrated structures. Like intentional cranial deformations, habitual sleeping positioning and the influence of gravity on the still-malleable infant cranium can result in directional in- and extrinsic compressing and restricting forces that can lead to 'abnormal' growth trajectories, i.e., deformations. Especially when such forces act during the first year of life, this may result in (unintentional) positional head deformities of both the morphological shape of the vault and base, including the FM (Argenta et al., 1996; Martínez-Lage et al., 2006; Zdilla et al., 2017). Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that certain behaviors and repeated, poor body postures of modern lifestyles can affect occipital morphology and obscure sexual and population differences in this skeletal structure of young adults (Shahar and Sayers, 2016, 2018; Zhang and Schepartz, 2021). However, when intentionally deformed crania are not considered, the induced variation is low compared to the bilaterally symmetrical shape variability along the sagittal and transversal body axes explained by more meaningful PCs. Therefore, it appears reasonable to assume that cultural factors such as intentional or unintentional cranial deformations (e.g., sleeping position in young infants and behavioral body posture in relation to workload in young adults) affect the variation seen in the FM to a small degree (Zdilla et al., 2017; Zhang and Schepartz, 2021).

The presence of specific bony tubercles, or exostosis, is another morphological anomaly with implications for FM shape and size characteristics, which can occasionally be observed among cranial series. Such tubercles are almost exclusively located at the middle anterior-most edge or Basion point of the FM and are therefore preferentially called 'Basion tubercle', although several other terminologies exist (Vazquez et al., 1996; Zdilla et al., 2017). They vary in size and shape and often protrude up to several millimeters into the FM space (Fig. S1.4a) and likely originated from the ossification of the apical ligament of the dens process of the second vertebra (Oetteking, 1923; Vazquez et al., 1996). Although these Basion tubercles seemingly occur in all populations, Zdilla et al. (2017) have reported higher incidences among a Peruvian sample of artificially deformed skulls. During the screening of around 1,000 cranial specimens at the anthropological collections in Berlin in search of samples for the present study, in only one case, a skull from Sri Lanka (RV 45; not included in this study), a bony tubercle with a length of 4.74 mm was found at the posterosagittal edge of

the FM, or Opisthion (Fig. S1.4b). The occurrence of ‘Opisthion tubercles’ might be considered even less frequent than its anterior counterpart. To the author’s knowledge, no comparable case has been described in the published literature. Its etiology, therefore, remains unknown.

Fig. S1.4a (left) and S1.4b (right): Indicated by the white arrows are examples of foramen magnum tubercles. Ectocranial view. Anterior is up. Left: Basion tubercle (3.37 mm) in a German individual (RV 901, included in the analysis of the present study). Right: Opisthion tubercle (4.74 mm) in an individual from Sri Lanka (RV 45, not included in the present analysis).

From the available data, it can be concluded that the overall variability in shape, not only between sexes within each population but also across different populations, is considerably small. This makes sense in an evolutionary framework given that the FM mainly serves as a passage for several vital neurocranial and locomotor tissues that run through it and demand their own space. Because of its important hydro-, hemodynamic, and neurological functions, there are functional and evolutionary constraints to the range in FM size dimensions. Abnormally grown FMs are often associated with a number of pathological and congenital conditions (e.g., achondroplasia, Arnold-Chiari malformation, Crouzon, Apert, and Pfeiffer syndrome) that may cause a disruption of normal neuronal signal transmission as well as the flow of blood and cerebrospinal fluids (Bliesener and Schmidt, 1980; Coll et al., 2015; Kruff and Jeffs, 1966; Richards and Jabbour, 2011; Rijken et al., 2015; Williams, 2008). These conditions may lead to a wide range of clinical symptoms that vary in severity, including ventricular enlargement, hydrocephaly, cerebellar tonsil ectopia, respiratory and electrophysiological problems, and even sudden death (Fremion et al., 1984; Nelson et al., 1984; Pauli et al., 1984; Stokes et al., 1983). Consequently, this promotes the idea of negative selection against significantly small FM dimensions, which have an increased risk of constraining vital hydro- and hemodynamical functions due to the lack of available space, as

seen in syndromic achondroplasia patients with significantly small, abnormal FM dimensions (Richards and Jabbour, 2011; Rijken et al., 2015). Identifying the evolutionary constraints for excessively large FMs, on the other hand, is more complicated. According to the data obtained from patients with Arnold-Chiari malformations, it is known that particularly large FMs are not significantly correlated with tonsillar brain herniation through the foramen and outside the cranial brain cavity (Rijken et al., 2015). In fact, excessively large FMs might even give a positive advantage in the case of abnormally high and rising intracranial pressure, as it facilitates more space for spatial compensation and can help to better maintain proper hemo- and hydrodynamic flow functions. Hence, large FMs would help to prevent, reduce, or release building-up pressure. Taken by itself, an individual's fitness is likely not negatively affected by larger FM dimensions. However, in regard to spatial integration within the cranial base, a large FM size might be constrained by neighboring, tightly packed tissues and structures that require their own space (Richards and Jabbour, 2011).

This evolutionary hypothesis about the constrained size and shape spectrum of the FM is supported by the findings of Gruber and colleagues (2009), who studied 111 European specimens ranging from 30,000 years BP to the present day. Their results suggest that the FMB only slightly increased over time, whereas the FML showed an unclear temporal change pattern that the authors could not relate to secular trends. They therefore conclude that there is little to no secular size change in the FM over time. This is interesting considering that FM size has been reported to be significantly correlated with body height by Gilbe et al. (2020), for which secular trends are well-known (Jaeger et al., 1998; Little, 2020). On the other hand, Röthig (1971) did not find a significant positive correlation between FM and body height. The size and shape of the FM have rarely been studied with respect to the entire occipital bone (Zhang and Schepartz, 2021). However, there is some evidence that the size of the occiput and FM in primates and humans is associated with brain size (Radinsky, 1967) and the size of the spinal cord (MacLarnon, 1996) to some extent. Although the evolutionary allometric trajectories of the latter are still widely unknown (Zhang and Schepartz, 2021).

Thus, FM dimensions are restricted to a relatively narrow spectrum, resulting in an overall large intra- and interpopulation overlap. Based on the results of this and other studies, it can be approximated that the optimal size dimensions for FML and FMB in modern humans range between 29 mm and 44 mm (15 mm) as well as 24 mm and 42 mm (18 mm), respectively. The optimal shape of the FM is round to ovoid. Although this is a relatively limited spectrum, it appears that there are small mean trends visible in the FM shape variation among human populations. These differences are best observed between the wide but short FMs in Asians and the narrower but elongated FMs in African populations. The reasons for this observation are currently unknown but could be related to external environmental factors. This is supported by a broad-geographical study based on the subsample of the large craniometric Howells dataset ($n = 707$), in which a significantly positive Pearson's correlation ($r(4) =$

0.94423, $p < 0.05$) between the length of the FM and geographical latitude was found (Tran, 2020; note that FMB was not studied because Howells did not measure this variable). Human populations from northern, colder latitudes (e.g., Inugsuk Inuit people from Greenland, Buriat people from Siberia) showed systematically higher FML distances than populations from lower latitudes with more temperate climates (e.g., Egyptians, Dogon people, both from Africa). Furthermore, their study showed that FML variation is more driven by population than by sex and not by their interaction. According to these authors, interpopulation variability in the FML may reflect local population adaptations based on body heat regulation (i.e., Bergmann's rule predicting higher body robusticity in cold-adapted populations (Bergmann, 1847)). However, no further reasoning is discussed for this interpretation; hence, additional research is necessary to account for associations between the FM and other body structures (e.g., overall body height and volumetric brain size) to make reliable statements on whether the FM is indeed climatically adapted to temperature (or other environmental proxies).

6. Study Limitations

One of the aims of the present study was to improve current osteometric FM research practices; however, it is not free from methodological limitations itself. The largest limitation was the small number of individuals within multiple subgroups, most notably the sex-pooled and sex-separated Japanese sub-datasets. Although only a restricted number of specimens were available for the remaining three population sample sets, their internal FM variation patterns resembled those observed in previously studied populations and sexed subgroups. This increases the confidence that these subsamples are overall representative of their underlying true populations.

Secondly, this study had to rely on visual sex determination, as clinical documentation for each individual does not exist for the majority of the anthropological collections in Berlin. Although the skull is known as the second most useful structure for sex estimation (Gapert et al., 2013), subjective morphognostic estimations represent a source of error. Therefore, great effort was made to reduce the potential intraobserver error. First, by comparing the new sexing results with those of previous observers, and secondly, by labeling sexually indistinguishable crania ($n = 15$) as such and subsequently excluding them from the intrapopulation analysis. However, this resulted in even smaller subsample sizes per population. In almost all four populations, sex-unidentified individuals tend to cluster in the middle of the population range. Furthermore, the inclusion of these specimens in the interpopulation analysis did not severely impact the statistical results and graphical data distributions between the entire and sex-known datasets. Likewise, the results of the present study widely reproduced patterns seen among the published FM literature, and the line of reasoning did not lead to paradoxical contradictions.

Considering these findings, the sexing does not seem to be heavily biased, as the results were not substantially affected or distorted.

The original data used in this study cannot be considered on its own as representative of broader geographical regions. However, the variation patterns obtained from the 2D and 3D analyses aligned well within the small trends present in the considerably large reference dataset available, which covers a wide geographic range. Hence, the inclusion of more data points and missing populations in blind spots on the world map is not likely to change the overall results of the current data.

Data sharing practices are widely lacking among FM studies. Not a single study was found that shared their underlying FM data. Likewise, key statistical metrics are often missing in the results sections. Thus, detailed meta-analyses for osteometric FM research are difficult, if not impossible, to conduct. This is not only a limitation of the present study but also for the entire FM research field, as results must be blindly trusted. Given the identified methodological flaws and biases embedded and still widely applied in FM research, previous results should be systematically evaluated and treated with greater caution so as not to reproduce cross-study errors and biases.

Lastly, as only FM data was collected in this study, no inferences about its relation to other cranial structures or environmental proxies were possible. This may have helped to better evaluate the sources of the restricted global FM variation.

7. Outlook for Future Research on the FM

Keeping in mind the limitations of FM studies, this thesis included that future works should consider analyzing larger sample sets to reduce biases and make their raw data publicly available to increase good scientific practice and its transparency. Regarding the identification of unknown human remains based on FM measurements, it has been noted that the inclusion of more specimens will likely not result in significantly higher correct classification accuracy rates above circa 70%, as reported by previous studies (Toneva et al., 2018). Multivariate analysis, including data from several anatomical features, might lead to somewhat higher accuracy rates in statistical discrimination attempts. Lastly, it is recommended to consider and apply the critiques that have been raised here and elsewhere on the usage of visual shape categories and metric index values (Richards and Jabbour, 2011; Toneva et al., 2018; Zdilla et al., 2017).

Instead, future studies should aim to identify the underlying reasons for the constitution of the FM shape and form in relation to cultural and environmental interplay with genetic factors. Results drawn from such studies might also help to explain the observed slight mean trends among populations. It would also be advantageous to test previous notions, such as

that the FM is less significantly affected by muscle-induced biomechanical forces (Ukoha et al., 2011) or secular trends (Gruber et al., 2009), that have often been cited but not yet systematically tested using larger and geographically more diverse reference samples. Furthermore, methodological differences and errors between different data collection methods should be revised, as there is evidence that they have the potential to produce different results when applied to the same specimens, which interferes with their comparability. There are several studies estimating differences in the consistency, reliability, and accuracy of landmark collection methods using dry bones and virtual models. Whereas some studies did not find substantial differences between dry bone and virtual (e.g., CT) measurements and landmark placements (Carew et al., 2019; Corron et al., 2017; Franklin et al., 2013; Nagashima et al., 1998; Shearer et al., 2017), others have (Colman et al., 2019). Reasons for these contradictory results might depend on the respective measurements, the exact methods and protocols used to generate and extract virtual 3D models, as well as the resolution of the scanning device (Carew et al., 2019; Nagashima et al., 1998). Some studies suggest that radiological, CT-based models yield slightly higher error rates than 3D models created from light- or laser-based optical surface scans when compared to measurements taken from dry bones, which are used as the gold standard in this comparison (Colman et al., 2019). This idea is supported by the estimation of the measurement precisions of the 3D Artec models in this study, which reveal overall negligible differences between physical and virtual measurements. In order to keep cumulative measurement error rates low (Colman et al., 2019), future studies focusing on FM morphology, especially when they rely on CT data, should keep this in mind and, if necessary, apply proper size correction factors to accurately rescale the image data.

The influence of the AOCs has not been addressed in greater detail, as the newly defined landmark configuration aimed to not account for their influence on the FM. As the AOCs protrude into the FM space in up to 20% of all individuals (Chethan et al., 2012; Murshed et al., 2003; Muthukumar et al., 2005), it would be interesting to specifically test their influential effect on FM shape assessments and estimations. The differences in the GM results between this study and Zdilla et al. (2017) may be partially related to the landmark configurations used. Whereas the present study aimed to exclude the protruding influence of the condyles in three dimensions, this was not possible in Zdilla's GM study, where semilandmark data was collected from planar photographs. Despite this, the results appeared to be relatively similar. Thus, it would be more interesting to analyze the covariation between those integrated and other related basicranial structures using 3D GM approaches. The degree of bending and building of the FM in a 3D lateral profile perspective, which has probably not been observed before, could not be addressed in more detail in this study due to the lack of reference information but is worth further investigation within the framework of morphological integration.

8. Summary and Conclusion

1) What is the current state of FM research, and what are the underlying problems that might bias FM study results?

To answer the first research question, the present study summarized methodological biases and persisting problems in FM research and gave recommendations to account for these issues. It has been demonstrated that common approaches to describing the shape of the FM using visual assessment or a numeric index metric are insufficiently applied and biased across studies. Cross-study comparisons of FM results from this data are therefore widely limited. Traditional attempts to classify the shape of the FM using distinct visual categories should be completely avoided in the future. Likewise, the use of the foramen magnum index should also be avoided when possible. Instead, landmark data and GM methods can be used to accurately quantify and analyze the metric shape of the FM.

2) Does the size, shape, and/or form of the FM differ between sexes and/or populations?

The results of this study include both previously published and newly generated osteometric 2D and 3D data of the FM which indicate that the absolute differences between sexes and populations are considerably small. Although a few groups from this study and other studies show significant differences between the average size dimensions between females and males, these distinctions are imposed by the large overlapping ranges visible in both sexes. The first null hypothesis of no significant differences in all measured variables between sexes per population ($H_{0.1}$) could not be rejected in this study. Small, mostly insignificant size, shape, and form differences of the FM have also been documented between different populations from different continents. The second null hypothesis ($H_{0.2}$), no significant differences in all FM variables between populations, also could not be rejected.

3) Which variable, or which type of osteometric data (2D linear measurements or 3D sliding semilandmarks) better separates sexes and/or populations statistically?

With regards to the consistent 2D and 3D size, and shape trends seen in the variation of the FM between human groups, this study also demonstrated that the results of the 3D landmark-based GM approach are not fundamentally different from those obtained by the 2D osteometric analysis.

4) Can the FM be reliably used to accurately infer the population affinity and sex of unknown human remains?

Based on the findings of the previous research questions, neither traditional osteometric nor geometric morphometric properties of the FM can be considered particularly valuable to estimate the sex and/or population affinity of skeletal human remains. Any

application of FM-based classification to highly fragmented remains should acknowledge the overall high shape and size similarities among humans.

Taken together, it can be concluded that the adult shape and form of the FM in modern humans appear to be most affected by genetic factors that regulate the phenotypic expression of the FM during ontogenetic development, although the underlying processes are still widely unknown. No muscular forces act on the bony FM, as it exclusively serves as a passageway for vital neurocranial tissues that connect the brain with the spinal cord. A large divergence from the normal range in shape and size of the FM may have fatal consequences under certain clinical and pathological conditions, thereby reducing the overall fitness of affected humans and resulting in a negative selection of dysfunctional large or small FM dimensions. This is supported by the observation that the morphology of the FM has not significantly changed since the late Pleistocene. It is therefore reasonable to assume that FM is a functionally well-adapted and evolutionary stable trait, which, in consequence, results in overall high intra- and interpopulation FM similarities across human groups. However, small interpopulation mean trends in the FM shape are visible, which might be caused by the interplay between genetic and environmental (epigenetic) as well as habitual-cultural influences rather than sex-based factors. The underlying developmental and epigenetic processes that regulate the growth and constitution of FM size and shape, however, are not yet well known.

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Das Ende